

Structural Information Flow: A Fresh Look at Types for Non-interference

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Information flow control is a long-studied approach for establishing *non-interference* properties of programs. For instance, it can be used to prove that a secret does not interfere with some computation, thereby establishing that the former does not leak through the latter. Despite their potential as a holy grail for security reasoning and their maturity within the literature, information flow type systems have seen limited adoption. In practice, information flow specifications tend to be excessively complex and can easily spiral out of control even for simple programs. Additionally, while non-interference is well-behaved in an idealized setting where information leakage never occurs, most practical programs *must* violate non-interference in order to fulfill their purpose. Useful information flow type systems in prior work must therefore contend with a definition of non-interference extended with *declassification*, which often offers weaker modular reasoning properties.

We introduce *structural information flow*, which both illuminates and addresses these issues from a logical viewpoint. In particular, we draw on established insights from the modal logic literature to argue that information flow reasoning arises from *hybrid logic*, rather than conventional modal logic as previously imagined. We show with a range of examples that structural information flow specifications are straightforward to write and easy to visually parse. Uniquely in the structural setting, we demonstrate that declassification emerges not as an aberration to non-interference, but as a *natural* and *unavoidable* consequence of sufficiently general machinery for information flow. This flavor of declassification features excellent local reasoning and enables our approach to account for real-world information flow needs without compromising its theoretical elegance. Finally, we establish non-interference via a logical relations approach, showing off its simplicity in the face of the expressive power captured.

CCS Concepts: • **Security and privacy** → **Information flow control**; • **Theory of computation** → *Modal and temporal logics*; Proof theory; • **Software and its engineering** → *Polymorphism*.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: information flow, security types, confidentiality, polarity, fine-grained, coarse-grained, dependency tracking, modal logic, polymorphism, declassification, existential quantification

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1 Introduction

Information flow control has long captured the interest of security researchers everywhere for its unique ability to establish *non-interference* [Goguen and Meseguer 1982], a powerful property which states that programs satisfying it cannot be manipulated to reveal sensitive information to untrusted parties. For instance, an e-mail notification system should never disclose password

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data, so password processing should not interfere with the execution of the former. Types are the dominant mechanism for enforcing non-interference owing to its status as a *hyperproperty* [McLean 1996]—a question about a program that can only be answered by comparing *multiple* traces of its evaluation. Due to their innate ability to reason simultaneously over all possible program executions, type systems might be expected to offer a straightforward path to discharging non-interference invariants.

However, even in the face of their potential to stem the avalanche of security compromises faced by the computer industry, existing information flow systems have seen limited adoption. Current approaches to information flow reasoning burden programmers with complex specifications and inadequately modular mechanics. In this paper, we argue that the reasons for these deficiencies can be both explained and remedied with time-tested intuitions from the literature on modal logic, within which information flow has previously been couched [Miyamoto and Igarashi 2004]. The system crafted from this process, which we call *structural information flow*, is simpler and easier to use both for metatheory and for program reasoning despite being expressive enough to support practical programs. We start this paper with a brief introduction to information flow, requiring only some familiarity with statically typed functional programming as a prerequisite.

1.1 An Opinionated Crash Course in Information Flow

Programmers often express information flow properties—without any access to purpose-built systems for doing so—by leveraging parametric polymorphism [Reynolds 1984].¹ A simple example is the polymorphic identity function. The typing $\text{id} : \alpha \rightarrow \alpha$ specifies that the return value must depend only on the data given as input. Likewise, the typing $\text{second} : \alpha \rightarrow \beta \rightarrow \beta$ expresses that its return value must depend only on its second argument. For a more interesting example, consider the typing of the standard map function on lists given here. The polymorphic components are the

$$\text{let map} : (\alpha \rightarrow \beta) \rightarrow \text{list } \alpha \rightarrow \text{list } \beta$$

list elements, so this type communicates that the elements of the input list are permitted to flow into the higher-order argument, and that the elements of the output list depend on the return value of that argument. All three of these types express *information flow* properties: for a given computation, they relate its inputs to its outputs. However, these types also express *data abstraction* properties: $\text{id} : \alpha \rightarrow \alpha$ expresses that the function should be able to be given an input at any type and return data at that same type. Both properties are consequences of *parametricity*, which states that not only does the argument flow to the return value, but that exactly the argument is returned.

Parametricity is quite useful, but its sheer strength greatly limits the range of programs we can write under it. What if we want to continue tracking information flow, but do not want to keep data abstract? For instance, we might like to write a function that takes as argument an integer, adds one to it, and returns it. We cannot, however, add one to data at type α because it is not known to be a number. Our first core intuition is that **parametric polymorphism offers two distinct features**, both (1) **providing data abstraction** and (2) **enforcing information flow properties**. We want to isolate the second, so let us try tagging types with *dependency variables* like α , rather than having α be the type. Under this proposal, we might type the successor function on integers as $\alpha \text{ int} \rightarrow \alpha \text{ int}$. The α no longer has any role in data abstraction, but merely tracks the *identity* of the data—that is, on which data it depends. Note that this is distinct from the α in $\text{list } \alpha$, which permits the list to be generic over the type of its contents.

We are better off now than we were before—we can do interesting computation with data whose information flow content is being tracked—but are not quite there yet. For instance, try to write

¹As distinguished from *ad hoc* polymorphism; the distinction is detailed in Strachey [2000].

down the information flow type of the addition function. We would like to be able to state that it takes two integers as arguments and returns an integer dependent on both. We can start out by writing $\text{add} : \alpha \text{ int} \rightarrow \beta \text{ int} \rightarrow \boxed{?}$. What should go in the $\boxed{?}$? Our current syntax is constrained to mention a single dependency per type, so we seem to be stuck. We can fix this by generalizing our type-level dependency variables to being **sets of dependency variables**. This is the other core intuition behind our system. We set $\boxed{?} = [\alpha \ \beta] \text{ int}$, which can be read as “this **int** depends on data from sources α and β .” The resulting typing for addition is shown by `add`. The dependency

```
let add : [  $\alpha$  ] int -> [  $\beta$  ] int -> [  $\alpha \ \beta$  ] int
```

variables on the arguments have also been turned into dependency sets for consistency. Keep in mind that these type signatures are polymorphic: now that we have generalized beyond single variables to sets of variables within our types, each variable in the set can be instantiated to another *set of variables*. Just as the α in $\alpha \rightarrow \alpha$ can be instantiated to **int** to obtain $\text{int} \rightarrow \text{int}$, the α in `add` can be instantiated to `[secret1 secret2]`, representing data depending on some secrets. `add1` shows the resulting typing, taking as a first argument an integer dependent on concrete sources `secret1` and `secret2`. It returns an integer dependent on `secret1`, `secret2`, and β .

```
let add1 : [ secret1 secret2 ] int -> [  $\beta$  ] int -> [ secret1 secret2  $\beta$  ] int
```

We haven't yet performed any meaningful information flow reasoning—what might a specification for preventing secret leakage look like in this setting? We consider below a simple password checker. We start by declaring some password data `pass`, which is a **string** tagged with `pwd` to indicate it contains password data. We assume `pwd` is in scope but defer detailing the mechanisms used to introduce it. Our checking function `check` takes a **string**—a password attempt—at any dependencies and returns a **bool** tagged with those dependencies and `pwd`, indicating whether the attempt was correct. This all seems to be as expected: the return value of `check` is dependent on

```
let pass : [ pwd ] string = "katya"
let check : [  $\alpha$  ] string -> [  $\alpha$  pwd ] bool = fun attempt -> attempt == pass
```

both its argument and `pass`, being the result of comparing them, so the type of the return value states exactly the same. If our purpose is to usefully detect whether password data is at risk of leaking, though, this seems too conservative: it is necessary to the function of the password checker that its boolean return value is permitted to leak.

Of course, it is intuitively a violation of non-interference to leak an arbitrary **bool** dependent on password data: consider the case where a function of the same type as `check` returns the n th bit of the password as a boolean value, where n is the length of the argument string. Unexpectedly, we will be able to give `check`—that is, this and only this implementation of `check`—the type $[\alpha] \text{ string} \rightarrow [\alpha] \text{ bool}$. Section 4 will reveal precisely how. For a final example, consider the function `f`. What must $\boxed{?}$ be?

```
let f : [  $\alpha$  ] bool -> [ ] bool =  $\boxed{?}$ 
```

The punchline of this paper, to be delivered in full in Section 5, will be that `f` must be constant in its argument. This is due to recovering non-interference as a flavor of parametricity over dependency variables. In fact, *any* function where the input dependency set is not a subset of the output must be the constant function. And with that, we conclude our introduction: the basic

notions we have introduced are all that will be needed for the structural information flow setting. The rest of this paper will elucidate the seemingly straightforward choices we have just made, grounding and justifying them via well-understood logical foundations and showing that the system created by these choices is expressive enough to capture information flow issues arising in the wild. In particular, the aforementioned desirable typing of check will turn out not to require any extensions. This is not the case with other approaches, which call this behavior *declassification* and add constructs to allow violations of non-interference. This often obstructs modular reasoning.

1.2 A Preview of the Rest

[Section 2](#) will reveal that the language we have set up is a variant of hybrid logic. We have just discussed how to arrive at this language from parametric polymorphism, but it is also possible to find the way there by drawing on logical intuitions. We describe how to arrive at our setting beginning from prior work grounding information flow in conventional modal logic. [Section 3](#) explores a number of further examples, touching on several subtle details of our system that significantly aid the straightforward and succinct nature of our information flow specifications. This is detailed by comparing to equivalent programs written in systems without our insights. [Section 4](#) introduces declassification by example, solving our issue with check above. [Section 5](#) discusses the typing rules, comparing to those for hybrid logic and discussing the simple logical relations argument with which non-interference can be validated in our setting. [Section 6](#) compares to other work investigating either declassification or the foundations of information flow. We conclude in [Section 7](#). Our contributions are the following:

- (1) We clarify and **re-cast the foundations of information flow** in the light of **hybrid logic** [[Prior 1968](#)], a well-studied generalization of modal logic designed around concerns we will show throughout this paper to be fundamental to information flow reasoning.
- (2) We show that the design intuition imparted by hybrid logic has the potential to **simplify information flow specifications**. We extoll the virtues of performing information flow reasoning in terms of *dependency sets*, inspired by hybrid logic's *world paths*. We touch on the important role played by the proof-theoretic concept of *polarity* in determining the granularity of dependency tracking.
- (3) Remarkably, the quantification machinery suggested by hybrid logic **realizes declassification fully internally** to the system. That is, our theory neither makes any explicit mention of declassification nor needs to be extended to support it. We remark on the nature of this as **computationally relevant information flow policies**.
- (4) Our metatheory and proof of non-interference inherit the elegance and simplicity of the programmer-facing side of our system. Namely, we show how our logical relation inherently supports **non-interference reasoning in the presence of declassification**, automatically ignoring disequalities resulting from declassification by writ of quantification.

By the end of this paper, we will have taken the initial steps towards bringing to bear the full-throated no-concessions-made variant of non-interference as a practical—even desirable—regime under which to write secure programs.

2 Background, Logic, and Typing

Having introduced one way of arriving at the structural approach to information flow starting from ordinary functional programming, we will now reveal another starting from constructive modal logic. It will turn out that *hybrid logic* [[Prior 1968](#)], a generalization of modal logic, provides a more robust foundation for information flow reasoning than the standard modal setting in which most prior work has been cast. In particular, we will show that hybrid logic has been designed around a

number of considerations critical to information flow reasoning. We start by reviewing programs written under a more standard theory of information flow, then elaborate its logical structure in the subsections that follow.

2.1 Introduction: Round Two

Let us revisit the examples from the introduction within a conventional theory of information flow in order to build intuition. In particular, our examples are lightly inspired by the syntax of Flow Caml [Pottier and Simonet 2002], an information flow system for OCaml. Figure 1 compares the typing of the identity function on integers between our approach and a standard one.

```
let id : [  $\alpha$  ] int -> [  $\alpha$  ] int (* Ours *)
let id' :  $\alpha$  int ->  $\alpha$  int      (* Theirs *)
```

Fig. 1. Similar-looking types...

They look pretty similar. In fact, the standard typing looks much like ours did before we generalized from singular variables to *sets* of variables. How, then, might we type addition?

```
let add : [  $\alpha$  ] int -> [  $\beta$  ] int -> [  $\alpha \beta$  ] int      (* Ours *)
let add' :  $\alpha$  int ->  $\beta$  int ->  $\delta$  int with  $\alpha, \beta \leq \delta$  (* Theirs *)
```

Fig. 2. A first sighting of lattice constraints

Here, we catch our first sighting of the *lattice constraints* which ordinarily comprise information flow specifications [Denning 1976]. At the point in our prior exploration where we chose to generalize to sets of dependency variables rather than individual dependency variables for typing add, two roads diverged—and we took the one less traveled by. The other option was to add additional structure to the variables themselves, transforming them into elements from a *semilattice* rather than leaving them inert. This is the more common option, so we review it here.

A semilattice has one primitive operation: *join*, written \sqcup . We can join two dependency variables α and β by writing $\alpha \sqcup \beta$, returning another dependency variable. The returned variable is interpreted to be greater than or equal to both α and β —specifically the *least* such variable. That is, \sqcup generates a partial ordering \sqsubseteq over the carrier set of dependency variables. $\alpha \sqsubseteq \beta$ means that α can be joined with other variables to produce β —in other words, β represents information from α . $\alpha \sqsubseteq \beta$ allows us to compare two dependency variables α and β to check if data from α is permitted to flow to β .

We use both operators in the type for add, writing \sqcup syntactically as a comma ‘,’ and writing \sqsubseteq syntactically as \leq . So we can parse the contents of the **with** clause as $(\alpha \sqcup \beta) \sqsubseteq \delta$, or in natural language, “both α and β must be able to flow to δ .” The dependency variable for the return value is δ , and flows to the return value can be specified by way of partial orderings which place δ above other variables representing input information. When this function is called, the caller must instantiate α, β , and δ —just as we previously set $\alpha = [\text{secret1 secret2}]$ in our typing for add1 in Section 1.1—with concrete variables such that the two *former* variables are *both ordered less* than the *latter* one. This will satisfy the type constraints because \sqcup is guaranteed to yield the least variable higher than both operands—so no higher than the instantiation of δ . As an aside, note that all this constraint information must be digested by programmers to appreciate the type of add', rather than relying on existing intuitions surrounding parametric polymorphism as in Section 1.1. The argument for the simplicity of the latter is already taking shape. Note that lattice-based systems ordinarily deploy *simplification algorithms* which attempt to elide constraints from types. We hold off on applying these until the next section to avoid obscuring the fundamental mechanics.

While picking through the above definitions, you may have noticed something curious. Our sets of dependency variables also have semilattice structure! Join is given by set union, which induces the partial order given by subset inclusion. When two sets are unioned, another set is produced which has exactly the elements needed to be the superset of both, and no more. This structure is known as the *free* semilattice in algebra. *Free* indicates that it is the *simplest possible way* to arrive at a semilattice starting with some carrier set—of dependency variables, in our case. We simply make each element of the set of variables into a singleton set to create the smallest elements of our semilattice, and apply set union to generate more elements until we reach closure. This is analogous to taking the power set of the carrier. Where before we used $\alpha_1 \leq \alpha_2$ to denote that data from source α_1 flowed to destination α_2 , we now have $[\alpha \beta]$ to mean that data from sources $[\alpha]$ and $[\beta]$ —subsets of the former—flowed into that destination.

Sharing the same algebraic structure does not collapse the two approaches into one, however—far from it. As we will show in [Section 3](#) and [Section 4](#), the choice to use the free semilattice in our setting has made all the difference. But we are not yet prepared to discuss why. For now, let us review a final example from the prior section under a conventional information flow system. The retyped password checker is shown in [Figure 3](#).

```

let pass : [ pwd ] string = "katya"           (* Ours *)
let check : [  $\alpha$  ] string -> [  $\alpha$  pwd ] bool =
  fun attempt -> attempt == pass
let pass' : pwd string = "katya"            (* Theirs *)
let check' :  $\alpha$  string ->  $\beta$  bool with  $\alpha$ , pwd <=  $\beta$  =
  fun attempt -> attempt == pass

```

Fig. 3. Comparing Our Password Checkers

The situation is much the same as in [Figure 2](#). We must somehow betray in the return type of `check'` that it depends on `pwd` data. We can achieve this by specifying that the variable annotating the return type must be ordered greater than `pwd`. The flow from the argument α is accounted for exactly as before. We look now to the mechanics underlying both flavors of information flow.

2.2 Reconstructing Information Flow via Hybrid Logic

The standard approach to information flow can be recovered from constructive modal logic [[Pfenning and Davies 2001](#)] by way of *partial necessity* [[Nanevski 2004](#)], which provides an account of indexed \Box (modal necessity) connectives. [Miyamoto and Igarashi \[2004\]](#) follow this approach, indexing the \Box operator with elements ℓ from a semilattice. It is common [[Abadi et al. 1999](#); [Choudhury et al. 2022](#); [Liu et al. 2024](#); [Shikuma and Igarashi 2008](#); [Tse and Zdancewic 2004](#)] to furthermore eliminate the necessity semantics and transition to a *lax modality* [[Fairtlough and Mendler 1997](#)] by admitting extra axioms on \Box_ℓ . The \Box_ℓ connective is kept around, because it is indexed with information flow machinery ℓ , but retains none of its original purpose within modal logic. We cannot provide the full story here—it is provided in [Gouni et al. \[2025, Appendix A\]](#) for the interested reader—but alternative, cleaner logical foundations are possible.

We will describe how to arrive at the structural approach starting at constructive modal logic as before. Modal logic was originally designed around reasoning about the possible states of affair, or configurations of reality, that can be reached from our current one. These states are known as worlds. $\Box A$ can be read as “in all reachable worlds, the proposition A will be true”. In usual presentations of modal logic, reachability of worlds is defined by a relation—which in our case will be a partial order \sqsubseteq —on worlds ℓ , where $\ell_1 \sqsubseteq \ell_2$ means that ℓ_2 is reachable from ℓ_1 . This is called a

Kripke semantics and is separate from the syntax of modal logic, underlying it. Partial necessity as previously mentioned can be deployed to pull—or internalize—worlds into the syntax of the logic by indexing \Box with worlds ℓ : each world-indexed necessitation \Box_ℓ identifies the world ℓ at whose accessible worlds it is true. In other words, in order to access some information at world ℓ , the current world ℓ' must have accounted for ℓ as a dependency— ℓ' must be reachable from ℓ in the semantics. The first core insight here is that **information flow variables denote worlds**. Worlds hold a special place at the heart of modal reasoning, though, and partial necessity offers little insight about them—it is oblivious to the fact that it is working with world indices.

This is a job for *hybrid logic* [Prior 1968], an alternative approach to generalizing standard modal logic *designed around internal reasoning about worlds*. Hybrid logic reifies worlds as a first-class syntactic construct rather than leaving them implicit in the semantic realm or judgemental structure, or relegating them to an index into an existing connective. It does this via a *satisfaction operator* $@_w A$ read as “at world w , proposition A should be true.” The usual introduction and elimination rules for $@_w A$ are given in red in Figure 4. The form of the typing judgement is $\Gamma \vdash M : A [\phi]$ and can be read “Under assumptions Γ , expression M has type A at world ϕ .”

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \textcircled{I} \\
 \frac{\Gamma \vdash M : A [\phi]}{\Gamma \vdash M : @_{\phi} A [\phi']} \\
 \\
 \textcircled{E} \\
 \frac{\Gamma \vdash M : @_{\phi} A [\phi']}{\Gamma \vdash M : A [\phi]} \\
 \\
 \textcircled{E-NEW} \\
 \frac{\Gamma \vdash M : @_{\phi} A [\phi']}{\Gamma \vdash M : A [\phi * \phi']}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \textcircled{I} \\
 \frac{\Gamma \vdash M : A [\phi]}{\Gamma \vdash M : @_{\phi} A [\phi']} \\
 \\
 \textcircled{E} \\
 \frac{\Gamma \vdash M : @_{\phi} A [\phi']}{\Gamma \vdash M : A [\phi]} \\
 \\
 \textcircled{E-NEW} \\
 \frac{\Gamma \vdash M : A [\phi] \quad \phi \sqsubseteq \phi * \phi'}{\Gamma \vdash M : A [\phi * \phi']} \text{SUB}
 \end{array}$$

Fig. 4. Satisfaction in Hybrid Logic and its Soundness

This setup is adapted from Reed [2009]. Rather than abstract world variables ℓ , the worlds in these rules consist of elements ϕ of a *free commutative monoid* generated from a set of atomic world variables $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n$. That is, $\phi = \alpha_1 * \alpha_2 * \dots * \alpha_i$. This is quite close to a semilattice, which is what we need for information flow. It is lacking only idempotency, or the property that $\alpha * \alpha = \alpha$, so we add it to turn each ϕ into an element of a *free semilattice*. The join operation \sqcup is given by set union \cup as described in Section 2.1. There are variants of hybrid logic which do not represent the structure of worlds using a free monoid or semilattice, but the guiding intuition behind hybrid logic is to pull as much of this structure as possible into the syntax. Elements from a parameterized semilattice ℓ and ℓ' have no meaning except that provided externally, outside the syntax, but join in a free semilattice $(\alpha * \beta) \sqcup \delta = \alpha * \beta * \delta$ is immediate from the notation of each element. The next section will show that this choice simplifies specifications; the section after will place it at the heart of a sound and compositional declassification mechanism.

We are not quite at a system suitable for information flow yet. We would like to be able to state that M has dependencies ϕ at type A —something akin to $\Box_\ell A$ —by saying $@_\phi A$, but it turns out this will not quite suffice. The problem is the \textcircled{E} rule, which wholesale replaces the current world ϕ' with the ϕ inside the satisfaction operator. For information flow, we need to keep track of the old world, as well. We must not forget the ambient security level! Our second core insight comes from Pfenning and Davies [2001], who suggest a solution in the form of *world paths*. **World paths keep track of the history of your traversals through worlds**, or the sequence of worlds you have ‘walked through’. We update the elimination rule to $\textcircled{E-NEW}$, which now preserves the old world *path* ϕ' and joins it with the world *path* ϕ obtained by eliminating the satisfaction operator. Each

dependency α in the judgemental ϕ is a world previously traversed and so recorded on the path. For subtle reasons elucidated in Gouni et al. [2025, Appendix A] and by Nanevski [2004], no notion of necessity exists in this connective. In short, indexing the necessity connective with modal worlds, as with other approaches, precludes its removal. By instead using hybrid logic to syntactically reify worlds, the core machinery for information flow emerges as a matter of *satisfaction*.²

Note that @E-NEW is no longer symmetric to @I. This appears to break local soundness, as shown in the second row of Figure 4. The issue is that reducing away pairs of introductory and eliminatory rule applications should not change the type A or world ϕ in a way that is unachievable through the other rules of the logic—that is, introduction followed by elimination does not let us prove anything we could not before. This obviously holds for @I and @E, as evidenced by the leftmost derivation, but not when the latter is replaced with @E-new, producing an extra ϕ' in the conclusion. Local soundness is retained via a subsumption rule SUB which permits the $M : A [\phi]$ at the top of each of the first two derivations to be used directly to prove $M : A [\phi * \phi']$. A different solution arises from exploiting the proof-theoretic concept of *polarity*. This is the strategy we will adopt when setting up our type system in Section 5.1. But in either case, local soundness is retained.

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \text{VAR} \frac{\text{pass} : [\text{pwd}] \text{ string} \in \dots}{\dots \vdash \text{pass} : [\text{pwd}] \text{ string} [\alpha]} \quad \text{VAR} \frac{\text{attempt} : [\alpha] \text{ string} \in \dots}{\dots \vdash \text{attempt} : [\alpha] \text{ string} [\text{pwd}]} \\
 \text{@E-NEW} \frac{\dots \vdash \text{pass} : [\text{pwd}] \text{ string} [\alpha]}{\dots \vdash \text{pass} : \text{string} [\alpha * \text{pwd}]} \quad \text{@E-NEW} \frac{\dots \vdash \text{attempt} : [\alpha] \text{ string} [\text{pwd}]}{\dots \vdash \text{attempt} : \text{string} [\alpha * \text{pwd}]} \\
 \hline
 \text{EQUALS} \frac{\text{pass} : [\text{pwd}] \text{ string}, \text{attempt} : [\alpha] \text{ string} \vdash \text{pass} == \text{attempt} : \text{bool} [\alpha * \text{pwd}]}{\text{pass} : [\text{pwd}] \text{ string}, \text{attempt} : [\alpha] \text{ string} \vdash \text{pass} == \text{attempt} : [\alpha \text{ pwd}] \text{ bool} [\epsilon]} \text{@I}
 \end{array}$$

Fig. 5. Derivation for the Body of check

Hybrid logic will offer one more fundamental insight, but before that, we have roughly all the tools we need to work through the body of check from Figure 3, shown in Figure 5. We will assume a typing for a comparison operator which requires both of its arguments to be at the same world path, and a variable rule which permits variables to be typed at any world. The syntax $[\delta \beta] A$ is interpreted as a satisfaction operator, namely $@_{\delta * \beta} A$. We use ϵ for the empty world path following Reed [2009]. Reading from the bottom of the derivation, we start by applying @I—reading the rule itself bottom-up—to extract the **bool** from the satisfaction operator. We then apply our imagined equality rule, producing a goal for each operand. For the left goal, we continue bottom-up by applying @E-new to give us **pass** at type $[\text{pwd}] \text{ string}$, drawing **pwd** from the world path in its conclusion. We finish with the variable rule. The right operand is analogous.

What is the final affordance of the hybrid setting? From the logic perspective, one of the primary motivations for hybrid logic is in its explicit treatment of quantification over worlds. From the information flow side, observe in the examples we have seen the prevalence of quantification—or polymorphism—over dependencies. We have not yet written a single program that does not rely on dependency polymorphism, even in introductory cases, and the rest of this paper will not contain any. Generic programming is broadly useful, but in the information flow setting it becomes absolutely essential. An information flow system without polymorphism cannot express useful programs without significant amounts of duplication. You may need to rewrite the same function for almost every single call site, because each usage will likely differ in its information dependencies.

²Satisfaction here is at a *lax* modality [Fairtlough and Mendler 1997; Moggi 1989], due to @E-NEW structuring the judgemental ϕ as an effect [Katsumata 2014]. The latter is connected to possibility [Benton et al. 1998], which becomes *lax* in the absence of necessity [Nanevski 2004, §4.1.1]. Section 5.1 treats this effectful structure via *polarity*.

This is our third and last core insight: **quantification over dependencies is essential and must be a first-class concern**. Hybrid logic will be of assistance one last time, deploying its inbuilt ability to quantify over the worlds in its syntax. The setup for quantification will be both simple yet general enough to let declassification emerge as a consequence.

Observe the parallels between the core insights from the preceding story and those from [Section 1.1](#). Our earlier introduction of dependency sets corresponds to world paths here, and polymorphism (or quantification) shows up fundamentally in both. As promised there, the affordances of our setup—the combination of world paths/dependency sets and quantification/polymorphism—will turn out to be the key to performing declassification in a modular, elegant way. We hold off on discussing these points until [Section 4](#) and [Section 5](#). The next section builds more intuition through a number of examples.

3 More Examples and Subtleties

In this section we review a few potentially subtle details that make the structural approach to information flow easier to use in practice. These do not emerge as ad-hoc heuristics, but are motivated by fundamental affordances bubbled up from the logical and type-theoretic foundations of our system. We start not with a feature we *have*, but with one we *lack*.

3.1 Uniformity, or Absence of Policies

In standard theories of information flow working in terms of an arbitrary semilattice, it is common to tweak the structure of the lattice to model information flow *policies*. For instance, imagine that Alice trusts Bob. We could have a two element semilattice where `alice` \sqcup `bob` = `bob` and so `alice` \leq `bob`. Why is this useful? Functions like in [Figure 6](#) become typable.

```

policy alice <= bob

let expected : bob string = "nemmerle"
let msg_bob : alice string ->  $\alpha$  string ->  $\beta$  string with  $\alpha$ , bob <=  $\beta$  =
  fun alice_secret msg_str ->
    if alice_secret == expected then msg_str else panic

```

Fig. 6. Declaring a Custom Dependency Ordering

This program allows Alice to message Bob by passing `msg_bob` **strings**, which Bob can then read. Alice must provide the correct secret to `msg_bob` so Bob knows it is the right person. There is something odd going on here. We pass data at levels `alice` and `α` as the first two arguments to `msg_bob`. The computation of the function body is certainly dependent on both arguments: `alice_secret` is used in a conditional guard, and `msg_str` is returned from one of its branches. However, the constraints on the return dependency `β` indicate that it only contains data from `α` and `bob`. This is because the `alice` dependency induced by comparing against `alice_secret` in the conditional guard is subsumed by the `bob` dependency induced by the `expected` variable against which it is compared. The policy declares that `alice` can flow into `bob`, so it does.

This can be expressed structurally, but not in this way. In particular, it is not possible in our setting to simply declare a partial ordering on dependencies `[α]` and `[β]`, because our dependencies are *inert*. They have no implicit structure, being determined by their syntax. `[α]` can only be partially ordered less than a dependency set that contains it, like `[α β]`. This means that two dependency sets can be compared for partial ordering at a glance, without having to keep declared policies in working memory. **Our experience is that the usage of orderings which violate the one given**

structurally are the *exception* rather than the *norm*, so should not be applied pervasively for the whole program. Section 4.4 will show a *local, computationally relevant* alternative to the above, leveraging the same machinery as for declassification. We still have not made a strong case for the simplicity of our approach yet. We look to Figure 7 to make it.

```

let alc :  $\alpha$  int  $\rightarrow$   $\alpha$  int
  with alice  $\leq$   $\alpha$ 
let bob :  $\alpha$  int  $\rightarrow$   $\alpha$  int
  with bob  $\leq$   $\alpha$ 

let both :  $\alpha$  int  $\rightarrow$   $\beta$  int *  $\delta$  int
  with bob  $\leq$   $\delta$ 
  and alice  $\leq$   $\beta$ 
  and  $\alpha \leq \beta, \delta$ 
let both x = (alc x, bob x)

let alc : [ $\alpha$ ] int  $\rightarrow$  [ $\alpha$  alice] int
let bob : [ $\alpha$ ] int  $\rightarrow$  [ $\alpha$  bob] int

let both : [ $\alpha$ ] int  $\rightarrow$ 
  [ $\alpha$  alice] int * [ $\alpha$  bob] int
let both x = (alc x, bob x)

```

Fig. 7. Alice and Bob Sharing a Computation

This program moderates flows between Alice and Bob, who want to perform computation together but *do not want their information to be intermingled or revealed to the other*. Looking first to the program on the left, `alc` and `bob` are the functions that represent their computations. Each takes as argument an `int` and mixes either `alice`'s or `bob`'s data into it. This is indicated by the `alice` and `bob` dependencies lower bounding the α dependency in their return types. Note that we are applying *simplification algorithms* in this example. We might have typed `alc` as given for `alc'` below. Instead the simplification algorithm recognizes that whatever the dependency level of

```

let alc' :  $\alpha$  int  $\rightarrow$   $\beta$  int
  with alice,  $\alpha \leq \beta$ 

```

the argument passed to `alc`, it can be raised until it is above `alice`, which loses no generality and preserves the soundness of dependency tracking. Next, the function `both` operationally invokes `alc` and `bob` in each projection of a pair and returns the pair. That this computation respects the desired separation property is not easy to determine from the type, however. We must instead confront a bag of constraints which, once analyzed, will hopefully say what we want.

Looking to the conjoining program on the right, the terms are exactly the same. The types of `alc` and `bob` again state that the return type of each depends on its input and on data from `alice` and `bob`. The indication of this fact with [α alice] is arguably already more direct. We need no simplification algorithms to arrive at this type—it is the only one that accounts for the flows from the argument α and `alice`. The biggest difference is in the type of `both`, which states that data α from its argument flows to each element of the returned pair, and data from `alice` and `bob` flows separately to each projection. From this we immediately know that the separation property we wanted is preserved by `both`. If data from Alice had been passed to Bob, or vice versa, we would see a set [`alice bob` ...] containing dependencies from both. At a glance, we see nothing of the sort. It is of course possible to use `both` to violate the separation property, but this would again be obvious at the callsite; this is in line with prior work [Pottier and Simonet 2002]. Next, we reconsider the heuristic of making fine-grained dependency tracking pervasive.

```

let const : [  $\alpha$  ] int -> [ ] int
let const _ = 10

let alice : [ alice ] int
let alice = 0

let result : [ ? ] int
let result = const alice

```

Fig. 8. The Constant Function

3.2 The Benefits of Explicit Satisfaction

We have so far carried an implicit assumption—mirrored by other information flow systems [Pottier and Simonet 2002]—that all dependencies are *tracked granularly*. That is, all values carry their dependencies with them through being passed into and returned from functions. As an illustration, look to Figure 8. What dependency set should the [?] be? The empty set [] of course! When we evaluate the call `const alice`, α gets instantiated to [`alice`]. α does not appear in the return type, so this has no effect. For the constant function, we want precise tracking. However, most functions are not the constant function: they have at least some arguments upon which the return value is guaranteed to depend. For instance, consider the type for `add` given in Section 1.1. Need it have any information flow content at all, since its return value will *always* depend on both of its arguments? The clean logical foundations of our system help us answer this.

3.2.1 Polarity. A tool from proof theory, *polarity*, suggests that we need not. Polarity classifies types into *positive*—defined by their constructors—or *negative*—defined by their behavior when used. Booleans and lists are positive because we think of them by the form of their inhabitants, like `True` and `Cons(...)`. Functions are negative because they are characterized by their behavior when we apply them to arguments, not by their implementation. Positive types are connected to *values*, and negative types to *computations* [Levy 1999]. Remember that the goal of information flow is to map the inputs of a computation to its outputs. Polarity implies that positive types need not have interesting information flow specifications, because they do not pertain to computations, but negatives must. In particular, positive types should not granularly track—that is, encapsulate—information flows, but negative types should. For instance, lists are a positive type, so the dependencies of its elements are not tracked separately but propagated to the dependency set for the entire list. Meanwhile, function types should not leak information dependencies contained in their bodies until they are called, so these dependencies must be captured in their return type. Not so for their arguments, which should be determined by the polarity of each argument type. Luckily, polarity does not force a predetermined coarseness of tracking on us, besides as a per-type default, but permits us to choose. The connective [α] **A**—which is the *satisfaction operator* from Section 2.2—is of negative type. If granular information flow tracking is desired within positive types, a satisfaction operator can be introduced to do so.

Our view on polarity in information flow provides the following: **the granularity of dependency tracking should be type driven, rather than using a heuristic of maximally precise tracking everywhere.** This will allow us to simplify types, writing the type of `add` as `int -> int -> int`. `int` is a positive type, so does not encapsulate any dependencies, and because this eliminates all dependencies on the arguments the return value need not encapsulate any either. The ambient world path—or security context— ϕ from the typing judgement in Figure 4 is given programmatic meaning now: it tracks dependencies not encapsulated inside the type. Though

we did not provide syntax for introducing and eliminating satisfaction in that section, we might imagine that the syntax $\#e$ introduces it, internalizing the current ambient dependencies into the type. Thus if x has type **int** and the ambient security context is α , the expression $\#x$ will have type $[\alpha] \text{int}$. Similarly, we use $!e$ to eliminate satisfaction and move the dependencies annotated in the type of an expression from the type to the ambient security context. Putting these together, the expression $\#(\text{add } !\text{alice } !\text{alice})$ would have type $[\text{alice}] \text{int}$ as before. alice is tracked ambiently after $!\text{alice}$ until $\#(\dots)$.

Practically, we should be able to let the language infer satisfaction for us. An algorithm to do this seems straightforward enough: if we have an $e : A$ but need an expression of type $[\alpha] A$, then attempt to apply satisfaction introduction. Analogously for the reverse direction. We leave the formulation of this algorithm as future work, assuming it for the time being for convenience. The important point is that we can exploit polarity to inform and control the granularity of dependency tracking. Prior work has pursued expressivity results [Rajani and Garg 2018] regarding different degrees of granularity, but has not identified the connection to polarity which informs *when* dependencies should be tracked.

3.2.2 Dependency Elision. Based on the ideas above, our system supports an interesting and useful type simplification pattern. The type for `map1` in Figure 9, specialized to lists of integers, precisely characterizes information flow for this function, and is comparable (even slightly better, due to the benefits noted in Section 3.1) to the types given for `map` by other information flow systems.

```

let map1 : [  $\alpha$  ] ( [  $\beta$  ] int -> [  $\delta$  ] int ) -> [  $\sigma$  ] list ( [  $\beta$  ] int ) ->
  [  $\alpha$   $\sigma$  ] list ( [  $\delta$  ] int )
let map2 : ( [  $\beta$  ] int -> [  $\delta$  ] int ) -> list ( [  $\beta$  ] int ) -> list ( [  $\delta$  ] int )
let map3 : ( A -> B ) -> list A -> list B

```

Fig. 9. Finding Simplifications in Map

Reading from left-to-right, we first annotate the function argument given to `map1` with α so that when it is used inside the body it can induce an α dependency. The function itself takes a $[\beta] \text{int}$ as argument, which is the type of the contents of the list, and returns a $[\delta] \text{int}$, the type of the contents of the returned list. This does not suffice to describe the dependencies of either the argument or the returned lists, though, because while β and δ describe the dependencies of their *contents*, the *structure* of the list may itself have dependencies. For instance, the length of a list may betray information about the number of bits in a cryptographic key. Since lists are positive types, it would not ordinarily be allowed to treat these distinctly, but we manually do so by using a satisfaction type for the elements. So we introduce a σ dependency for the argument list to represent the structure information. The structure of the returned list is dependent on both σ and α , because the dependencies from the higher-order argument must be captured in the return value.

Precision can be useful, but this type is more complicated than we might like. Looking at the type of `map1` more carefully, we see that α and σ both occur in outermost satisfaction types in the argument types and on the return value. When such a pattern arises, the corresponding variables can be removed entirely without losing any precision, which we call *dependency-elision*. The unmentioned dependencies on the arguments will then be propagated ambiently to the whole application expression. The resulting type is given for `map2`. This simplification is not possible in systems which do not follow the directive given by polarity and instead track dependencies maximally granularly everywhere [Liu et al. 2024; Pottier and Simonet 2002], for instance forcing positive types like **list** to always hold their structural dependencies. A further simplification can be made in this case: the standard polymorphic type of `map`, reproduced in `map3`, now captures

that of `map2`. So it can be used to track information flow with no loss in precision from `map1`. For simplicity and clarity the formal system in Section 5 focuses on dependency polymorphism; we leave an extension of the system that supports type polymorphism to future work.

4 Declassification

The essence of declassification, as hinted, is *quantification* and *dependency sets* (i.e. world paths from hybrid logic). We rely on the same fundamental machinery used to ensure modularity across most modern typed languages. In that respect it should be uncontroversial. The core of the technique can be subtle for those unfamiliar with existentials from prior work on type abstraction [Mitchell and Plotkin 1985], but we will use simple examples to make the ideas more accessible.

4.1 Explicit, Higher-Rank Quantification and Dependency Sets

When we typed the identity function as with `id_implicit` in Figure 10, we omitted the bindings of the α variables. We now give a more explicit version as `id_explicit`, matching the formal system to be described in Section 5. The difference is the `forall α` sitting in front of the type signature, called a *quantifier*. This construct acts as a binder for α : where `let` binds term-level variables, `forall` binds type-level variables.

```
let pass : [ pwd ] string = "katya"

let id_implicit : [  $\alpha$  ] int -> [  $\alpha$  ] int
let id_explicit : forall  $\alpha$  . [  $\alpha$  ] int -> [  $\alpha$  ] int

let v1 : [ pwd ] int = id_implicit pass
let v2 : [ pwd ] int -> [ pwd ] int = id_explicit [ pwd ]
let v2' : [ pwd ] int = v2 pass
```

Fig. 10. Exposing the Type of the Identity Function

`v1` shows the function `id_implicit` being applied as we have done so far, simply passing it an argument with dependencies `[pwd]` and expecting that the α in its type will change to reflect these dependencies. `v2` shows the plumbing: we first instantiate `id_implicit` to `[pwd]`, whereupon the type system substitutes away the α for that set of dependencies. The type that results is a function with nearly the same input and output types, but which is no longer polymorphic in α . In `v2'` we apply `v2` to the same argument `pass` as before—which matches the expected dependency set `[pwd]`—yielding the same type as in `v1`. `forall`s are usually handled transparently when polymorphism is in use, but declassification will require us to explicate them.

4.2 ‘Where’ Declassification: Disappearing Dependencies with Quantification

We now illustrate declassification in our system, using the what-where-when-who framework of Sabelfeld and Sands [2009] to structure our discussion. We start by asking *where can quantifiers go?* They have so far appeared exclusively and implicitly in *prefix* position, or at the beginning of the function signature. Consider the type `higher_rank` in Figure 11. The `forall`-quantified β here is no longer in prefix position, because it has been moved inside the higher-order function. This is called *higher-ranked* quantification.

Here our goal is to allow a function defined by client code to compute with a secret number without being able to reveal it to the outside world until the computation is done. When the computation finishes, the final answer is revealed. Observe that `num` in `client` has type `[β] int`.

```

type higher_rank = (forall  $\beta$  . [  $\beta$  ] int -> [  $\beta$  ] int) -> int

let impl : higher_rank = fun compute -> compute [ ] 7

let client : int = impl (fun num -> num + 123)

```

Fig. 11. Higher-Rank Quantification

We add `123` to it, and then return it as the result of the higher-order function. The whole function is passed to `impl`, which gives us back an `int`. Inspecting `impl` we see that it sets `num` to `7`. So the higher order function passed to it by `client` will add `123` to `7`. The sum `130` is returned to `client` as the result of the computation. This is dependent on the initial value of `num`, which has dependency β , but β does not occur in the type of `client`! Indeed, β is not in scope there. The reason β disappears is because `client` is polymorphic in β . This means that its logic must be written without knowing what β actually is—as though β could be anything. `impl` takes advantage of this by instantiating β to `[]`. Inside the higher-order function in the body of `client`, the dependency β must be treated like any other. However, when `130` is sent to `impl`, where β is set to `[]`, it returns a `[] int`. We implicitly unwrap the now-unnecessary satisfaction operator to yield just `[] int`.

In Sabelfeld and Sands’s framework, we bound *where* the disappearance—or declassification—occurs to the lexical scope for β . Observe that this is *not* declassification in the typical [Sabelfeld and Sands 2009] sense of violating the faithfulness of dependency tracking. Rather, we simply exploit the internal knowledge of β ’s emptiness to eventually elide it. This work demonstrates that declassification in the usual sense is not needed to expose the programming facilities offered by it.

4.3 ‘What’ Declassification: Revisiting Password Checking

We can now solve the problem with `check` from the introduction, which will involve controlling *what* information can be declassified. Our solution is laid out in Figure 12. We start by generalizing the schema of higher-ranked quantification, represented by the `passwd_checker` type. There is now a quantified variable α which allows us to return data at any dependencies. Importantly, α *cannot* mention π because it is scoped outside of it. In fact, the π is not *universally* quantified anymore—another name for `forall`—but *existentially* quantified. The ability to encode existential quantification by leveraging universal quantification as shown is discussed in Girard et al. [1989, §11.3.5]. **Existentials allow us to realize declassification fully generally.**

π plays the same role as `pwd` from our first attempt in Section 1.1. As in the preceding section we use a higher-order function to allow the client to compute on a secret value, then declassify the final result. This time, however, we provide the client with a secret value `pass` along with *methods* that can manipulate it: `check` and `hash`. To describe an interface exposing these elements we use the $F(\pi)$ notation, which is a template that takes a dependency variable as an argument and splices in a record containing methods typed at that variable. `impl` works on the same principle as before, instantiating the existential dependency π to the empty set of dependencies. It lives up to its namesake, providing implementations of each of the exposed methods. The clients are more interesting. `client1` exhibits a standard usage, instantiating α to `[]` and using `check`. `client1` is of type `bool`, as was promised in Section 1.1. So we have successfully declassified exactly the `bool` resulting from the password check. `client2` attempts to instantiate α with `[π]` so it can try to do the password check without going through `check`, but existential quantification bars it from doing so. π is not in scope at the point of instantiation! `client3` instantiates α to `[]`, but again accesses password data through `imports.pass`. This induces a π dependency—since the template was called with π as an argument—which will not check against the empty set.

```

F( $\pi$ )  $\triangleq$  {
  pass : [  $\pi$  ] string,
  check : forall  $\beta$  . [  $\beta$  ] string -> [  $\beta$  ] bool,
  hash : forall  $\beta$  . [  $\pi$   $\beta$  ] string -> [  $\beta$  ] string
}

type passwd_checker = forall  $\alpha$  . (forall  $\pi$  . F( $\pi$ ) -> [  $\alpha$  ] bool) -> [  $\alpha$  ] bool

let impl : passwd_checker = fun compute -> compute [ ] {
  pass = "katya",
  check = fun attempt -> attempt == pass,
  hash = fun pass_str -> sha256sum pass_str,
}

let client1 : bool = impl [ ] (fun imports -> imports.check "arren")
let client2 : bool = impl [  $\pi$  ] (fun imports -> "arren" == imports.pass)  $\triangleleft$ 
let client3 : bool = impl [ ] (fun imports -> "arren" == imports.pass)  $\triangleleft$ 

```

Fig. 12. A Fancier Password Checker

There is one point left to illuminate. Look to hash, which permits password-dependent strings' hashes to be leaked. From a client's perspective, such a function is possible when specified using world paths / dependency sets, but *is not possible under an arbitrary semilattice-based theory of information flow*. When calling hash, the information flow content of the data passed to hash's first argument must be able to be uniquely decomposed into the dependencies which comprise it. This allows hash to 'match' on dependencies in its input type and remove them, as it does with π . Joining in arbitrary lattices does not necessarily preserve information about the inputs, preventing the client from performing this decomposition, but the same in a free semilattice does.

Scaling the existential approach to practical programs necessitates being able to express declassifiers like hash. Otherwise, one is relegated to declassifying only by virtue of exported methods which *do not induce* some dependency, like check, rather than being able to *actively remove* that dependency in the style of hash. For instance, you may wish to perform some string processing on password data—say, padding it with a nonce—before hashing it. If we could not express functions like hash which remove dependencies from a given computation, this would require a specialized function in the style of check which does the desired padding, followed by hashing, to be exported from the password checker interface. In the general case, each individual use-case would require specialized support from the password checker itself. This is neither modular nor scalable.

The general problem here is highlighted by Cruz and Tanter [2019], who import the the machinery of *faceted types* to address it. It is remedied here without the need for specialized modifications to the type system. At an intuitive level, declassifying functions like hash can be seen as a computationally relevant ordering on dependency sets which may violate the one given structurally. Specifically, hash can be read as an ordering $[\pi \delta] \sqsubseteq [\delta]$ —note that the left hand side is not a subset of the right—that must be manually applied wherever it is used, transforming expressions at $[\pi \delta]$ into those at $[\delta]$. So this allows us to preserve the uniform structure of our information flow specifications while, in effect, introducing information flow policies on them. Let us review the example in Section 3.1 where we confronted policy declarations to see if we can capture them now.

```

open Alice with [ bob ] importing
  alice,
  reveal_alice : [ alice ] string -> [ bob ] string

let expected : [ bob ] string = "nemmerle"
let msg_bob : [ alice ] string -> [  $\alpha$  ] string -> [  $\alpha$  bob ] string =
  fun alice_secret msg_str ->
    if reveal_alice alice_secret == expected then msg_str else panic
. . .

```

Fig. 13. Declaring a Custom Dependency Ordering, Computation-Relevantly

4.4 ‘Who’ Declassification: Alice talks to Bob

The program in Figure 13 uses a slightly higher-level syntax for existential dependencies, closer to what programmers would see while employing our approach to declassification. In particular, we might imagine that **Alice** is defined as follows, where α is used to propagate the output

```

type Alice = forall  $\alpha$   $\beta$  .
  (forall alice . F(alice,  $\beta$ ) -> [  $\alpha$  ] A) -> [  $\alpha$  ] A

```

dependencies as before and **alice** is existentially quantified. **with** instantiates β with `[bob]`, which propagates it to the interface template $F(\dots)$. The **importing** clause brings into scope the existential variable **alice** and a function `reveal_alice` from the instantiated interface $F(\text{alice}, \text{bob})$. **bob** is assumed to be in-scope. Functionally, this program revisits Figure 6, showing how our system can model an information flow policy that allows Alice’s data to be sent to Bob. This corresponds to the *who* dimension of declassification from Sabelfeld and Sands [2009].

Looking to the client machinery, assume α is instantiated as needed for the eventual return dependencies of the program in Figure 13, and similarly that **A** is as needed for the program’s eventual return type since our core system lacks polymorphism over types. The purpose of the `reveal_alice` function is to declassify **alice** data to Bob by relabeling it as **bob** data. As in the prior two examples, the `reveal_alice` function can be implemented by the **Alice** module because the latter has internally instantiated **alice** to a convenient dependency set—perhaps `[]` or `[bob]`. The only difference compared to Figure 6 is that `reveal_alice` must be called explicitly, rather than the flow being permitted implicitly. As a result, `reveal_alice` can transform Alice’s data arbitrarily before revealing it to Bob, such as by redacting certain information or cryptographically signing it. This is what is meant by *computationally relevant*: **policies and declassification inherently have computational content in our system**. In our view, information flow policies and declassifiers are *one and the same*; there should be no distinction between the two. The setup of both within our system makes this apparent. This is particularly desirable in the context of, say, revealing secrets: it is rare that a secret value should be leaked fully intact rather than after some redacting computation. The computational *irrelevance* of ordinary policy declarations makes them unfit to serve as a declassification mechanism, so computational relevance can be seen as unifying the two.

We could extend this example by introducing another existential module **Bob** which permits messages tagged with **bob** to be read without inducing a dependency, effectively declassifying messages after processing them. Only *when* declassification remains of the major flavors of declassification [Sabelfeld and Sands 2009]. This is easy enough: simply integrate the ordering constraints into the function type which performs declassification. For instance, to declassify bids only after an auction has closed, require the auction to run to completion before running a callback to declassification.

Dependency ϕ Type A, B Expr e, v Dependency Vars $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots \in \Delta$ Vars $x_1, x_2, \dots \in \Gamma$

Dependencies $\phi ::= \circ \mid \phi; \alpha$

Types $A ::= \text{unit} \mid [A \cdot \phi] \mid A_1 \rightarrow A_2 \mid \forall(\alpha.A)$

Expressions $e, v ::= \langle \rangle \mid x \mid \#e \mid !e \mid \lambda(x.e) \mid \text{ap}(e_1; e_2) \mid \Lambda(\alpha.e) \mid e[\phi]$

$\frac{}{\Delta; \Gamma \vdash \langle \rangle : \text{unit} \mid \circ}$	$\frac{}{\Delta; \Gamma, x : A \vdash x : A \mid \circ}$	$\frac{}{\Delta; \Gamma \vdash \#e : [A \cdot \phi] \mid \circ}$	$\frac{}{\Delta; \Gamma \vdash !e : A \mid \phi_1 \sqcup \phi_2}$
$\frac{\text{T-LAM} \quad \Delta; \Gamma, x : A_1 \vdash e : A_2 \mid \circ \quad \Delta \vdash A_1}{\Delta; \Gamma \vdash \lambda(x.e) : A_1 \rightarrow A_2 \mid \circ}$	$\frac{\text{T-AP} \quad \Delta; \Gamma \vdash e : A_1 \rightarrow A_2 \mid \phi \quad \Delta; \Gamma \vdash e_1 : A_1 \mid \phi_1}{\Delta; \Gamma \vdash \text{ap}(e; e_1) : A_2 \mid \phi \sqcup \phi_1}$		
$\frac{}{\Delta; \Gamma \vdash \Lambda(\alpha.e) : \forall(\alpha.A) \mid \circ}$	$\frac{\text{T-DEPLAM} \quad \Delta, \alpha; \Gamma \vdash e : A \mid \circ}{\Delta; \Gamma \vdash \Lambda(\alpha.e) : \forall(\alpha.A) \mid \circ}$	$\frac{\text{T-DEPAP} \quad \Delta; \Gamma \vdash e : \forall(\alpha.A) \mid \phi' \quad \Delta \vdash \phi}{\Delta; \Gamma \vdash e[\phi] : [\phi/\alpha]A \mid \phi'}$	$\frac{\text{T-SUB} \quad \Delta; \Gamma \vdash e : A_1 \mid \phi \quad A_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A_2}{\Delta; \Gamma \vdash e : A_2 \mid \phi}$

Fig. 14. TS/SCI: Type System for the Structural Calculus of Indistinguishability (Core Rules)

5 Metatheory

We have surveyed a zoo of interesting examples ranging beyond those in [Section 1.1](#), but have not introduced any new primitive notions! Even existential quantification as revealed in the last section is simply re-using the same machinery introduced initially for polymorphism. This makes our job in this section relatively straightforward.

5.1 Syntax and Typing: A Hybrid Type System

The core syntax and typing rules of our system, the *Structural Calculus of Indistinguishability*, are shown in [Figure 14](#). Our typing judgment is $\Delta; \Gamma \vdash e : A \mid \phi$ and can be read “Under in-scope dependency variables Δ and in-scope term variables Γ the expression e has type A with set of dependencies ϕ .” Dependencies ϕ play the same role as in [Section 2.2](#), reifying the *ambient security level* from [Section 3.2.1](#). The type $[A \cdot \phi]$ corresponds to a satisfaction operator $@_{\phi}A$ and uses the syntax $\#e$ and $!e$ for introduction and elimination. The corresponding rules T-CONSUME and T-PRODUCE look familiar, nearly mirroring [@!](#) and [@E-new](#) modulo syntax. The biggest difference is that T-CONSUME concludes at the empty dependency set \circ , which will be important.

Starting simple, the introduction rule for `unit` states that a unit expression $\langle \rangle$ incurs no dependencies. The variable typing rule shows the structure of the typing context Γ , which contains variables at a particular type. Unlike other information flow systems, we do not annotate variables in the context with security levels. They may carry dependency information in their type—using $[A \cdot \phi]$ —if needed, but the entries in the context themselves are not annotated. This is in line with the interpretation of the ϕ in the typing judgment as an *effect*. Only computations should have effects; variables, being connected in a call-by-value language to values, should not [[Levy 1999](#)].

Moving on to functions, T-LAM is relatively standard. Strangely, however, it requires that its body have no dependencies. This is a way of forcing its body to consume all its dependencies—that is, represent them within its type A_2 using T-CONSUME—before a lambda is allowed to form around it. Forcing dependencies into function types is in line with the intuitions about granular tracking

and polarity from [Section 3.2.1](#). There is also a premise $\Delta \vdash A_1$, which we will return to shortly. The application rule T-AP propagates the function and argument’s dependencies to the application expression in the conclusion, but is otherwise as usual. T-DEPLAM is the introduction rule for the quantifier type $\forall(\alpha.A)$. It again requires the dependencies in its body to be consumed. Its premise introduces an α into Δ , the environment responsible for tracking the in-scope information flow variables. This can be thought of analogously to the introduction rule for type abstraction in System F [[Girard 1986](#)]. The elimination rule T-DEPAP for quantifiers is instantiation, substituting the instantiated ϕ into the inner type of the quantifier. This is analogous to type application in System F. The type of `id` in [Figure 1](#) under this syntax might be $\forall(\alpha.[\text{int} \cdot \alpha] \rightarrow [\text{int} \cdot \alpha])$, using `int` as a base type. A term under this type is $\Lambda(\alpha.\lambda(x.x))$, but more are possible by using `!x` to extract out the underlying `int` and compute with it as in $\Lambda(\alpha.\lambda(x. \#(!x + !x)))$.

The premise $\Delta \vdash \phi$ appearing in T-DEPAP is toward the same end as $\Delta \vdash A_1$ from T-LAM. Its purpose is to ensure the well-scopedness of all elements of the typing judgement within any derivation. We want to be sure that whenever we have a valid type derivation, all dependencies α in the expression e , type A , and dependency set ϕ in the typing judgement are contained within Δ . We also want to ensure that any term variables x in e are contained in Γ . Regularity establishes this rigid lexical scoping. $\Delta \vdash A$ can be read as “all dependencies α mentioned in A are members of Δ ”; analogously for the other three scoping judgements.

Theorem 5.1 (Regularity). *If $\Delta; \Gamma \vdash e : A \mid \phi$ and $\Delta \vdash A_i$ for each assumption $x_i : A_i$ in Γ , then $\Delta \vdash e$ and $\Gamma \vdash e$ and $\Delta \vdash A$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi$.*

PROOF. By induction on a derivation of $\Delta; \Gamma \vdash e : A \mid \phi$. □

Observe that all introduction rules for the connectives so far introduced, namely $[A \cdot \phi]$, $A_1 \rightarrow A_2$, and $\forall(\alpha.A)$, conclude at the empty set of dependencies \circ . This is because they are *negative connectives*. In line with the reasoning in [Section 3.2.1](#), **all negative connectives must consume their dependencies**. This also provides a solution to the

local soundness issue noted with the satisfaction rules in [Section 2.2](#), because T-CONSUME (unlike [⊗](#)) does not create a spurious ϕ' in its conclusion. The derivation is reproduced here.

$$\frac{\frac{\Delta; \Gamma \vdash e : A \mid \phi}{\Delta; \Gamma \vdash \#e : [A \cdot \phi] \mid \circ} \text{T-CONSUME}}{\Delta; \Gamma \vdash !\#e : A \mid \phi} \text{T-PRODUCE}$$

Finally, T-SUB allows *subsumption*, which enables us to raise the security levels of programs’ types. Reading from the top, if one has e at type A_1 and a proof that A_1 is a subtype of A_2 , then T-SUB provides e at type A_2 . We have $[A_1 \cdot \phi_1] \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} [A_2 \cdot \phi_2]$ when $\phi_1 \subset \phi_2$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi_2$ and $A_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A_2$. This permits the security levels of expressions to be raised—that is, it permits them to add extra dependencies to themselves. Beyond for $[A \cdot \phi]$ the subtyping judgment is standard so we elide its definition. We also omit the operational semantics, which are as usual but for the syntax $\#e$ and $!e$ for $[A \cdot \phi]$. These act respectively as *thunking* and *forcing thunks*. Removing the syntactic forms for these—and therefore the *thunking semantics*—presents no formal obstacle. We have found it pedagogically easier to give them explicit syntax, since they can then be mentioned explicitly if needed. The *thunking semantics* for their syntax simply aligns with the negative polarity [[Levy 1999](#)] of the satisfaction connective, discussed in [Section 3.2.1](#). We look now to the positives.

5.1.1 Positive Connectives. Our system supports two positive connectives: positive products and sums. T-INJL is one of two introduction rules for sums, the other being T-INJR. Observe that the dependencies ϕ of the expression e are propagated straightforwardly in both rules to their conclusion. The type of the injection *not* witnessed is checked for scoping, to ensure regularity. T-CASE largely works as usual, but now accounts for the *indirect flows* from the expression e being branched on, adding its dependencies ϕ in the conclusion to those coming from e_1 or e_2 . We require

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{Types } A ::= \dots \mid A_1 + A_2 \mid A_1 \otimes A_2 \\
\text{Expressions } e, v ::= \dots \mid l \cdot e \mid r \cdot e \mid \text{case } e \{ l \cdot x_1 \hookrightarrow e_1 \mid r \cdot x_2 \hookrightarrow e_2 \} \\
\quad \mid \langle e_1, e_2 \rangle \mid \text{split } e_1 \text{ into } \langle x_1, x_2 \rangle \text{ in } e_2 \\
\\
\begin{array}{c}
\text{T-INJL} \\
\frac{\Delta; \Gamma \vdash e : A_1 \mid \phi \quad \Delta \vdash A_2}{\Delta; \Gamma \vdash l \cdot e : A_1 + A_2 \mid \phi}
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{c}
\text{T-PAIR} \\
\frac{\Delta; \Gamma \vdash e_1 : A_1 \mid \phi_1 \quad \Delta; \Gamma \vdash e_2 : A_2 \mid \phi_2}{\Delta; \Gamma \vdash \langle e_1, e_2 \rangle : A_1 \otimes A_2 \mid \phi_1 \sqcup \phi_2}
\end{array} \\
\\
\begin{array}{c}
\text{T-INJR} \\
\frac{\Delta; \Gamma \vdash e : A_2 \mid \phi \quad \Delta \vdash A_1}{\Delta; \Gamma \vdash r \cdot e : A_1 + A_2 \mid \phi}
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{c}
\text{T-SPLIT} \\
\frac{\Delta; \Gamma \vdash e : A_1 \otimes A_2 \mid \phi \quad \Delta; \Gamma, x_1 : A_1, x_2 : A_2 \vdash e_1 : A \mid \phi'}{\Delta; \Gamma \vdash \text{split } e \text{ into } \langle x_1, x_2 \rangle \text{ in } e_1 : A \mid \phi \sqcup \phi'}
\end{array} \\
\\
\begin{array}{c}
\text{T-CASE} \\
\frac{\Delta; \Gamma \vdash e : A_1 + A_2 \mid \phi \quad \Delta; \Gamma, x_1 : A_1 \vdash e_1 : A \mid \phi' \quad \Delta; \Gamma, x_2 : A_2 \vdash e_2 : A \mid \phi'}{\Delta; \Gamma \vdash \text{case } e \{ l \cdot x_1 \hookrightarrow e_1 \mid r \cdot x_2 \hookrightarrow e_2 \} : A \mid \phi \sqcup \phi'}
\end{array}
\end{array}$$

Fig. 15. Positive Connectives for the Structural Calculus of Indistinguishability

e_1 and e_2 to have the same dependency level. Introducing positive products works similarly with respect to the flow of dependencies, with the introduction rule T-PAIR propagating the dependencies ϕ_1, ϕ_2 from each of its subexpressions to the conclusion of the rule at $\phi_1 \sqcup \phi_2$. T-SPLIT works the same way as T-CASE from an information flow perspective.

We see that the introduction rules for **positives act transparently with respect to the judgemental dependencies** ϕ , instead of being forced to encapsulate them and conclude at the empty set. An alternative formulation of the introduction rule for products forces e_1 and e_2 to consume their dependencies into their types; this would then be a negative product. Stemming from the choice to have a separate type connective $[A \cdot \phi]$ for tagging types with dependencies—rather than tagging each type with dependency information individually—the design of such a rule is predetermined by polarity. Observe that negative (or *lazy*) products would track dependencies more granularly than positive products, as expected from Section 3.2.1: each projection’s dependencies can be distinguished from the other’s. Not so for positive products, which blend both projections’ dependencies ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 together. Positive products can be viewed as more general than negative products in our setting, since we can simply use satisfaction for one or both elements of the pair. As a rule, introduction forms for positive types will be transparent to dependency information, while those for negative types will be opaque. This is in line with the interpretation of the former as connected to values, and the latter to computations [Levy 1999].

5.2 Non-interference

We prove non-interference via a binary logical relation. We show that it satisfies a number of desirable properties. We then show the fundamental theorem, which relates well-typed programs to membership in the logical relation. Non-interference is captured with a corollary stating that any function whose argument dependencies are not represented in its return dependencies must be constant in its argument, fulfilling our promise from Section 1.1. The proof treats declassification without additional machinery beyond that for handling quantifiers. The definition of the logical

$$\begin{aligned}
e \sim^* e' \in A \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta] &\triangleq \phi_1 \not\sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2 \text{ or } v \text{ val}, v' \text{ val}, e \mapsto^* v, e' \mapsto^* v', \\
v \sim v' \in A \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta] \\
\langle \rangle \sim \langle \rangle \in \text{unit} \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta] &\triangleq \text{true} \\
1 \cdot v \sim 1 \cdot v' \in A_1 + A_2 \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta] &\triangleq v \sim^* v' \in A_1 \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta] \\
r \cdot v \sim r \cdot v' \in A_1 + A_2 \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta] &\triangleq v \sim^* v' \in A_2 \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta] \\
\langle v_1, v_2 \rangle \sim \langle v'_1, v'_2 \rangle \in A_1 \otimes A_2 \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta] &\triangleq v_1 \sim^* v'_1 \in A_1 \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta], \\
v_2 \sim^* v'_2 \in A_2 \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta] \\
v \sim v' \in [A \cdot \phi] \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta] &\triangleq !v \sim^* !v' \in A \mid \phi \sqcup \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta] \\
v \sim v' \in A_1 \rightarrow A_2 \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta] &\triangleq \forall \phi'_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2, \Delta \vdash \phi'_1, v_1 \text{ val}, v'_1 \text{ val} . \\
v_1 \sim^* v'_1 \in A_1 \mid \phi'_1 [\phi'_2] [\Delta] &\implies \\
\text{ap}(v; v_1) \sim^* \text{ap}(v'; v'_1) \in A_2 \mid \phi_1 \sqcup \phi_1 [\phi'_2] [\Delta] \\
v \sim v' \in \forall(\alpha.A) \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta] &\triangleq \Delta \vdash \phi \implies v[\phi] \sim^* v'[\phi] \in [\phi/\alpha]A \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]
\end{aligned}$$

Fig. 16. Semantic Equality for the Structural Calculus of Indistinguishability

relation is given in [Figure 16](#). Full proofs of all theorems referenced in this section can be found in the accompanying artifact [[Gouni et al. 2025](#), Appendix C].

The starred relation $e \sim^* e' \in A \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$ can be read as “ e relates to e' at type A with security level ϕ_1 and observer level ϕ_2 under in-scope dependency variables Δ .” Here e, e' are closed expressions, containing no variables. We introduce a notion of an *observer level* [[Kozyri et al. 2022](#)] which determines whether an “observer” of a program who is permitted to see certain dependencies should be allowed to see the outputs of the program in question. If the security level—which plays the same role as the ϕ in the typing judgment—is a subset of the observer level, then the answer is yes. Otherwise, the answer is no. The $\phi_1 \not\sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$ in the definition of the starred relation codifies this, and is called the *non-interference condition*. If the security level ϕ_1 of some related expressions is *not* a subset of the current observer level ϕ_2 , then to that observer, the expressions are equal. From their perspective, no discriminating information can be gleaned. This is why non-interference is a *hyperproperty* [[McLean 1996](#)], or inherently a matter of two or more related traces of evaluation: it reasons about the observable differences between them.

If the non-interference condition in $e \sim^* e' \in A \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$ is not triggered then the equality must ultimately be established according to the type A . First, e and e' must evaluate to values $v \text{ val}$ and $v' \text{ val}$. And v, v' must be related at $v \sim v' \in A \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$, the non-starred relation. The definition of $e \sim^* e'$ by evaluation immediately gives us the following two properties.

Lemma 5.2 (Closed \rightarrow). *If $e \sim^* e' \in A \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$ and $e \mapsto^* e_1$ then $e_1 \sim^* e' \in A \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$.*

PROOF. By use of evaluation in $e \sim^* e' \in A \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$ and determinicity of evaluation. \square

Lemma 5.3 (Closed \leftarrow). *If $e \sim^* e' \in A \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$ and $e_1 \mapsto^* e$ then $e_1 \sim^* e' \in A \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$.*

PROOF. By use of evaluation in $e \sim^* e' \in A \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$ and transitivity of evaluation. \square

These two lemmas show that the logical relation is preserved by evaluation *in both directions*. [Lemma 5.3](#) is the critical one: if expressions e, e' are logically related, then *anything that evaluates*

to them is also in the logical relation. This means that there are many expressions which are related by the logical relation, but are not well-typed.

The relation $v \sim v'$ is mutually recursive with the starred relation and is defined inductively on types in a standard way. For positive types it ensures that both sides have the expected canonical forms, and that the insides of the canonical forms are related at the appropriate type. For negative types it ensures they behave correctly under elimination. Within each case it recurses back onto $e \overset{*}{\sim} e'$ to check the equality of the inner or eliminated expressions. This is important when the security level is raised as in the cases for $[A \cdot \phi]$ and $A_1 \rightarrow A_2$, because a higher security level, or larger set, may satisfy the non-interference condition. Note that while the security level ϕ_1 is *monotonic* with respect to non-interference, the observer level ϕ_2 is *anti-monotonic*.

Lemma 5.4 (Monotone). *If $e \overset{*}{\sim} e' \in A \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$ and $\phi_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'_1$ then $e \overset{*}{\sim} e' \in A \mid \phi'_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$.*

PROOF. By straightforward induction on A . □

Lemma 5.5 (Anti-monotone). *If $e \overset{*}{\sim} e' \in A \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$ and $\phi'_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$ then $e \overset{*}{\sim} e' \in A \mid \phi_1 [\phi'_2] [\Delta]$.*

PROOF. By straightforward induction on A . □

Intuitively, $\phi_1 \not\sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$ is preserved by either adding elements to the left side, or removing elements from the right. The former raises the security level, and the latter means the observer drops permissions for viewing certain dependencies. That the dependency elision heuristic from [Section 3.2.2](#) preserves non-interference, and is therefore sound, can be justified via monotonicity: it always produces equally as many or more dependencies into the ambient security level than the non-elided variant, because argument dependencies get propagated ambiently to the application expression. As mentioned, we leave the elision algorithm and its completeness for future work. We next show that our logical relation satisfies certain properties of equivalence relations.

Lemma 5.6 (Symmetry). *If $e_1 \overset{*}{\sim} e_2 \in A \mid \phi [\phi'] [\Delta]$ then $e_2 \overset{*}{\sim} e_1 \in A \mid \phi [\phi'] [\Delta]$.*

PROOF. By straightforward induction on A . □

Lemma 5.7 (Transitivity). *If $e_1 \overset{*}{\sim} e_2 \in A \mid \phi [\phi'] [\Delta]$ and $e_2 \overset{*}{\sim} e_3 \in A \mid \phi [\phi'] [\Delta]$ then $e_1 \overset{*}{\sim} e_3 \in A \mid \phi [\phi'] [\Delta]$*

PROOF. By induction on A and [Lemma 5.6](#) in the $A_1 \rightarrow A_2$ case to handle contravariance. □

Importantly, the logical relation *does not* satisfy reflexivity. For instance, the expression $\langle \rangle$ cannot be self-equated at any type other than unit, and in general related expressions must behave appropriately for their declared type. Thus our logical relation is a *partial equivalence relation*, satisfying symmetry and transitivity but not reflexivity. Finally, the fundamental theorem translates well-typedness to membership in the logical relation. However, recall that while the typing rules work with open expressions, the logical relation only works on closed expressions. We must generalize the logical relation to account for open expressions. We begin by defining *closing substitutions* which replace free dependency variables and term variables with appropriate forms.

(1) Define $\delta \in \Delta \rightsquigarrow \Delta'$ as a map from each $\alpha \in \Delta$ to a dependency environment $\Delta' \vdash \phi$.

(2) Define:

(a) $\gamma \in \Gamma [\Delta']$ as a map from $x \in \Gamma$ to an expression e closed under term variables s.t. $\Delta' \vdash e$

(b) $\gamma \overset{*}{\sim} \gamma' \in \Gamma \mid \phi [\phi'] [\Delta \rightsquigarrow \Delta']$ to mean that if $\Delta' \vdash \phi'$ and $\delta \in \Delta \rightsquigarrow \Delta'$ then we have

$\gamma, \gamma' \in \Gamma [\Delta']$ s.t. $\gamma(x) \overset{*}{\sim} \gamma'(x) \in \widehat{\delta}(A) \mid \phi [\phi'] [\Delta']$ for all $x : A \in \Gamma$

(3) Define $\Delta \Gamma \gg_{\Delta'}^{\phi'} e \overset{*}{\sim} e' \in A \mid \phi$ to mean that for all $\Delta' \vdash \phi_{\gamma}$ if [3a](#), [3b](#), and [3c](#) then [3d](#).

(a) $\Delta' \vdash \phi'$

- (b) $\delta \in \Delta \rightsquigarrow \Delta'$
- (c) $\gamma \sim^* \gamma' \in \Gamma \mid \phi_\gamma [\phi'] \mid [\Delta \rightsquigarrow \Delta']$ (instantiated to 3a and 3b)
- (d) $\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e)) \sim^* \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e')) \in \widehat{\delta}(A) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi) \sqcup \phi_\gamma [\phi'] \mid [\Delta']$

δ replaces dependency variables α with dependency sets ϕ closed under Δ' . γ, γ' replace term variables x with closed expressions related at the type of the variable. The type itself is closed using $\widehat{\delta}$. The security level ϕ represents the cumulative dependencies of all information contained in Γ . $\widehat{\delta}$ and $\widehat{\gamma}$ apply the mappings in δ and γ *simultaneously* to all open variables in their arguments. The generalized logical relation in [item 3](#) is defined by using $\widehat{\delta}$ and $\widehat{\gamma}$ on its expressions e, e' and $\widehat{\delta}$ on its type A and security level ϕ . We invoke the starred relation on the substituted forms.

Theorem 5.8 (Fundamental Theorem). *If $\Delta_0, \Delta; \Gamma \vdash e : A \mid \phi$ then $\Delta \Gamma \gg_{\Delta_0}^{\phi'} e \sim^* e \in A \mid \phi$.*

PROOF. By induction on a derivation of $\Delta_0, \Delta; \Gamma \vdash e : A \mid \phi$. □

The statement of the fundamental theorem splits up the information flow variable environment from the typing judgment into Δ_0 and Δ . Δ_0 denotes *the observer's dependency environment*. The definition of equality of open expressions requires that $\Delta_0 \vdash \phi'$ where ϕ' is the observer level. Δ_0 provides an environment for a closing substitution on dependency variables α to be *closed under*, because all dependencies considered in the logical relation must be meaningful to the observer. That the open and closed logical relations are *relativized* to a base Δ_0 representing the observer's environment is key to the formal treatment of declassification. The constant function property we desired in [Section 1.1](#) emerges as a straightforward corollary of the fundamental theorem.

Corollary 5.9 (Constant Function). *If we have $\Delta; \Gamma \vdash e : [A_1 \cdot \phi_1] \rightarrow [A_2 \cdot \phi_2] \mid \circ$ and c val and $\phi_1 \not\sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$ then $\circ \Gamma \gg_{\Delta}^{\phi_2} e \sim^* \lambda(x.\text{ap}(e; c)) \in [A_1 \cdot \phi_1] \rightarrow [A_2 \cdot \phi_2] \mid \circ$.*

PROOF. Follows directly from [Theorem 5.8](#). We sketch the proof here.

- (1) Assume ϕ_γ and $\Delta \vdash \phi_2$ and appropriate δ and γ, γ' .
- (2) To show $[A_1 \cdot \phi_1] \rightarrow [A_2 \cdot \phi_2]$ assume $v_1 \sim v'_1 \in [A_1 \cdot \phi_1] \mid \phi'_1 [\phi'_2] \mid [\Delta]$ where $\phi'_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$.
- (3) Suffices to show $\text{ap}(\widehat{\gamma}(e); v_1) \sim^* \text{ap}(\lambda(x.\text{ap}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e); c)); v'_1) \in [A_2 \cdot \phi_2] \mid \phi'_1 \sqcup \phi_\gamma [\phi'_2] \mid [\Delta]$.
- (4) We have $\phi_1 \not\sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'_2$ by properties of set inclusion.
- (5) Obtain $!v_1 \sim^* !c \in A_1 \mid \phi_1 [\phi'_2] \mid [\Delta]$ by non-interference, so $v_1 \sim^* c \in [A_1 \cdot \phi_1] \mid \circ [\phi'_2] \mid [\Delta]$.
- (6) By [Lemma 5.4](#) we have $v_1 \sim^* c \in [A_1 \cdot \phi_1] \mid \phi'_1 [\phi'_2] \mid [\Delta]$.
- (7) Use [Theorem 5.8](#) on the typing assumption for e and instantiate with [item 1](#) to get $\widehat{\gamma}(e) \sim^* \widehat{\gamma}'(e) \in [A_1 \cdot \phi_1] \rightarrow [A_2 \cdot \phi_2] \mid \phi_\gamma [\phi_2] \mid [\Delta]$.
- (8) If $\phi_\gamma \not\sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$ then we have $\phi_\gamma \not\sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'_2$ and the goal is immediate. Otherwise:
 - (a) $\widehat{\gamma}(e) \mapsto^* v_2, \widehat{\gamma}'(e) \mapsto^* v'_2, v_2 \text{ val}, v'_2 \text{ val}$
 - (b) $v_2 \sim v'_2 \in [A_1 \cdot \phi_1] \rightarrow [A_2 \cdot \phi_2] \mid \phi_\gamma [\phi_2] \mid [\Delta]$
- (9) Apply [item 8b](#) to [item 6](#) to obtain $\text{ap}(v_2; v_1) \sim^* \text{ap}(v'_2; c) \in [A_2 \cdot \phi_2] \mid \phi'_1 \sqcup \phi_\gamma [\phi'_2] \mid [\Delta]$.
- (10) Have $\text{ap}(\widehat{\gamma}(e); v_1) \mapsto^* \text{ap}(v_2; v_1), \text{ap}(\lambda(x.\text{ap}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e); c)); v'_1) \mapsto^* \text{ap}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e); c) \mapsto^* \text{ap}(v'_2; c)$.
- (11) The result follows by applying [Lemma 5.3](#) twice to [item 9](#) and each evaluation in [item 10](#). □

The constant function property states that a function whose argument dependencies are not a subset of those in its return value is observationally the constant function. Particularly, such a function is observationally equivalent to a function which has its argument stubbed out with some constant c . From the perspective of the observer both the original function and that which ignores its argument behave the same way. Observe that the final example from [Section 1.1](#) falls under the constant function theorem because $\circ; \alpha \not\sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \circ$. For completeness' sake, we have $\text{unit} + \text{unit} \cong \text{bool}$.

Note that the correspondence of our logical relation with observational equivalence is apparent from the fact that it does not introspect on the syntax of expressions under evaluation and from its synchronization with polarity. We (1) do not examine the structure of negatively typed computations, only observing their behavior under elimination, and (2) explicitly examine the canonical forms of positive values. This is all done modulo an observer level, which can be seen as internalizing observational equivalence. We have not yet made a point of declassification; we do so now.

5.3 Metatheoretic Mechanics of Declassification

Note that [Corollary 5.9](#) only forces the function to be constant *from the observer's perspective*. Assume we have $\phi_1 \not\sqsubseteq \phi_2$ as before, observing at ϕ_2 . We might implement a function typed at $[A_1 \cdot \phi_1] \rightarrow [[A_1 \cdot \phi_1] \cdot \phi_2]$ as $\lambda(x.\#x)$. However, eliminating the inner satisfaction at ϕ_1 immediately satisfies the non-interference condition and therefore the logical relation. The observer level ϕ_2 denotes our *perspective*: it says we cannot observe information at ϕ_1 so we may trivially equate programs at level ϕ_1 . That equality is subject to observability is central to non-interference.

Accounting for declassification requires us to generalize this idea. Instead of conditioning equality merely on *which dependencies can be observed*, it is additionally conditioned on *which dependencies were available to observe*. This is the role of the Δ which indexes the logical relation in [Figure 16](#), and accordingly Δ_0 in [Theorem 5.8](#). All dependencies which appear in the closed logical relation must be scoped under Δ . The closing map δ and the logical relation's handling of the quantifier type $\forall(\alpha.A)$ are the foremost machinery which act to ensure this. As a consequence of fixing the scope of dependency variables, we can choose whether to reason about existential dependencies according to whether we wish to reason about declassification. We can explicate this in terms of the schema for existential quantification from [Figure 12](#).

Fig. 17. Reasoning (or not) about declassification

[Figure 17](#) shows the schema, annotated. We write $A(\alpha)$ to mean that the type A may contain α . Recall that β is an existential dependency, and that α cannot mention it. $F(\beta)$ is an interface offering declassifying functions like `check` and `hash`, as before. The schema for existential quantification gives rise to two perspectives: (1) where any declassifying behavior is completely **unobserved** because β is not in scope, and (2) where the functions in $F(\beta)$ are **assumed** to conserve equalities, and the use of this interface to produce a type $A(\alpha)$ is **checked** to be in the logical relation.

Starting with the first perspective, we imagine observing a program from **outside** the existential schema, without β in scope. This corresponds to working with an instance of the closed logical relation at some Δ which does not include β . We call this ‘unobserved’ because β will never arise in any form while reasoning with the logical relation; it can never be used to trigger non-interference. That any declassification is happening is entirely invisible from this perspective. We can demonstrate this by sketching using the logical relation to show equality for some arbitrary program at the type in [Figure 17](#), and observing the goal it reduces to.

- (1) We want to show $\dots \in \forall(\alpha.\forall(\beta.F(\beta) \rightarrow A(\alpha)) \rightarrow A(\alpha)) \mid \dots [\Delta]$.
- (2) **Assume** $\Delta \vdash \phi$ and substitute it for α to get $\dots \in \forall(\beta.F(\beta) \rightarrow A(\phi)) \rightarrow A(\phi) \mid \dots [\Delta]$.
- (3) Assume $\dots \in \forall(\beta.F(\beta) \rightarrow A(\phi)) \mid \dots [\Delta]$.
- (4) Suffices to show $\dots \in A(\phi) \mid \dots [\Delta]$.

Observe that we never introduce β in this process, and $A(\phi)$ does not contain β . The critical step is in [item 2](#), where we instantiate α —and therefore the output type $A(\alpha)$ of the program—with a $\Delta \vdash \phi$ where $\beta \notin \Delta$. So reasoning about the behavior of some program which declassifies, if our perspective is from *outside* the existential, does not permit us to observe the effect of any declassifications. Put another way, declassification in our setting is *modular*. Client code downstream of some program using declassification, but which does not expose the associated existential dependency variables in its types, must reason about the program without regard to any declassifying behavior. But what if existential variables *do* appear in types?

We move now to the second perspective, which regards the *inside* of the existential—specifically the higher-order function where β is in scope. Accordingly, β can now occur within the logical relation, with the latter being indexed at Δ, β . This presents a problem. To illustrate, imagine our observer level does not include β and that there is a function at type $[\text{string} \cdot \beta] \rightarrow \text{string}$ in $F(\beta)$, akin to `hash` from [Figure 12](#). We want to use the logical relation to see what happens when it is applied. We can use non-interference to obtain related expressions at $[\text{string} \cdot \beta]$ and pass them to the function. Then the application forms are equated at `string`, but not by non-interference. Note the *equated* outputs of the function depend on its *non-equated* inputs! This disconnect can be explained by walking through the inner part of the existential via the logical relation.

- (1) We want to show $\dots \in F(\beta) \rightarrow A(\phi) \mid \dots [\Delta, \beta]$.
- (2) **Assume** $\dots \in F(\beta) \mid \dots [\Delta, \beta]$.
- (3) **Suffices to show** $\dots \in A(\phi) \mid \dots [\Delta, \beta]$.

The critical step is [item 2](#), where we *assume* our declassifying functions to be in the logical relation, and therefore to preserve equalities. We then must *show* in [item 3](#) that the computation that uses them itself establishes an equality. Importantly, the act of assuming declassifiers preserve equalities, or *ignoring* any disequalities induced—due to observable results depending on non-observable inputs—privileges them. The logical relation will only permit these assumed declassifiers to perform declassification in [item 3](#). Membership in the logical relation will not be able to be shown for expressions which attempt a non-permitted (non-assumed) declassification because a disequality will result. So it is checked that any declassification which occurs is as a consequence of operations from $F(\beta)$.

6 Related and Future Work

6.1 Declassification via Type Abstraction

The first paper to recognize the relationship between declassification and type abstraction was [Nanevski et al. \[2013\]](#), working in a verification logic embedded in a dependent type theory. Unlike in our setting, their language works directly in terms of abstract types exporting equality predicates for non-interference reasoning. Due to being coalesced with functional correctness reasoning, their specifications are quite complex. We target a type system intended to be used outside a verification setting, in general-purpose languages. [Frumin et al. \[2021\]](#) also use a relational logic, integrated with a simpler type system, to reason about declassification. Due to the expressiveness of the logic, their ability to verify the safety of declassification according to e.g. the concrete values taken on by a variable surpasses ours. We suspect extending our system to account for type-level value dependency may permit a similar degree of expressivity.

[Ngo et al. \[2020\]](#) recovers noninterference with declassification via existential quantification over types. Such quantification, however, comes with the issues noted in [Section 1.1](#): interesting computation cannot be done on abstract types, so their approach does not permit computing with secrets until they have been declassified. A follow-up paper [[Cruz and Tanter 2019](#)] approaches from a similar angle, again existentially quantifying over types. They adapt *faceted types* from

the information flow setting to make computations on secrets possible. The approach presented there is attractive, but combining quantification over dependencies and free semilattices seems to accomplish the same goals more directly and with better-understood logical foundations.

6.2 Foundations for Information Flow

Miyamoto and Igarashi [2004] discuss modal logic as the logical basis for information flow, working in a partial modal logic setting. While they do not strictly make the connection to partial modal logic or hybrid logic, it is observed that their information flow tracking connective may decompose as $@_r \Box A$. They do not make the further step to lax logic to notice that the necessity semantics is vestigial. Many of the hybrid intuitions we relied on here emerged later from Reed [2009].

Other work [Askarov et al. 2008; Halpern and O’Neill 2008] grounds information flow in epistemic logic, a flavor of modal logic which contends naturally with principals in information flow systems such as Jif [Myers 1999]. Like Jif’s model, our approach is decentralized [Myers and Liskov 2000] in that it is not based on a single trusted principal or a fixed lattice structure. Our approach differs in that our types make no statements about policy or the allowed readers and writers of data governed by such policy; this allows us to focus exclusively on information flow itself, simplifying our system. Future work could explore whether the mechanisms in Jif could be built on this foundation, and whether the intuitions from our setting might transfer to a principal-based approach.

Sterling and Harper [2022] establish a sheaf model for non-interference, using the topos-theoretic *sealing* and *transparency* modalities to selectively obscure information. We suspect that our satisfaction connective $[A \cdot \phi]$ is related to the transparency modality, exhibiting similar behavior and being of the same polarity. We are actively investigating the categorical semantics of our language and expect to shine further light on any connections here.

Finally, a fragment of the structural approach to information flow appears to be related to Algebraic Subtyping [Dolan 2017; Parreaux 2020]. In particular, one might imagine encapsulating every type T in a wrapper type $\text{IFC}[T, I]$ playing a similar role to the satisfaction connective. Information flow dependencies can then be expressed as unions of types representing dependencies, for instance $\text{IFC}[\text{int}, \text{PWD} \mid 'a \mid 'b]$. We leave a full development of this idea to future work; this may serve as a lightweight way to port our style of information flow reasoning to existing languages. It is unclear to what extent current Algebraic Subtyping systems provide support for higher-ranked quantification, though there is ongoing work [Parreaux et al. 2024] to do so.

7 Conclusion

We have provided here the *Structural Calculus of Indistinguishability*. We have described a logically motivated approach to information flow which simultaneously unlocks interesting opportunities to simplify information flow specifications and offers a modular, sound approach to declassification. We have shown that the latter captures useful programming patterns from the literature and that the treatment of non-interference for it can reuse, unchanged, the machinery for hybrid-style quantification over worlds.

8 Data Availability Statement

Referenced appendices, auxiliary definitions, and full proofs are available at Gouni et al. [2025].

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$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{HYP} \\
\frac{A \text{ valid} \in \Theta}{\Theta \Gamma \vdash A \text{ true}}
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{c}
\Box I \\
\frac{\Theta \cdot \vdash A \text{ true}}{\Theta \Gamma \vdash \Box A \text{ true}}
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{c}
\Box E \\
\frac{\Theta \Gamma \vdash \Box A \text{ true} \quad \Theta, A \text{ valid} \Gamma \vdash B \text{ true}}{\Theta \Gamma \vdash B \text{ true}}
\end{array}$$

Fig. 18. Hypothesis, Introduction, and Elimination for Modal Necessity

A Appendix: From Constructive Modal Logic to Standard Information Flow

A.1 Necessity in Constructive Modal Logic

We set course for where we left off at the end of [Section 1.1](#). In [Section A.2](#), we will point out which twists and turns lead to a language that looks like that in [Section 2.1](#), and discuss in [Section 2.2](#) how they can be straightened out to make landfall at the structural approach. Note that where we show metatheory from prior work in the following sections, we have taken liberties with the presentation to better highlight any similarities and preempt syntactic conflicts.

Our starting point is constructive modal logic, for which [Pfenning and Davies \[2001\]](#) provides a natural deduction-style presentation. Their judgment is of the form $\Theta \Gamma \vdash A \text{ true}$, where Θ contains *valid* propositions and Γ contains *true* propositions. A *valid* proposition is true regardless of which assumptions are in play. A *true* proposition is one that can be shown under some set of assumptions. Observe that this allows valid propositions to depend on *valid*—but not *true*—assumptions. They introduce modal necessity, which internalizes (reifies) the judgmental notion of validity, as the logical connective \Box . Selected rules, including the introduction and elimination rules for \Box , are given in [Figure 18](#).

The first rule, HYP, should be uncontroversial: if we have some valid proposition A in Θ , then we can conclude that it is true. The introduction rule $\Box I$, reading bottom-to-top, represents the idea of validity. It requires that if one wants to prove $\Box A$, then they must show A in the environment where only valid propositions (the contents of Θ) are available. The elimination rule $\Box E$, reading top-to-bottom, translates the $\Box A \text{ true}$ in its first premise to its judgmental form as $A \text{ valid}$, which it adds as a validity assumption to its second premise. The second premise may use it to show some B , which is then returned in the conclusion. Let us now consider the first of two paths forward.

A.2 From Modal Logic to Standard Information Flow

The presentation in [Figure 18](#) is generalized to *partial necessity* in [Nanevski \[2004\]](#), shown in [Figure 19](#). *Partial* because a validity assumption may now only be used *if an arbitrary side condition is satisfied*, rather than unconditionally. For this reason the judgmental form corresponding to necessity is now named *nec* instead of *valid*. The updated judgment is of the form $\Theta \Gamma \vdash A \text{ true} [C]$, where C is the side condition. The new validity rule HYP-PARTIAL reflects the core of the change, where a valid proposition B in Θ relativized to some side condition C —the form of that condition is left abstract, for generality—can only be used to conclude B in a context D when the satisfaction of C is implied by the satisfaction of D . Only Θ contains relativized assumptions, because it is connected to usages of \Box_C as before.

The introduction rule for partial necessity, reading from the bottom as before, requires a proof of $\Box_C A$ to show A under an empty set of assumptions and under side condition C . A subtlety here is that the valid assumptions in Θ can be used to show A , but because of the prior rule, *only those relativized to side conditions implied by C* can be used. Finally, the elimination rule again transfers the conclusion of the first premise into the assumptions of the second premise, propagating the conclusion of the latter to the conclusion of the rule. It extracts the side condition C out of the $\Box_C A$ in the first premise in order to relativize the assumption for the second premise to it. If this

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{HYP-PARTIAL} \\
\frac{B \text{ nec } [C] \in \Theta \quad C \subseteq D}{\Theta \Gamma \vdash B \text{ true } [D]} \\
\\
\text{HYP-PARTIAL} \\
\frac{\Theta \Gamma \vdash \square_C A \text{ true } [D] \quad \Theta, A \text{ nec } [C] \Gamma \vdash B \text{ true } [D]}{\Theta \Gamma \vdash B \text{ true } [D]} \\
\\
\text{HYP-PARTIAL} \\
\frac{\Theta \cdot \vdash A \text{ true } [C]}{\Theta \Gamma \vdash \square_C A \text{ true } [D]}
\end{array}$$

Fig. 19. Hypothesis and Introduction for Partial Necessity

assumption is used in proving B without being hidden inside another box, say \square_C , then HYP-PARTIAL will force $C \subseteq D$. Usages inside boxes are no cause for concern, because they will be handled upon attempting to open the box.

Partial necessity provides sufficient machinery to perform information flow reasoning, as illustrated by Miyamoto and Igarashi [2004].³ They use the judgment $\Theta \Gamma \vdash M : A [\ell]$. Over straightforward partial necessity, program terms M are added, turning the logic shown previously into a type theory. The similarities to what came before can be seen in Figure 20. The new element of interest is the ℓ in the typing judgment, which specializes the side conditions seen before to being elements of a semilattice over which the theory is parameterized. This ℓ represents the *ambient security level*: it tracks the maximum level of information the current context is permitted to observe. For instance, in Figure 3, to use data at levels α and pwd , we had to be in a context (the body of the function) expecting data at level β (the level of the return type).

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{T-MVAR} \\
\frac{x : A [\ell'] \in \Theta \quad \ell' \sqsubseteq \ell}{\Theta \Gamma \vdash x : A [\ell]} \\
\\
\text{T-LETBOX} \\
\frac{\Theta \Gamma \vdash M : \square_{\ell'} A [\ell] \quad \Theta, x : A [\ell'] \Gamma \vdash N : C [\ell]}{\Theta \Gamma \vdash \text{let } \square_{\ell'} x = M \text{ in } N : C [\ell]} \\
\\
\text{T-BOX} \\
\frac{\Theta \cdot \vdash M : A [\ell']}{\Theta \Gamma \vdash \text{box}_{\ell'} M : \square_{\ell'} A [\ell]}
\end{array}$$

Fig. 20. Partial Necessity for Information Flow, Variables and Introduction

The rule T-MVAR—previously the hypothesis rule in the logical presentation—captures exactly this idea: to use a variable x at a type A relativized to some level ℓ' , the ambient security level must be at some greater level ℓ . Intuitively, variable usage represents a (transitive) flow from that variable's data (like α or pwd) into the destination represented by the ambient security level (like δ), so the safety of that flow must be verified. The introduction rule T-BOX states that an expression $\text{box}_{\ell'} M$ which wishes to claim it depends on *at most* data at level ℓ' must be checked by setting the ambient security level to ℓ' . Here, the dropping of assumptions in Γ can be explained in information flow terms: Θ contains variables connected to usages of \square_{ℓ} , so its variables are relativized to a security level. To verify that only data at security level ℓ' and below is depended upon, the data in Γ cannot be used, because we do not know their precise security level. The

³They do not state this explicitly in the paper, instead reconstructing their approach from that in Pfenning and Davies [2001]—it is not clear whether the authors were aware of the connection between their work and partial necessity.

intuition for the elimination rule T-LETBOX carries over straightforwardly from the analogous rule for partial necessity: it binds the boxed type produced by M as a variable x in N .

We are nearly all the way to a standard information flow type system, but we still have the somewhat odd distinction between environments Θ and Γ to deal with. First, observe that the side conditions $[C]$ and $[\ell]$ in the judgments for partial modal logic behave like effects, which are known to be connected to modal possibility [Benton et al. 1998]. Second, notice that given a $\Box A$, it is rather easy to get an A from it via elimination. Not so the other way around! It was discovered by Nanevski [2004] that introducing such a rule—in other words, admitting $A \rightarrow \Box A$, which is not the case in any of the theories we have discussed so far—turns the *possibility* modality induced by the effect into a *lax* modality [Fairtlough and Mendler 1997]. The latter corresponds to *strong monads* as regularly enjoyed in functional programming. Much work on information flow [Abadi et al. 1999; Choudhury et al. 2022; Liu et al. 2024; Shikuma and Igarashi 2008; Tse and Zdancewic 2004] opts for some variant of this route,⁴ which simplifies the above rules to those in Figure 21—adapted in particular from Liu et al. [2024].

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \text{T-VAR} \\
 \frac{x : A [\ell'] \in \Gamma \quad \ell' \sqsubseteq \ell}{\Gamma \vdash x : A [\ell]}
 \end{array}
 \qquad
 \begin{array}{c}
 \text{T-BOX} \\
 \frac{\Gamma \vdash M : A [\ell']}{\Gamma \vdash \text{box}_{\ell'} M : \Box_{\ell'} A [\ell]}
 \end{array}
 \qquad
 \begin{array}{c}
 \text{T-UNBOX} \\
 \frac{\Gamma \vdash M : \Box_{\ell'} A [\ell] \quad \ell' \sqsubseteq \ell}{\Gamma \vdash \text{unbox}_{\ell'} M : A [\ell]}
 \end{array}$$

Fig. 21. Lax Information Flow

The rule for checking variables is almost completely intact; the necessity environment Θ has been rolled into Γ , which now contains variables relativized to a security level. The reason this is possible is because the introduction rule T-BOX now permits us to form a $\Box_{\ell'} A$ from any expression at type $A [\ell']$, without dropping any assumptions. So all expressions can be bound to variables that indicate their security levels. As a stylistic choice, the elimination rule is generally presented as T-UNBOX is, without any bindings introduced—though the other would work, as well. This simply means there is no difference between using a variable and unboxing an expression, as far as the effect on the ambient security level. The unboxing rule integrates the level inequality $\ell' \sqsubseteq \ell$. Note that both $A \rightarrow \Box A$ and $A \rightarrow \Box_{\ell} A$ are now both true in some way, but \Box_{ℓ} must stick around because it is indexed.

For the sake of an example, let us imagine a typing rule for $==$ that requires as its premises that both of its **string** operands are at the same security level δ , and concludes with a **bool** at the same level δ . Let us also assume that function arguments and return values are always boxed up, and that boxing is a type refinement, or done implicitly. This is a reasonable assumption, commonly employed for extra precision since the security level inside the box will not affect the ambient security level until the box is opened (if ever). With these assumptions and the rules from Figure 21 in hand, we can work out a derivation for the body of `check'` from Figure 3. This is shown in Figure 22. The syntax δA is interpreted as a boxed type $\Box_{\delta} A$.

We begin by applying T-BOX to the whole body to extract the box's security level into the judgment. It replaces a \perp security level, which represents the *bottom* element of the semilattice and the identity element for \sqcup . We then apply our mocked up rule for equality, tagged as T-EQUALS. Noticing that the environment contains boxed assumptions δA , we apply T-UNBOX to both sides of the equality—currently at type **string**—to recover the boxed types. When we do this, we must check that the information flow variables indexing the boxes—`pwd` and α respectively—are ordered less than the ambient variable β originating from the return type. T-VAR then finds exactly what it

⁴This is again not recognized in detail anywhere, as far as we have been able to find. We may be codifying folklore here!

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{T-VAR} \frac{\text{pass} : \text{pwd string } [\perp] \in \dots \quad \perp \sqsubseteq \beta}{\dots \vdash \text{pass} : \text{pwd string } [\beta] \quad \text{pwd} \sqsubseteq \beta} \quad \text{T-VAR} \frac{\text{attempt} : \alpha \text{ string } [\perp] \in \dots \quad \perp \sqsubseteq \beta}{\dots \vdash \text{attempt} : \alpha \text{ string } [\beta] \quad \alpha \sqsubseteq \beta} \\
\text{T-UNBOX} \frac{\dots \vdash \text{pass} : \text{string } [\beta]}{\dots \vdash \text{pass} : \text{string } [\beta]} \quad \text{T-UNBOX} \frac{\dots \vdash \text{attempt} : \text{string } [\beta]}{\dots \vdash \text{attempt} : \text{string } [\beta]} \\
\text{T-EQUALS} \frac{\text{pass} : \text{pwd string } [\perp], \text{attempt} : \alpha \text{ string } [\perp] \vdash \text{pass} == \text{attempt} : \text{bool } [\beta]}{\text{pass} : \text{pwd string } [\perp], \text{attempt} : \alpha \text{ string } [\perp] \vdash \text{pass} == \text{attempt} : \beta \text{ bool } [\perp]} \\
\text{T-BOX} \frac{}{\text{pass} : \text{pwd string } [\perp], \text{attempt} : \alpha \text{ string } [\perp] \vdash \text{pass} == \text{attempt} : \beta \text{ bool } [\perp]}
\end{array}$$

Fig. 22. Derivation for the Body of check'

needs in the typing environment, checking that the boxes' security levels \perp are ordered less than β , which they must be by definition. This is required because all variables must be tagged with security levels, even those at box type. You might imagine that, as default behavior, when T-Box is used on some expression its new ambient security level to \perp —this is perfectly secure.

B Appendix: Definitions

B.1 Operational Semantics

$\frac{}{\langle \rangle \text{ val}}$	$\frac{v \text{ val}}{l \cdot v \text{ val}}$	$\frac{v \text{ val}}{r \cdot v \text{ val}}$	$\frac{v_1 \text{ val} \quad v_2 \text{ val}}{\langle v_1, v_2 \rangle \text{ val}}$	$\frac{}{\#e \text{ val}}$	$\frac{}{\lambda(x.e) \text{ val}}$
$\frac{}{\Lambda(\alpha.e) \text{ val}}$	$\frac{e \mapsto e'}{!e \mapsto !e'}$	$\frac{}{!\#e \mapsto e}$	$\frac{e \mapsto e'}{l \cdot e \mapsto l \cdot e'}$	$\frac{e \mapsto e'}{r \cdot e \mapsto r \cdot e'}$	
$\frac{\text{E-CASE-CONG} \quad e \mapsto e'}{\text{case } e \{ l \cdot x_1 \hookrightarrow e_1 \mid r \cdot x_2 \hookrightarrow e_2 \} \mapsto \text{case } e \{ l \cdot x_1 \hookrightarrow e_1 \mid r \cdot x_2 \hookrightarrow e_2 \}}$					
$\frac{\text{E-CASE-}\beta 1 \quad l \cdot e \text{ val}}{\text{case } l \cdot e \{ l \cdot x_1 \hookrightarrow e_1 \mid r \cdot x_2 \hookrightarrow e_2 \} \mapsto [e/x_1]e_1}$					
$\frac{\text{E-CASE-}\beta 2 \quad r \cdot e \text{ val}}{\text{case } r \cdot e \{ l \cdot x_1 \hookrightarrow e_1 \mid r \cdot x_2 \hookrightarrow e_2 \} \mapsto [e/x_2]e_2}$			$\frac{\text{E-PAIR-CONG1} \quad e_1 \mapsto e'_1}{\langle e_1, e_2 \rangle \mapsto \langle e'_1, e_2 \rangle}$		
$\frac{\text{E-PAIR-CONG2} \quad e_1 \text{ val} \quad e_2 \mapsto e'_2}{\langle e_1, e_2 \rangle \mapsto \langle e_1, e'_2 \rangle}$		$\frac{\text{E-SPLIT-CONG} \quad e_1 \mapsto e'_1}{\text{split } e_1 \text{ into } \langle x_1, x_2 \rangle \text{ in } e_2 \mapsto \text{split } e'_1 \text{ into } \langle x_1, x_2 \rangle \text{ in } e_2}$			
$\frac{\text{E-SPLIT-}\beta \quad \langle e_1, e_2 \rangle \text{ val}}{\text{split } \langle e_1, e_2 \rangle \text{ into } \langle x_1, x_2 \rangle \text{ in } e \mapsto [e_2/x_2][e_1/x_1]e}$			$\frac{\text{E-AP-CONG1} \quad e_1 \mapsto e'_1}{\text{ap}(e_1; e_2) \mapsto \text{ap}(e'_1; e_2)}$		
$\frac{\text{E-AP-CONG2} \quad e_1 \text{ val} \quad e_2 \mapsto e'_2}{\text{ap}(e_1; e_2) \mapsto \text{ap}(e_1; e'_2)}$		$\frac{\text{E-AP-}\beta \quad e_2 \text{ val}}{\text{ap}(\lambda(x.e); e_2) \mapsto [e_2/x]e}$		$\frac{\text{E-DEPAP-CONG} \quad e \mapsto e'}{e[\phi] \mapsto e'[\phi]}$	
$\frac{\text{E-DEPAP-}\beta}{\Lambda(\alpha.e)[\phi'] \mapsto [\phi'/\alpha]e}$					

B.2 Environment Formation

$\frac{}{\circ \text{ venv}}$	$\frac{\Gamma \text{ venv}}{\Gamma, x : A \text{ venv}}$	$\frac{}{\circ \text{ denv}}$	$\frac{\Delta \text{ denv}}{\Delta, \alpha \text{ denv}}$
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B.3 Formation

B.3.1 $\Delta \vdash \alpha$.

$$\text{F-1} \quad \frac{}{\Delta, \alpha \vdash \alpha}$$

B.3.2 $\Delta \vdash \phi$.

$$\text{F-2} \quad \frac{}{\Delta \vdash \circ} \quad \text{F-3} \quad \frac{\Delta \vdash \alpha \quad \Delta \vdash \phi}{\Delta \vdash \phi; \alpha}$$

B.3.3 $\Delta \vdash A$.

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{F-4} \quad \frac{}{\Delta \vdash \text{unit}} \quad \text{F-5} \quad \frac{\Delta, \alpha \vdash A}{\Delta \vdash \forall(\alpha.A)} \quad \text{F-6} \quad \frac{\Delta \vdash A_1 \quad \Delta \vdash A_2}{\Delta \vdash A_1 \rightarrow A_2} \quad \text{F-7} \quad \frac{\Delta \vdash A \quad \Delta \vdash \phi}{\Delta \vdash [A \cdot \phi]} \quad \text{F-8} \quad \frac{\Delta \vdash A_1 \quad \Delta \vdash A_2}{\Delta \vdash A_1 + A_2} \\ \\ \text{F-9} \quad \frac{\Delta \vdash A_1 \quad \Delta \vdash A_2}{\Delta \vdash A_1 \otimes A_2} \end{array}$$

B.3.4 $\Delta \vdash e$.

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{F-10} \quad \frac{}{\Delta \vdash \langle \rangle} \quad \text{F-11} \quad \frac{}{\Delta \vdash x} \quad \text{F-12} \quad \frac{\Delta \vdash e}{\Delta \vdash \#e} \quad \text{F-13} \quad \frac{\Delta \vdash e}{\Delta \vdash !e} \quad \text{F-14} \quad \frac{\Delta \vdash e}{\Delta \vdash l \cdot e} \quad \text{F-15} \quad \frac{\Delta \vdash e}{\Delta \vdash r \cdot e} \\ \\ \text{F-16} \quad \frac{\Delta \vdash e \quad \Delta \vdash e_1 \quad \Delta \vdash e_2}{\Delta \vdash \text{case } e \{ l \cdot x_1 \hookrightarrow e_1 \mid r \cdot x_2 \hookrightarrow e_2 \}} \quad \text{F-17} \quad \frac{\Delta \vdash e_1 \quad \Delta \vdash e_2}{\Delta \vdash \langle e_1, e_2 \rangle} \\ \\ \text{F-18} \quad \frac{\Delta \vdash e_1 \quad \Delta \vdash e_2}{\Delta \vdash \text{split } e_1 \text{ into } \langle x_1, x_2 \rangle \text{ in } e_2} \quad \text{F-19} \quad \frac{\Delta \vdash e}{\Delta \vdash \lambda(x.e)} \quad \text{F-20} \quad \frac{\Delta \vdash e_1 \quad \Delta \vdash e_2}{\Delta \vdash \text{ap}(e_1; e_2)} \quad \text{F-21} \quad \frac{\Delta, \alpha \vdash e}{\Delta \vdash \Lambda(\alpha.e)} \\ \\ \text{F-22} \quad \frac{\Delta \vdash e \quad \Delta \vdash \phi}{\Delta \vdash e[\phi]} \end{array}$$

B.3.5 $\Gamma \vdash e$.

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{F-23} \quad \frac{}{\Gamma \vdash \langle \rangle} \quad \text{F-24} \quad \frac{x \in \Gamma}{\Gamma \vdash x} \quad \text{F-25} \quad \frac{\Gamma \vdash e}{\Gamma \vdash \#e} \quad \text{F-26} \quad \frac{\Gamma \vdash e}{\Gamma \vdash !e} \quad \text{F-27} \quad \frac{\Gamma \vdash e}{\Gamma \vdash l \cdot e} \quad \text{F-28} \quad \frac{\Gamma \vdash e}{\Gamma \vdash r \cdot e} \\ \\ \text{F-29} \quad \frac{\Gamma \vdash e \quad \Gamma, x_1 \vdash e_1 \quad \Gamma, x_2 \vdash e_2}{\Gamma \vdash \text{case } e \{ l \cdot x_1 \hookrightarrow e_1 \mid r \cdot x_2 \hookrightarrow e_2 \}} \quad \text{F-30} \quad \frac{\Gamma \vdash e_1 \quad \Gamma \vdash e_2}{\Gamma \vdash \langle e_1, e_2 \rangle} \\ \\ \text{F-31} \quad \frac{\Gamma \vdash e_1 \quad \Gamma, x_1, x_2 \vdash e_2}{\Gamma \vdash \text{split } e_1 \text{ into } \langle x_1, x_2 \rangle \text{ in } e_2} \quad \text{F-32} \quad \frac{\Gamma, x \vdash e}{\Gamma \vdash \lambda(x.e)} \quad \text{F-33} \quad \frac{\Gamma \vdash e_1 \quad \Gamma \vdash e_2}{\Gamma \vdash \text{ap}(e_1; e_2)} \quad \text{F-34} \quad \frac{\Gamma \vdash e}{\Gamma \vdash \Lambda(\alpha.e)} \quad \text{F-35} \quad \frac{\Gamma \vdash e}{\Gamma \vdash e[\phi]} \end{array}$$

B.4 $\phi_1 \sqcup \phi_2$

$$\begin{aligned}\phi_1 \sqcup \circ &\triangleq \phi_1 \\ \phi_1 \sqcup \phi_2; \alpha &\triangleq (\phi_1 \sqcup \phi_2); \alpha\end{aligned}$$

B.5 $\phi_1 \equiv \phi_2$

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{E-REFL} \\ \hline \phi \equiv \phi \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{c} \text{E-SYM} \\ \phi_2 \equiv \phi_1 \\ \hline \phi_1 \equiv \phi_2 \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{c} \text{E-TRANS} \\ \phi_1 \equiv \phi_2 \quad \phi_2 \equiv \phi_3 \\ \hline \phi_1 \equiv \phi_3 \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{c} \text{E-CONTRACT} \\ \phi_1 \equiv \phi_2; \alpha \sqcup \phi'_2 \\ \hline \phi_1 \equiv \phi_2; \alpha; \alpha \sqcup \phi'_2 \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{c} \text{E-EXCHANGE} \\ \phi_1 \equiv \phi_2 \sqcup \phi'_2; \alpha \sqcup \phi''_2 \\ \hline \phi_1 \equiv \phi_2; \alpha \sqcup \phi'_2 \sqcup \phi''_2 \end{array}$$

B.6 $\phi_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{I-REFL} \\ \phi_1 \equiv \phi_2 \\ \hline \phi_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2 \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{c} \text{I-WEAKEN} \\ \Delta \vdash \alpha \quad \phi_1; \alpha \sqcup \phi'_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2 \\ \hline \phi_1 \sqcup \phi'_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2 \end{array}$$

B.7 $A_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A_2$

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{S-UNIT} \\ \hline \text{unit} \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \text{unit} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{c} \text{S-SUM} \\ A_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A'_1 \quad A_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A'_2 \\ \hline A_1 + A_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A'_1 + A'_2 \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{c} \text{S-PROD} \\ A_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A'_1 \quad A_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A'_2 \\ \hline A_1 \otimes A_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A'_1 \otimes A'_2 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{S-DEP} \\ A_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A_2 \quad \phi_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2 \\ \hline [A_1 \cdot \phi_1] \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} [A_2 \cdot \phi_2] \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{c} \text{S-ARROW} \\ A'_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A_1 \quad A_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A'_2 \\ \hline A_1 \rightarrow A_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A'_1 \rightarrow A'_2 \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{c} \text{S-ALL} \\ A_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta, \alpha} A_2 \\ \hline \forall(\alpha. A_1) \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \forall(\alpha. A_2) \end{array}$$

B.8 Substitution

Note that we work with substitution on terms and types determined up to α -equivalence; capture is not a concern. Substitution into expressions is as usual.

$$\begin{aligned}[\phi/\alpha] \circ &\triangleq \circ \\ [\phi/\alpha] \Gamma, x : A &\triangleq ([\phi/\alpha] \Gamma), x : [\phi/\alpha] A \\ [\phi/\alpha] \circ &\triangleq \circ \\ [\phi/\alpha] (\phi'; \alpha) &\triangleq [\phi/\alpha] \phi' \sqcup \phi \\ [\phi/\alpha] (\phi'; \alpha') &\triangleq [\phi/\alpha] \phi'; \alpha' \\ [\phi/\alpha] \text{unit} &\triangleq \text{unit} \\ [\phi/\alpha] \forall(\alpha'. A) &\triangleq \forall(\alpha'. [\phi/\alpha] A) \\ [\phi/\alpha] A_1 \rightarrow A_2 &\triangleq [\phi/\alpha] A_1 \rightarrow [\phi/\alpha] A_2 \\ [\phi/\alpha] [A \cdot \phi'] &\triangleq [[\phi/\alpha] A \cdot [\phi/\alpha] \phi'] \\ [\phi/\alpha] A_1 + A_2 &\triangleq [\phi/\alpha] A_1 + [\phi/\alpha] A_2 \\ [\phi/\alpha] A_1 \otimes A_2 &\triangleq [\phi/\alpha] A_1 \otimes [\phi/\alpha] A_2\end{aligned}$$

C Appendix: Non-interference

Lemma C.1 (Associativity of \sqcup). $(\phi_1 \sqcup \phi_2) \sqcup \phi_3 = \phi_1 \sqcup (\phi_2 \sqcup \phi_3)$

PROOF. Proceed by induction on ϕ_3 .

(1) Case: $\phi_3 = \circ$

$$\begin{aligned} (\phi_1 \sqcup \phi_2) \sqcup \phi_3 &\triangleq (\phi_1 \sqcup \phi_2) \sqcup \circ \\ &\triangleq \phi_1 \sqcup \phi_2 \\ &\triangleq \phi_1 \sqcup (\phi_2 \sqcup \circ) \\ &\triangleq \phi_1 \sqcup (\phi_2 \sqcup \phi_3) \end{aligned}$$

(2) Case: $\phi_3 = \phi'_3; \alpha$

$$\begin{aligned} (\phi_1 \sqcup \phi_2) \sqcup \phi_3 &\triangleq (\phi_1 \sqcup \phi_2) \sqcup \phi'_3; \alpha \\ &\triangleq ((\phi_1 \sqcup \phi_2) \sqcup \phi'_3); \alpha \\ &\triangleq (\phi_1 \sqcup (\phi_2 \sqcup \phi'_3)); \alpha \\ &\triangleq \phi_1 \sqcup (\phi_2 \sqcup \phi'_3); \alpha \\ &\triangleq \phi_1 \sqcup (\phi_2 \sqcup \phi'_3; \alpha) \\ &\triangleq \phi_1 \sqcup (\phi_2 \sqcup \phi_3) \end{aligned}$$

□

Lemma C.2 (Substitution distributes over \sqcup). $[\phi/\alpha](\phi_1 \sqcup \phi_2) = [\phi/\alpha]\phi_1 \sqcup [\phi/\alpha]\phi_2$

PROOF. Proceed by induction on ϕ_2 .

(1) Case: $\phi_2 = \circ$

$$\begin{aligned} [\phi/\alpha](\phi_1 \sqcup \phi_2) &\triangleq [\phi/\alpha](\phi_1 \sqcup \circ) \\ &\triangleq [\phi/\alpha]\phi_1 \\ &\triangleq [\phi/\alpha]\phi_1 \sqcup \circ \\ &\triangleq [\phi/\alpha]\phi_1 \sqcup [\phi/\alpha]\circ \\ &\triangleq [\phi/\alpha]\phi_1 \sqcup [\phi/\alpha]\phi_2 \end{aligned}$$

(2) Case: $\phi_2 = \phi'_2; \alpha'$ where $\alpha' \neq \alpha$

$$\begin{aligned} [\phi/\alpha](\phi_1 \sqcup \phi_2) &\triangleq [\phi/\alpha](\phi_1 \sqcup \phi'_2; \alpha') \\ &\triangleq [\phi/\alpha]((\phi_1 \sqcup \phi'_2); \alpha') \\ &\triangleq [\phi/\alpha](\phi_1 \sqcup \phi'_2); \alpha' \\ &\triangleq ([\phi/\alpha]\phi_1 \sqcup [\phi/\alpha]\phi'_2); \alpha' \\ &\triangleq [\phi/\alpha]\phi_1 \sqcup [\phi/\alpha]\phi'_2; \alpha' \\ &\triangleq [\phi/\alpha]\phi_1 \sqcup [\phi/\alpha](\phi'_2; \alpha') \\ &\triangleq [\phi/\alpha]\phi_1 \sqcup [\phi/\alpha]\phi_2 \end{aligned}$$

(3) Case: $\phi_2 = \phi'_2; \alpha$

$$\begin{aligned}
[\phi/\alpha](\phi_1 \sqcup \phi_2) &\triangleq [\phi/\alpha](\phi_1 \sqcup \phi'_2; \alpha) \\
&\triangleq [\phi/\alpha](\phi_1 \sqcup \phi'_2); \alpha \\
&\triangleq [\phi/\alpha](\phi_1 \sqcup \phi'_2) \sqcup \phi \\
&\triangleq ([\phi/\alpha]\phi_1 \sqcup [\phi/\alpha]\phi'_2) \sqcup \phi \\
&\triangleq [\phi/\alpha]\phi_1 \sqcup ([\phi/\alpha]\phi'_2 \sqcup \phi) \\
&\triangleq [\phi/\alpha]\phi_1 \sqcup [\phi/\alpha](\phi'_2; \alpha) \\
&\triangleq [\phi/\alpha]\phi_1 \sqcup [\phi/\alpha]\phi_2
\end{aligned}$$

□

Lemma C.3 (Transitivity of \sqsubseteq_{Δ}). *If $\phi_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$ and $\phi_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_3$ then $\phi_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_3$.*

PROOF. Proceed by induction on $\phi_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$.

(1) Case: I-REFL

(a) Then we have that $\phi_1 = \phi_2$.

(b) So we have the property immediately by rewriting ϕ_2 to ϕ_1 in the second assumption.

(2) Case: I-WEAKEN

(a) Then we have that $\phi_1 = \phi'_1 \sqcup \phi''_1$.

(b) And we have as a premise that $\phi'_1; \alpha \sqcup \phi''_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$.

(c) By applying the induction hypothesis to this result and the second assumption, we have $\phi'_1; \alpha \sqcup \phi''_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_3$.

(d) We also have as a premise that $\Delta \vdash \alpha$.

(e) By applying this and $\phi'_1; \alpha \sqcup \phi''_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_3$ to I-WEAKEN we have that $\phi'_1 \sqcup \phi''_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_3$.

(f) So we have $\phi_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_3$, by definition of ϕ_1 .

□

Lemma C.4 (\sqcup preserves \equiv). *If $\phi_1 \equiv \phi'_1$ and $\phi_2 \equiv \phi'_2$ then $\phi_1 \sqcup \phi_2 \equiv \phi'_1 \sqcup \phi'_2$.*

PROOF. Proceed by induction on $\phi_2 \equiv \phi'_2$.

(1) Case: E-REFL

(a) Then we have that $\phi_2 \equiv \phi_2$.

(b) Want to show $\phi_1 \sqcup \phi_2 \equiv \phi'_1 \sqcup \phi_2$.

(c) From $\phi_1 \equiv \phi'_1$ we have some $\phi''_1 \equiv \phi'_1$ where ϕ_1 and ϕ'_1 can both be rewritten to ϕ''_1 .

(d) Apply the same series of rewrites to $\phi_1 \sqcup \phi_2 \equiv \phi'_1 \sqcup \phi_2$ to get $\phi''_1 \sqcup \phi_2 \equiv \phi''_1 \sqcup \phi_2$, observing that all equality rules operate on the relative positions of manipulated dependencies.

(e) We can then apply E-REFL to this equality.

(2) Case: E-SYM

(a) Then we have that $\phi_2 \equiv \phi'_2$.

(b) We have as a premise that $\phi'_2 \equiv \phi_2$.

(c) Apply E-SYM to $\phi_1 \equiv \phi'_1$ to obtain $\phi'_1 \equiv \phi_1$.

(d) Apply the induction hypothesis to 2c and 2b to obtain $\phi'_1 \sqcup \phi'_2 \equiv \phi_1 \sqcup \phi_2$.

(e) Apply E-SYM to 2d to obtain $\phi_1 \sqcup \phi_2 \equiv \phi'_1 \sqcup \phi'_2$.

(3) Case: E-TRANS

(a) Then we have that $\phi_2 \equiv \phi''_2$.

(b) We have as premises that $\phi_2 \equiv \phi'_2$ and $\phi'_2 \equiv \phi''_2$.

(c) Apply the induction hypothesis to $\phi_1 \equiv \phi'_1$ and $\phi_2 \equiv \phi'_2$ to obtain $\phi_1 \sqcup \phi_2 \equiv \phi'_1 \sqcup \phi'_2$.

- (d) Apply the induction hypothesis to $\phi'_1 \equiv \phi'_1$ and $\phi'_2 \equiv \phi''_2$ to obtain $\phi'_1 \sqcup \phi'_2 \equiv \phi'_1 \sqcup \phi''_2$.
- (e) Apply E-TRANS to 3c and 3d to obtain $\phi_1 \sqcup \phi_2 \equiv \phi'_1 \sqcup \phi''_2$.
- (4) Case: E-CONTRACT
 - (a) Then we have that $\phi'_2 = \phi_3; \alpha; \alpha \sqcup \phi'_3$.
 - (b) And we have as a premise that $\phi_2 \equiv \phi_3; \alpha \sqcup \phi'_3$.
 - (c) By applying the induction hypothesis to our first assumption and this premise we have $\phi_1 \sqcup \phi_2 \equiv \phi'_1 \sqcup \phi_3; \alpha \sqcup \phi'_3$.
 - (d) By using the associativity and definition of \sqcup we have $\phi_1 \sqcup \phi_2 \equiv (\phi'_1 \sqcup \phi_3); \alpha \sqcup \phi'_3$.
 - (e) By applying E-CONTRACT to this we have the result.
- (5) Case: E-EXCHANGE
 - (a) Then we have that $\phi'_2 \equiv \phi_3; \alpha \sqcup \phi'_3 \sqcup \phi''_3$.
 - (b) And we have as a premise that $\phi_2 \equiv \phi_3 \sqcup \phi'_3; \alpha \sqcup \phi''_3$.
 - (c) By applying the induction hypothesis to our first assumption and this premise we have $\phi_1 \sqcup \phi_2 \equiv \phi'_1 \sqcup \phi_3 \sqcup \phi'_3; \alpha \sqcup \phi''_3$.
 - (d) By using associativity of \sqcup we have $\phi_1 \sqcup \phi_2 \equiv (\phi'_1 \sqcup \phi_3) \sqcup \phi'_3; \alpha \sqcup \phi''_3$.
 - (e) By applying to E-EXCHANGE this we have the result.

□

Lemma C.5 (Monotonicity of \sqsubseteq_{Δ} and \sqcup). *If $\phi_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'_1$ and $\phi_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'_2$ then $\phi_1 \sqcup \phi_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'_1 \sqcup \phi'_2$.*

PROOF. Proceed by induction on $\phi_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'_1$ and $\phi_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'_2$.

- (1) Case: I-REFL, I-REFL
 - (a) Then we have:
 - (i) $\phi_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'_1$
 - (ii) $\phi_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'_2$
 - (b) And we have as premises:
 - (i) $\phi_1 \equiv \phi'_1$
 - (ii) $\phi_2 \equiv \phi'_2$
 - (c) Show $\phi_1 \sqcup \phi_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'_1 \sqcup \phi'_2$.
 - (d) Apply Lemma C.4 to 1(b)i and 1(b)ii to obtain $\phi_1 \sqcup \phi_2 \equiv \phi'_1 \sqcup \phi'_2$.
 - (e) Apply I-REFL to 1d to obtain $\phi_1 \sqcup \phi_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'_1 \sqcup \phi'_2$.
- (2) Case: I-REFL, I-WEAKEN
 - (a) Then we have:
 - (i) $\phi_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'_1$
 - (ii) $\phi_2 \sqcup \phi''_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'_2$
 - (b) And we have as premises $\Delta \vdash \alpha$ and $\phi_2; \alpha \sqcup \phi''_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'_2$.
 - (c) Show that $\phi_2 \sqcup \phi''_2 \sqcup \phi_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'_2 \sqcup \phi'_1$.
 - (d) Apply the induction hypothesis to 2b and 2(a)i to obtain $\phi_2; \alpha \sqcup \phi''_2 \sqcup \phi_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'_2 \sqcup \phi'_1$.
 - (e) 2d is equivalent to $\phi_2; \alpha \sqcup (\phi''_2 \sqcup \phi_1) \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'_2 \sqcup \phi'_1$.
 - (f) Apply I-WEAKEN to $\Delta \vdash \alpha$ and 2e to obtain $\phi_2 \sqcup (\phi''_2 \sqcup \phi_1) \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'_2 \sqcup \phi'_1$.
 - (g) 2f is equivalent to $\phi_2 \sqcup \phi''_2 \sqcup \phi_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'_2 \sqcup \phi'_1$.
- (3) Case: I-WEAKEN, I-REFL
 - (a) Then we have:
 - (i) $\phi_1 \sqcup \phi''_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'_1$
 - (ii) $\phi_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'_2$
 - (b) And we have as premises $\Delta \vdash \alpha$ and $\phi_1; \alpha \sqcup \phi''_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'_1$.
 - (c) Show that $\phi_1 \sqcup \phi''_1 \sqcup \phi_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'_1 \sqcup \phi'_2$.
 - (d) Apply the induction hypothesis to 3b and 3(a)ii to obtain $\phi_1; \alpha \sqcup \phi''_1 \sqcup \phi_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'_1 \sqcup \phi'_2$.

- (e) **3d** is equivalent to $\phi_1; \alpha \sqcup (\phi_1'' \sqcup \phi_2) \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_1' \sqcup \phi_2'$.
- (f) Apply I-WEAKEN to $\Delta \vdash \alpha$ and **3e** to obtain $\phi_1 \sqcup (\phi_1'' \sqcup \phi_2) \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_1' \sqcup \phi_2'$.
- (g) **3f** is equivalent to $\phi_1 \sqcup \phi_1'' \sqcup \phi_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_1' \sqcup \phi_2'$.
- (4) Case: I-WEAKEN, I-WEAKEN
 - (a) Then we have:
 - (i) $\phi_1 \sqcup \phi_1'' \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_1'$
 - (ii) $\phi_2 \sqcup \phi_2'' \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2'$
 - (b) And we have as premises:
 - (i) $\Delta \vdash \alpha_1$ and $\phi_1; \alpha_1 \sqcup \phi_1'' \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_1'$
 - (ii) $\Delta \vdash \alpha_2$ and $\phi_2; \alpha_2 \sqcup \phi_2'' \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2'$
 - (c) Show that $\phi_1 \sqcup \phi_1'' \sqcup \phi_2 \sqcup \phi_2'' \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_1' \sqcup \phi_2'$.
 - (d) Apply the induction hypothesis to $\phi_1; \alpha_1 \sqcup \phi_1'' \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_1'$ and $\phi_2; \alpha_2 \sqcup \phi_2'' \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2'$ to get $\phi_1; \alpha_1 \sqcup \phi_1'' \sqcup \phi_2; \alpha_2 \sqcup \phi_2'' \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_1' \sqcup \phi_2'$.
 - (e) **4d** is equivalent to $\phi_1; \alpha_1 \sqcup (\phi_1'' \sqcup \phi_2; \alpha_2 \sqcup \phi_2'') \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_1' \sqcup \phi_2'$.
 - (f) Apply I-WEAKEN to $\Delta \vdash \alpha_1$ and **4e** to get $\phi_1 \sqcup (\phi_1'' \sqcup \phi_2; \alpha_2 \sqcup \phi_2'') \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_1' \sqcup \phi_2'$.
 - (g) **4f** is equivalent to $(\phi_1 \sqcup \phi_1'' \sqcup \phi_2); \alpha_2 \sqcup \phi_2'' \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_1' \sqcup \phi_2'$.
 - (h) Apply I-WEAKEN to $\Delta \vdash \alpha_2$ and **4g** to get $(\phi_1 \sqcup \phi_1'' \sqcup \phi_2) \sqcup \phi_2'' \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_1' \sqcup \phi_2'$.
 - (i) **4h** is equivalent to $\phi_1 \sqcup \phi_1'' \sqcup \phi_2 \sqcup \phi_2'' \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_1' \sqcup \phi_2'$.

□

Lemma C.6 (Monotonicity of \sqsubseteq_{Δ} and \sqcup). *If $\phi_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$ then $\phi \sqcup \phi_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi \sqcup \phi_2$ and $\phi_1 \sqcup \phi \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2 \sqcup \phi$.*

PROOF. Prove the first element of the conjunction.

- (1) We have $\phi \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi$ by E-REFL followed by I-REFL.
- (2) Apply Lemma C.5 to $\phi \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi$ and $\phi_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$ to obtain $\phi \sqcup \phi_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi \sqcup \phi_2$.

Prove the second element of the conjunction.

- (1) We have $\phi \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi$ by E-REFL followed by I-REFL.
- (2) Apply Lemma C.5 to $\phi_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$ and $\phi \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi$ to obtain $\phi_1 \sqcup \phi \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2 \sqcup \phi$.

□

Lemma C.7 (Containment). *If $\phi_1 \not\sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$ then $\forall \phi . \phi_1 \sqcup \phi \not\sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$.*

PROOF. Proceed directly.

- (1) Assume $\phi_1 \not\sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$.
- (2) Assume for a contradiction that there exists some ϕ such that $\phi_1 \sqcup \phi \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$.
- (3) Then repeatedly apply I-WEAKEN to **2** to obtain $\phi_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$
- (4) This contradicts **1**.

□

Lemma C.8 (Anti-transitivity 1). *If $\phi_1 \not\sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$ and $\phi_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_1'$ then $\phi_1' \not\sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$.*

PROOF. Proceed directly.

- (1) Assume for a contradiction that $\phi_1' \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$.
- (2) Then we could use Lemma C.3 with our second assumption and the contrary assumption to obtain $\phi_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$.
- (3) This contradicts our first assumption.

□

Lemma C.9 (Anti-transitivity 2). *If $\phi_1 \not\sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$ and $\phi_2' \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$ then $\phi_1 \not\sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2'$.*

PROOF. Proceed directly.

- (1) Assume for a contradiction that $\phi_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'_2$.
- (2) Then we have by Lemma C.3 on this and our second assumption that $\phi_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$.
- (3) This contradicts our first assumption.

□

Lemma C.10 (Lifted Weakening). *If $\Delta \vdash \phi$ and $\phi_1 \sqcup \phi \sqcup \phi_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'$ then $\phi_1 \sqcup \phi_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'$*

PROOF. Proceed by induction on ϕ .

- (1) Case: \circ
 - (a) We must show $\phi_1 \sqcup \phi_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'$.
 - (b) We have this by the second assumption.
- (2) Case: $\phi''; \alpha$
 - (a) We must show $\phi_1 \sqcup \phi_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'$.
 - (b) We have by assumption that $\phi_1 \sqcup \phi''; \alpha \sqcup \phi_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'$.
 - (c) By $\Delta \vdash \phi''; \alpha$ we have $\Delta \vdash \alpha$.
 - (d) We have by I-WEAKEN and $\Delta \vdash \alpha$ that $\phi_1 \sqcup \phi'' \sqcup \phi_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'$.
 - (e) Apply the induction hypothesis to obtain $\phi_1 \sqcup \phi_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'$.

□

Lemma C.11 (Lifted Contraction). *If $\phi_1 \sqcup \phi \sqcup \phi_2 \equiv \phi'$ then $\phi_1 \sqcup \phi \sqcup \phi \sqcup \phi_2 \equiv \phi'$*

PROOF. Proceed by induction on ϕ .

- (1) Case: \circ
 - (a) Then we must show $\phi_1 \sqcup \circ \sqcup \circ \sqcup \phi_2 \equiv \phi'$.
 - (b) This is the same as $\phi_1 \sqcup \phi_2 \equiv \phi'$.
 - (c) We have this by assumption.
- (2) Case: $\phi''; \alpha$
 - (a) Then we must show $\phi_1 \sqcup \phi''; \alpha \sqcup \phi''; \alpha \sqcup \phi_2 \equiv \phi'$.
 - (b) We have by assumption that $\phi_1 \sqcup \phi''; \alpha \sqcup \phi_2 \equiv \phi'$.
 - (c) We have by E-SYM and E-CONTRACT that $\phi_1 \sqcup \phi''; \alpha; \alpha \sqcup \phi_2 \equiv \phi'$.
 - (d) And so $\phi_1 \sqcup \phi'' \sqcup \circ; \alpha; \alpha \sqcup \phi_2 \equiv \phi'$.
 - (e) Rewrite using the induction hypothesis to obtain $\phi_1 \sqcup \phi'' \sqcup \phi'' \sqcup \circ; \alpha; \alpha \sqcup \phi_2 \equiv \phi'$.
 - (f) We have by E-SYM and E-EXCHANGE that $\phi_1 \sqcup \phi''; \alpha \sqcup \phi'' \sqcup \circ; \alpha \sqcup \phi_2 \equiv \phi'$.
 - (g) This is the same as $\phi_1 \sqcup \phi''; \alpha \sqcup \phi''; \alpha \sqcup \phi_2 \equiv \phi'$.

□

Lemma C.12 (Lifted Exchange). *If $\phi_1 \sqcup \phi \sqcup \phi_2 \sqcup \phi_3 \equiv \phi'$ then $\phi_1 \sqcup \phi_2 \sqcup \phi \sqcup \phi_3 \equiv \phi'$*

PROOF. Proceed by induction on ϕ .

- (1) Case: \circ
 - (a) Then we must show $\phi_1 \sqcup \phi_2 \sqcup \circ \sqcup \phi_3 \equiv \phi'$.
 - (b) This is the same as $\phi_1 \sqcup \phi_2 \sqcup \phi_3 \equiv \phi'$.
 - (c) We have this by assumption.
- (2) Case: $\phi''; \alpha$
 - (a) Then we must show $\phi_1 \sqcup \phi_2 \sqcup \phi''; \alpha \sqcup \phi_3 \equiv \phi'$.
 - (b) We have by assumption that $\phi_1 \sqcup \phi''; \alpha \sqcup \phi_2 \sqcup \phi_3 \equiv \phi'$.
 - (c) This is the same as $\phi_1 \sqcup \phi'' \sqcup \circ; \alpha \sqcup \phi_2 \sqcup \phi_3 \equiv \phi'$.
 - (d) Rewrite using the induction hypothesis to obtain $\phi_1 \sqcup \circ; \alpha \sqcup \phi_2 \sqcup \phi'' \sqcup \phi_3 \equiv \phi'$.

- (e) Apply E-EXCHANGE repeatedly to $\phi_2 \sqcup \phi''$ to obtain $\phi_1 \sqcup \circ \sqcup \phi_2 \sqcup \phi''$; $\alpha \sqcup \phi_3 \equiv \phi'$.
- (f) This is equivalent to $\phi_1 \sqcup \phi_2 \sqcup \phi''$; $\alpha \sqcup \phi_3 \equiv \phi'$.

□

Lemma C.13 (Strengthening). *If $\Delta, \alpha \vdash \alpha'$ where $\alpha \neq \alpha'$ then $\Delta \vdash \alpha'$.*

PROOF. Proceed directly.

- (1) Observe that $\circ, \alpha' \vdash \alpha'$ by F-1.
- (2) We can weaken all the elements of Δ besides α' , denoted Δ' , on to this result to obtain $\Delta', \alpha' \vdash \alpha'$.
- (3) Observe that $\Delta', \alpha' = \Delta$, by definition of Δ' .
- (4) So we have $\Delta \vdash \alpha'$.

□

Lemma C.14 (\sqcup Preserves Well-Formedness). *$\Delta \vdash \phi_1$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi_2$ iff $\Delta \vdash \phi_1 \sqcup \phi_2$.*

PROOF. Consider the forward direction, assuming that $\Delta \vdash \phi_1$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi_2$ and showing $\Delta \vdash \phi_1 \sqcup \phi_2$. Proceed by induction on ϕ_2 .

- (1) Case: \circ
 - (a) Then we have that $\phi_1 \sqcup \circ = \phi_1$.
 - (b) We have $\Delta \vdash \phi_1$ by assumption.
- (2) Case: $\phi'_2; \alpha$
 - (a) Then we have that $\phi_1 \sqcup \phi'_2; \alpha = (\phi_1 \sqcup \phi'_2); \alpha$.
 - (b) By inversion on $\Delta \vdash \phi'_2; \alpha$ we have that $\Delta \vdash \phi'_2$ and $\Delta \vdash \alpha$.
 - (c) By applying the inductive hypothesis to $\Delta \vdash \phi_1$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi'_2$ we have that $\Delta \vdash \phi_1 \sqcup \phi'_2$.
 - (d) And by applying F-3 to $\Delta \vdash \alpha$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi_1 \sqcup \phi'_2$, we have that $\Delta \vdash (\phi_1 \sqcup \phi'_2); \alpha$.
 - (e) This is equivalent to $\Delta \vdash \phi_1 \sqcup \phi'_2; \alpha$ by definition of \sqcup .
 - (f) So we have $\Delta \vdash \phi_1 \sqcup \phi_2$.

Now consider the backwards direction. Assume that $\Delta \vdash \phi_1 \sqcup \phi_2$ and show that $\Delta \vdash \phi_1$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi_2$. Proceed by induction on ϕ_2 .

- (1) Case: \circ
 - (a) Then we have that $\phi_1 \sqcup \circ = \phi_1$ by definition of \sqcup .
 - (b) And so we have that $\Delta \vdash \phi_1$.
 - (c) And we have $\Delta \vdash \circ$, which is the same as $\Delta \vdash \phi_2$, by F-2.
- (2) Case: $\phi'_2; \alpha$
 - (a) Then we have that $\Delta \vdash \phi_1 \sqcup \phi'_2; \alpha$.
 - (b) This is equivalent to $\Delta \vdash (\phi_1 \sqcup \phi'_2); \alpha$ by definition of \sqcup .
 - (c) By inversion on F-3 we have $\Delta \vdash \alpha$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi_1 \sqcup \phi'_2$.
 - (d) By applying the induction hypothesis to $\Delta \vdash \phi_1 \sqcup \phi'_2$ we have that $\Delta \vdash \phi_1$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi'_2$.
 - (e) By applying F-3 to $\Delta \vdash \alpha$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi'_2$ we have that $\Delta \vdash \phi'_2; \alpha$, which is equivalent to $\Delta \vdash \phi_2$.

□

Lemma C.15 (Substitution of ϕ into ϕ preserves well-formedness). *If $\Delta, \alpha \vdash \phi'$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi$ then $\Delta \vdash [\phi/\alpha]\phi'$.*

PROOF. Proceed by induction on ϕ' .

- (1) Case: $\phi' = \circ$
 - (a) Then $[\phi/\alpha]\circ = \circ$.
 - (b) And we have $\Delta \vdash \circ$ by F-2.

- (2) Case: $\phi' = \phi_1; \alpha$
- Then $[\phi/\alpha](\phi_1; \alpha) = [\phi/\alpha]\phi_1 \sqcup \phi$.
 - By inversion on $\Delta, \alpha \vdash \phi'$, we have that $\Delta, \alpha \vdash \phi_1$.
 - We have that $\Delta \vdash [\phi/\alpha]\phi_1$ by applying the inductive hypothesis to $\Delta, \alpha \vdash \phi_1$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi$.
 - We have the result by applying Lemma C.14 to $\Delta \vdash [\phi/\alpha]\phi_1$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi$.
- (3) Case: $\phi' = \phi_1; \alpha_1$ where $\alpha_1 \neq \alpha$
- Then $[\phi/\alpha](\phi_1; \alpha_1) = [\phi/\alpha]\phi_1; \alpha_1$.
 - By inversion on $\Delta, \alpha \vdash \phi'$, we have that $\Delta, \alpha \vdash \phi_1$ and $\Delta, \alpha \vdash \alpha_1$.
 - We have that $\Delta \vdash [\phi/\alpha]\phi_1$ by applying the inductive hypothesis to $\Delta, \alpha \vdash \phi_1$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi$.
 - We have that $\Delta \vdash \alpha_1$ by applying Lemma C.13 to $\Delta, \alpha \vdash \alpha_1$ and $\alpha_1 \neq \alpha$.
 - By applying F-3 to $\Delta \vdash \alpha_1$ and $\Delta \vdash [\phi/\alpha]\phi_1$ we have that $\Delta \vdash [\phi/\alpha]\phi_1; \alpha_1$.

□

Lemma C.16 (Substitution of ϕ into A preserves well-formedness). *If $\Delta, \alpha \vdash A$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi$ then $\Delta \vdash [\phi/\alpha]A$.*

PROOF. We have $\Delta, \alpha \vdash A$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi$. Show that $\Delta \vdash [\phi/\alpha]A$. Proceed by induction on A .

- Case: `unit`
 - Then $[\phi/\alpha]\text{unit} = \text{unit}$.
 - By F-4 we get $\Delta \vdash \text{unit}$.
- Case: $\forall(\alpha'. A_1)$
 - Then $[\phi/\alpha]\forall(\alpha'. A_1) = \forall(\alpha'. [\phi/\alpha]A_1)$.
 - By inversion on $\Delta, \alpha \vdash \forall(\alpha'. A_1)$ we have that $\Delta, \alpha, \alpha' \vdash A_1$.
 - Since $\Delta \vdash \phi$, we can weaken this to $\Delta, \alpha' \vdash \phi$.
 - Since $\Delta, \alpha, \alpha' \vdash A_1$, we can exchange this to $\Delta, \alpha', \alpha \vdash A_1$.
 - By applying the inductive hypothesis to $\Delta, \alpha', \alpha \vdash A_1$ and $\Delta, \alpha' \vdash \phi$, we get that $\Delta, \alpha' \vdash [\phi/\alpha]A_1$.
 - Then by applying F-5 to $\Delta, \alpha' \vdash [\phi/\alpha]A_1$ we have that $\Delta \vdash \forall(\alpha'. [\phi/\alpha]A_1)$.
- Case: $A_1 \rightarrow A_2$
 - Then $[\phi/\alpha](A_1 \rightarrow A_2) = [\phi/\alpha]A_1 \rightarrow [\phi/\alpha]A_2$.
 - By inversion on $\Delta, \alpha \vdash A_1 \rightarrow A_2$ we have that $\Delta, \alpha \vdash A_1$ and $\Delta, \alpha \vdash A_2$.
 - By applying the inductive hypothesis to $\Delta, \alpha \vdash A_1$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi$, we have that $\Delta \vdash [\phi/\alpha]A_1$.
 - By applying the inductive hypothesis to $\Delta, \alpha \vdash A_2$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi$ we have that $\Delta \vdash [\phi/\alpha]A_2$.
 - By F-6 we have that $\Delta \vdash [\phi/\alpha]A_1 \rightarrow [\phi/\alpha]A_2$.
- Case: $A_1 + A_2$
Analogous to the case for $A_1 \rightarrow A_2$.
- Case: $A_1 \otimes A_2$
Analogous to the case for $A_1 \rightarrow A_2$.
- Case: $[A \cdot \phi']$
 - Then $[\phi/\alpha][A \cdot \phi'] = [[\phi/\alpha]A \cdot [\phi/\alpha]\phi']$.
 - By inversion on $\Delta, \alpha \vdash [A \cdot \phi']$ we have that $\Delta, \alpha \vdash A$ and $\Delta, \alpha \vdash \phi'$.
 - By applying the inductive hypothesis to $\Delta, \alpha \vdash A$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi$ we obtain $\Delta \vdash [\phi/\alpha]A$.
 - By applying Lemma C.15 to $\Delta, \alpha \vdash \phi'$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi$ we obtain $\Delta \vdash [\phi/\alpha]\phi'$.
 - By applying F-7 to $\Delta \vdash [\phi/\alpha]A$ and $\Delta \vdash [\phi/\alpha]\phi'$ we obtain $\Delta \vdash [[\phi/\alpha]A \cdot [\phi/\alpha]\phi']$.

□

Lemma C.17. *ϕ substitution preserves \equiv*

If $\phi_1 \equiv \phi_2$ then $[\phi/\alpha]\phi_1 \equiv [\phi/\alpha]\phi_2$.

PROOF. Proceed by induction on $\phi_1 \equiv \phi_2$.

- (1) Case: E-REFL
We have the result immediately, since substitution is deterministic.
- (2) Case: E-SYM
 - (a) We have $\phi_1 \equiv \phi_2$.
 - (b) Show $[\phi/\alpha]\phi_1 \equiv [\phi/\alpha]\phi_2$.
 - (c) We have as a premise that $\phi_2 \equiv \phi_1$.
 - (d) Apply the induction hypothesis to 2c to obtain $[\phi/\alpha]\phi_2 \equiv [\phi/\alpha]\phi_1$.
 - (e) Apply E-SYM to 2d to obtain $[\phi/\alpha]\phi_1 \equiv [\phi/\alpha]\phi_2$.
- (3) Case: E-TRANS
 - (a) We have $\phi_1 \equiv \phi_3$.
 - (b) Show $[\phi/\alpha]\phi_1 \equiv [\phi/\alpha]\phi_3$.
 - (c) We have as premises that $\phi_1 \equiv \phi_2$ and $\phi_2 \equiv \phi_3$.
 - (d) Apply the induction hypothesis to each equality in 3c to obtain $[\phi/\alpha]\phi_1 \equiv [\phi/\alpha]\phi_2$ and $[\phi/\alpha]\phi_2 \equiv [\phi/\alpha]\phi_3$.
 - (e) Apply E-TRANS to each equality in 3d to obtain $[\phi/\alpha]\phi_1 \equiv [\phi/\alpha]\phi_3$.
- (4) Case: E-CONTRACT
 - (a) We have $\phi_1 \equiv \phi_2; \alpha'; \alpha' \sqcup \phi'_2$.
 - (b) Show $[\phi/\alpha]\phi_1 \equiv [\phi/\alpha]\phi_2; \alpha'; \alpha' \sqcup \phi'_2$.
 - (c) We have as a premise that $\phi_1 \equiv \phi_2; \alpha' \sqcup \phi'_2$.
 - (d) Assume that $\alpha' = \alpha$. If not, apply E-CONTRACT to the result of induction to get the goal.
 - (e) Apply the induction hypothesis to obtain $[\phi/\alpha]\phi_1 \equiv [\phi/\alpha]\phi_2 \sqcup \phi \sqcup [\phi/\alpha]\phi'_2$.
 - (f) We have the goal by applying Lemma C.11 to the induction result.
- (5) Case: E-EXCHANGE
 - (a) We have $\phi_1 \equiv \phi_2; \alpha' \sqcup \phi'_2 \sqcup \phi''_2$.
 - (b) Show $[\phi/\alpha]\phi_1 \equiv [\phi/\alpha]\phi_2; \alpha' \sqcup \phi'_2 \sqcup \phi''_2$.
 - (c) We have as a premise that $\phi_1 \equiv \phi_2 \sqcup \phi'_2; \alpha' \sqcup \phi''_2$.
 - (d) Assume that $\alpha' = \alpha$. If not, apply E-EXCHANGE to the result of induction to get the goal.
 - (e) Apply the induction hypothesis to obtain $[\phi/\alpha]\phi_1 \equiv [\phi/\alpha]\phi_2 \sqcup [\phi/\alpha]\phi'_2 \sqcup \phi \sqcup [\phi/\alpha]\phi''_2$.
 - (f) We have the goal by applying Lemma C.12 to the induction result.

□

Lemma C.18. ϕ substitution preserves \sqsubseteq

If $\phi_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta, \alpha} \phi_2$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi$ then $[\phi/\alpha]\phi_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} [\phi/\alpha]\phi_2$.

PROOF. Proceed by induction on $\phi_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta, \alpha} \phi_2$.

- (1) Case: I-REFL
Immediate from Lemma C.17.
- (2) Case: I-WEAKEN
 - (a) We have $\phi_1 \sqcup \phi'_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta, \alpha} \phi_2$.
 - (b) Show that $[\phi/\alpha]\phi_1 \sqcup [\phi/\alpha]\phi'_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} [\phi/\alpha]\phi_2$.
 - (c) We have as premises that $\Delta, \alpha \vdash \alpha'$ and $\phi_1; \alpha' \sqcup \phi'_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta, \alpha} \phi_2$.
 - (d) Assume that $\alpha' = \alpha$. If not, apply I-WEAKEN to $\Delta \vdash \alpha'$ (by Lemma C.13) and the result of induction to get the goal.
 - (e) Apply the induction hypothesis to the inequality premise to obtain $[\phi/\alpha]\phi_1 \sqcup \phi \sqcup [\phi/\alpha]\phi'_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} [\phi/\alpha]\phi_2$.
 - (f) We have the goal by applying Lemma C.10 to $\Delta \vdash \phi$ and the induction result.

□

Lemma C.19. ϕ substitution preserves subtyping

If $A_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta, \alpha} A_2$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi$ then $[\phi/\alpha]A_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} [\phi/\alpha]A_2$.

PROOF. Proceed by induction on subtyping.

(1) Case: S-UNIT

Immediate from $\text{unit} \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \text{unit}$.

(2) Case: S-DEP

(a) We have $[A_1 \cdot \phi_1] \sqsubseteq_{\Delta, \alpha} [A_2 \cdot \phi_2]$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi$.

(b) We have as premises $A_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta, \alpha} A_2$ and $\phi_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta, \alpha} \phi_2$.

(c) Apply the induction hypothesis to the first premise and $\Delta \vdash \phi$ to obtain $[\phi/\alpha]A_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} [\phi/\alpha]A_2$.

(d) Apply Lemma C.18 to the second premise and $\Delta \vdash \phi$ to obtain $[\phi/\alpha]\phi_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} [\phi/\alpha]\phi_2$.

(e) Apply S-DEP to 2c and 2d to obtain $[[\phi/\alpha]A_1 \cdot [\phi/\alpha]\phi_1] \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} [[\phi/\alpha]A_2 \cdot [\phi/\alpha]\phi_2]$.

(3) Case: S-ALL

(a) We have $\forall(\alpha'. A_1) \sqsubseteq_{\Delta, \alpha} \forall(\alpha'. A_2)$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi$.

(b) We have as a premise $A_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta, \alpha, \alpha'} A_2$.

(c) Weaken $\Delta \vdash \phi$ to $\Delta, \alpha' \vdash \phi$.

(d) Apply the induction hypothesis to the premise and $\Delta, \alpha' \vdash \phi$ to obtain $[\phi/\alpha]A_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta, \alpha'} [\phi/\alpha]A_2$.

(e) Apply S-ALL to obtain $\forall(\alpha'. [\phi/\alpha]A_1) \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \forall(\alpha'. [\phi/\alpha]A_2)$.

(4) All other cases

(a) Apply the induction hypothesis to the subtyping premises.

(b) Apply current rule to the results of induction to obtain the goal.

□

Lemma C.20. $\phi_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$ preserves scoping

If $\Delta \vdash \phi_1$ and $\phi_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$ then $\Delta \vdash \phi_2$. If $\Delta \vdash \phi_2$ and $\phi_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$ then $\Delta \vdash \phi_1$.

PROOF. Proceed by induction on $\phi_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$.

Consider the first case.

(1) Case: I-REFL

This property is straightforward for $\phi_1 \equiv \phi_2$, because it only manipulates existing variables.

So we have the result immediately.

(2) Case: I-WEAKEN

(a) We have $\Delta \vdash \phi_1 \sqcup \phi'_1$ and $\phi_1 \sqcup \phi'_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$.

(b) We have as premises $\Delta \vdash \alpha$ and $\phi_1; \alpha \sqcup \phi'_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$.

(c) From $\Delta \vdash \phi_1 \sqcup \phi'_1$ and $\Delta \vdash \alpha$ we have $\Delta \vdash \phi_1; \alpha \sqcup \phi'_1$.

(d) Apply the induction hypothesis to this and the premise inequality to obtain $\Delta \vdash \phi_2$.

Now consider the second case.

(1) Case: I-REFL

This property is straightforward for $\phi_1 \equiv \phi_2$, because it only manipulates existing variables.

So we have the result immediately.

(2) Case: I-WEAKEN

(a) We have $\Delta \vdash \phi_2$ and $\phi_1 \sqcup \phi'_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$.

(b) We have as premises $\Delta \vdash \alpha$ and $\phi_1; \alpha \sqcup \phi'_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$.

(c) Apply the induction hypothesis to $\Delta \vdash \phi_2$ and the premise inequality to obtain $\Delta \vdash \phi_1; \alpha \sqcup \phi'_1$.

□

Lemma C.21. $A_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A_2$ preserves scoping

If $\Delta \vdash A_1$ and $A_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A_2$ then $\Delta \vdash A_2$. If $\Delta \vdash A_2$ and $A_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A_2$ then $\Delta \vdash A_1$.

PROOF. Proceed by induction on $A_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A_2$.

Consider the first case.

- (1) Case: S-UNIT
We have $\Delta \vdash \text{unit}$ by F-4.
- (2) Case: S-SUM
 - (a) We have $\Delta \vdash A_1 + A_2$ and $A_1 + A_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A'_1 + A'_2$.
 - (b) We have as premises $A_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A'_1$ and $A_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A'_2$.
 - (c) By inversion on $\Delta \vdash A_1 + A_2$ we have $\Delta \vdash A_1$ and $\Delta \vdash A_2$.
 - (d) Apply the induction hypothesis to $\Delta \vdash A_1$ and $A_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A'_1$ to obtain $\Delta \vdash A'_1$.
 - (e) Analogously obtain $\Delta \vdash A'_2$.
 - (f) Apply F-8 to $\Delta \vdash A'_1$ and $\Delta \vdash A'_2$ to obtain $\Delta \vdash A'_1 + A'_2$.
- (3) Case: S-PROD
Analogous to the case for S-SUM.
- (4) Case: S-DEP
 - (a) We have $\Delta \vdash [A_1 \cdot \phi_1]$ and $[A_1 \cdot \phi_1] \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} [A_2 \cdot \phi_2]$.
 - (b) We have as premises $A_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A_2$ and $\phi_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$.
 - (c) By inversion on $\Delta \vdash [A_1 \cdot \phi_1]$ we have $\Delta \vdash A_1$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi_1$, by F-7.
 - (d) Apply the induction hypothesis to $\Delta \vdash A_1$ and $A_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A_2$ to obtain $\Delta \vdash A_2$.
 - (e) Apply Lemma C.20 to $\Delta \vdash \phi_1$ and $\phi_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$ to obtain $\Delta \vdash \phi_2$.
 - (f) Apply F-7 to $\Delta \vdash A_2$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi_2$ to obtain $\Delta \vdash [A_2 \cdot \phi_2]$.
- (5) Case: S-ARROW
 - (a) We have $\Delta \vdash A_1 \rightarrow A_2$ and $A_1 \rightarrow A_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A'_1 \rightarrow A'_2$.
 - (b) We have as premises $A'_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A_1$ and $A_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A'_2$.
 - (c) By inversion on $\Delta \vdash A_1 \rightarrow A_2$ we have $\Delta \vdash A_1$ and $\Delta \vdash A_2$.
 - (d) Apply the induction hypothesis to $\Delta \vdash A_2$ and $A_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A'_2$ to obtain $\Delta \vdash A'_2$.
 - (e) Apply the induction hypothesis for the second case to $\Delta \vdash A_1$ and $A'_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A_1$ to obtain $\Delta \vdash A'_1$.
 - (f) Apply F-6 to $\Delta \vdash A'_2$ and $\Delta \vdash A'_1$ to obtain $\Delta \vdash A'_1 \rightarrow A'_2$.
- (6) Case: S-ALL
 - (a) We have $\Delta \vdash \forall(\alpha.A_1)$ and $\forall(\alpha.A_1) \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \forall(\alpha.A_2)$.
 - (b) We have as a premise $A_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta, \alpha} A_2$.
 - (c) By inversion on $\Delta \vdash \forall(\alpha.A_1)$ we have $\Delta, \alpha \vdash A_1$.
 - (d) Apply the induction hypothesis to this and the inequality premise to obtain $\Delta, \alpha \vdash A_2$.
 - (e) Apply F-5 to this to obtain $\Delta \vdash \forall(\alpha.A_2)$.

Now consider the second case.

- (1) Case: S-UNIT
We have $\Delta \vdash \text{unit}$ by F-4.
- (2) Case: S-SUM
 - (a) We have $\Delta \vdash A'_1 + A'_2$ and $A_1 + A_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A'_1 + A'_2$.
 - (b) We have as premises $A_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A'_1$ and $A_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A'_2$.
 - (c) By inversion on $\Delta \vdash A'_1 + A'_2$ we have $\Delta \vdash A'_1$ and $\Delta \vdash A'_2$.
 - (d) Apply the induction hypothesis to $\Delta \vdash A'_1$ and $A_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A'_1$ to obtain $\Delta \vdash A_1$.
 - (e) Analogously obtain $\Delta \vdash A_2$.
 - (f) Apply F-8 to $\Delta \vdash A_1$ and $\Delta \vdash A_2$ to obtain $\Delta \vdash A_1 + A_2$.
- (3) Case: S-PROD
Analogous to the case for S-SUM.
- (4) Case: S-DEP
 - (a) We have $\Delta \vdash [A_2 \cdot \phi_2]$ and $[A_1 \cdot \phi_1] \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} [A_2 \cdot \phi_2]$.
 - (b) We have as premises $A_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A_2$ and $\phi_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$.

- (c) By inversion on $\Delta \vdash [A_2 \cdot \phi_2]$ we have $\Delta \vdash A_2$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi_2$, by F-7.
- (d) Apply the induction hypothesis to $\Delta \vdash A_2$ and $A_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A_2$ to obtain $\Delta \vdash A_1$.
- (e) Apply Lemma C.20 to $\Delta \vdash \phi_2$ and $\phi_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$ to obtain $\Delta \vdash \phi_1$.
- (f) Apply F-7 to $\Delta \vdash A_1$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi_1$ to obtain $\Delta \vdash [A_1 \cdot \phi_1]$.
- (5) Case: S-ARROW
 - (a) We have $\Delta \vdash A'_1 \rightarrow A'_2$ and $A_1 \rightarrow A_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A'_1 \rightarrow A'_2$.
 - (b) We have as premises $A'_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A_1$ and $A_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A'_2$.
 - (c) By inversion on $\Delta \vdash A'_1 \rightarrow A'_2$ we have $\Delta \vdash A'_1$ and $\Delta \vdash A'_2$.
 - (d) Apply the induction hypothesis to $\Delta \vdash A'_2$ and $A_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A'_2$ to obtain $\Delta \vdash A_2$.
 - (e) Apply the induction hypothesis for the first case to $\Delta \vdash A'_1$ and $A'_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A_1$ to obtain $\Delta \vdash A_1$.
 - (f) Apply F-6 to $\Delta \vdash A_1$ and $\Delta \vdash A_2$ to obtain $\Delta \vdash A_1 \rightarrow A_2$.
- (6) Case: S-ALL
 - (a) We have $\Delta \vdash \forall(\alpha.A_2)$ and $\forall(\alpha.A_1) \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \forall(\alpha.A_2)$.
 - (b) We have as a premise $A_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta, \alpha} A_2$.
 - (c) By inversion on $\Delta \vdash \forall(\alpha.A_2)$ we have $\Delta, \alpha \vdash A_2$.
 - (d) Apply the induction hypothesis to this and the inequality premise to obtain $\Delta, \alpha \vdash A_1$.
 - (e) Apply F-5 to this to obtain $\Delta \vdash \forall(\alpha.A_1)$.

□

Theorem C.22 (Regularity). *If $\Delta; \Gamma \vdash e : A \mid \phi$ and $\Delta \vdash A_i$ for each assumption $x_i : A_i$ in Γ , then $\Delta \vdash e$ and $\Delta \vdash A$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi$ and $\Gamma \vdash e$.*

PROOF. Proceed by induction on typing. We will not mention the second assumption except where Γ is used or changed.

- (1) Case: T-SUB
 - (a) We have $\Delta; \Gamma \vdash e : A_2 \mid \phi$.
 - (b) Want to show $\Delta \vdash e$ and $\Delta \vdash A_2$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi$ and $\Gamma \vdash e$.
 - (c) We have as premises $\Delta; \Gamma \vdash e : A_1 \mid \phi$ and $A_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A_2$.
 - (d) Apply the induction hypothesis to the typing premise to obtain $\Delta \vdash e$ and $\Delta \vdash A_1$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi$ and $\Gamma \vdash e$.
 - (e) Apply Lemma C.21 to $\Delta \vdash A_1$ and $A_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A_2$ to get $\Delta \vdash A_2$.
- (2) Case: T-UNIT
 - (a) We have $\Delta; \Gamma \vdash \langle \rangle : \text{unit} \mid \circ$.
 - (b) Show $\Delta \vdash \langle \rangle$ and $\Delta \vdash \text{unit}$ and $\Gamma \vdash \langle \rangle$.
 - (c) We have the former by F-10, the next by F-4, and the last by F-23.
- (3) Case: T-VAR
 - (a) We have $\Delta; \Gamma, x : A \vdash x : A \mid \circ$.
 - (b) Show $\Delta \vdash x$ and $\Delta \vdash A$ and $\Gamma \vdash x$.
 - (c) We have $\Delta \vdash x$ by F-11.
 - (d) We have $\Delta \vdash A$ by instantiating our second assumption with $x : A \in \Gamma$.
 - (e) We have $\Gamma \vdash x$ by applying F-24 to $x \in \Gamma$.
- (4) Case: T-CONSUME
 - (a) We have $\Delta; \Gamma \vdash \#e : [A \cdot \phi] \mid \circ$.
 - (b) Show $\Delta \vdash \#e$ and $\Delta \vdash [A \cdot \phi]$ and $\Gamma \vdash \#e$.
 - (c) We have as a premise $\Delta; \Gamma \vdash e : A \mid \phi$.
 - (d) Apply the inductive hypothesis to this premise to obtain $\Delta \vdash e$ and $\Delta \vdash A$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi$ and $\Gamma \vdash e$.
 - (e) Apply F-12 to $\Delta \vdash e$ to obtain $\Delta \vdash \#e$.

- (f) Apply F-7 to $\Delta \vdash A$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi$ to obtain $\Delta \vdash [A \cdot \phi]$.
- (g) Apply F-25 to $\Gamma \vdash e$ to obtain $\Gamma \vdash \#e$.
- (5) Case: T-PRODUCE
- (a) We have $\Delta; \Gamma \vdash !e : A \mid \phi_1 \sqcup \phi_2$.
- (b) Show $\Delta \vdash !e$ and $\Delta \vdash A$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi_1 \sqcup \phi_2$ and $\Gamma \vdash !e$.
- (c) We have as a premise $\Delta; \Gamma \vdash e : [A \cdot \phi_1] \mid \phi_2$.
- (d) Apply the induction hypothesis to this premise to obtain $\Delta \vdash e$ and $\Delta \vdash [A \cdot \phi_1]$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi_2$ and $\Gamma \vdash e$.
- (e) Apply F-13 to $\Delta \vdash e$ to obtain $\Delta \vdash !e$.
- (f) By inversion on $\Delta \vdash [A \cdot \phi_1]$ we have $\Delta \vdash A$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi_1$.
- (g) Apply Lemma C.14 to $\Delta \vdash \phi_1$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi_2$ to get $\Delta \vdash \phi_1 \sqcup \phi_2$.
- (h) Apply F-26 to $\Gamma \vdash e$ to obtain $\Gamma \vdash !e$.
- (6) Case: T-INJL
- (a) We have $\Delta; \Gamma \vdash l \cdot e : A_1 + A_2 \mid \phi$.
- (b) Show $\Delta \vdash l \cdot e$ and $\Delta \vdash A_1 + A_2$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi$ and $\Gamma \vdash l \cdot e$.
- (c) We have as premises $\Delta; \Gamma \vdash e : A_1 \mid \phi$ and $\Delta \vdash A_2$.
- (d) Apply the induction hypothesis to the premise to obtain $\Delta \vdash e$ and $\Delta \vdash A_1$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi$ and $\Gamma \vdash e$.
- (e) Apply F-14 to $\Delta \vdash e$ to obtain $\Delta \vdash l \cdot e$.
- (f) Apply F-8 to $\Delta \vdash A_1$ and $\Delta \vdash A_2$ to obtain $\Delta \vdash A_1 + A_2$.
- (g) Apply F-27 to $\Gamma \vdash e$ to obtain $\Gamma \vdash l \cdot e$.
- (7) Case: T-INJR
- Analogous to the case for T-INJL.
- (8) Case: T-CASE
- (a) We have $\Delta; \Gamma \vdash \text{case } e \{ l \cdot x_1 \hookrightarrow e_1 \mid r \cdot x_2 \hookrightarrow e_2 \} : A \mid \phi \sqcup \phi'$.
- (b) Show $\Delta \vdash \text{case } e \{ l \cdot x_1 \hookrightarrow e_1 \mid r \cdot x_2 \hookrightarrow e_2 \}$ and $\Delta \vdash A$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi \sqcup \phi'$ and $\Gamma \vdash \text{case } e \{ l \cdot x_1 \hookrightarrow e_1 \mid r \cdot x_2 \hookrightarrow e_2 \}$.
- (c) We have as premises
- (i) $\Delta; \Gamma \vdash e : A_1 + A_2 \mid \phi$
 - (ii) $\Delta; \Gamma, x_1 : A_1 \vdash e_1 : A \mid \phi'$
 - (iii) $\Delta; \Gamma, x_2 : A_2 \vdash e_2 : A \mid \phi'$
- (d) Apply the induction hypothesis to the first premise to obtain $\Delta \vdash e$ and $\Delta \vdash A_1 + A_2$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi$ and $\Gamma \vdash e$.
- (e) By inversion on $\Delta \vdash A_1 + A_2$ we have $\Delta \vdash A_1$ and $\Delta \vdash A_2$.
- (f) Apply the induction hypothesis to the second two premises and $\Delta \vdash A_1$, $\Delta \vdash A_2$ respectively to obtain:
- (i) $\Delta \vdash e_1$, $\Delta \vdash A$, $\Delta \vdash \phi'$, $\Gamma, x_1 \vdash e_1$
 - (ii) $\Delta \vdash e_2$, $\Delta \vdash A$, $\Delta \vdash \phi'$, $\Gamma, x_2 \vdash e_2$
- (g) Apply F-16 to $\Delta \vdash e$ and $\Delta \vdash e_1$ and $\Delta \vdash e_2$ to obtain $\Delta \vdash \text{case } e \{ l \cdot x_1 \hookrightarrow e_1 \mid r \cdot x_2 \hookrightarrow e_2 \}$.
- (h) Apply Lemma C.14 to $\Delta \vdash \phi$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi'$ to get $\Delta \vdash \phi \sqcup \phi'$.
- (i) Apply F-29 to $\Gamma \vdash e$ and $\Gamma, x_1 \vdash e_1$ and $\Gamma, x_2 \vdash e_2$ to obtain $\Gamma \vdash \text{case } e \{ l \cdot x_1 \hookrightarrow e_1 \mid r \cdot x_2 \hookrightarrow e_2 \}$.
- (9) Case: T-PAIR
- (a) We have $\Delta; \Gamma \vdash \langle e_1, e_2 \rangle : A_1 \otimes A_2 \mid \phi_1 \sqcup \phi_2$
- (b) Show $\Delta \vdash \langle e_1, e_2 \rangle$ and $\Delta \vdash A_1 \otimes A_2$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi_1 \sqcup \phi_2$ and $\Gamma \vdash \langle e_1, e_2 \rangle$.
- (c) We have as premises $\Delta; \Gamma \vdash e_1 : A_1 \mid \phi_1$ and $\Delta; \Gamma \vdash e_2 : A_2 \mid \phi_2$.
- (d) Apply the induction hypothesis to each premise to obtain $\Delta \vdash e_1, e_2$ and $\Delta \vdash A_1, A_2$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi_1, \phi_2$ and $\Gamma \vdash e_1, e_2$.
- (e) Apply F-17 to $\Delta \vdash e_1, e_2$ to obtain $\Delta \vdash \langle e_1, e_2 \rangle$.

- (f) Apply F-9 to $\Delta \vdash A_1, A_2$ to obtain $\Delta \vdash A_1 \otimes A_2$.
 - (g) Apply Lemma C.14 to $\Delta \vdash \phi_1, \phi_2$ to get $\Delta \vdash \phi_1 \sqcup \phi_2$.
 - (h) Apply F-30 to $\Gamma \vdash e_1$ and $\Gamma \vdash e_2$ to obtain $\Gamma \vdash \langle e_1, e_2 \rangle$.
- (10) Case: T-SPLIT
- (a) We have $\Delta; \Gamma \vdash \text{split } e$ into $\langle x_1, x_2 \rangle$ in $e_1 : A \mid \phi \sqcup \phi'$.
 - (b) Show $\Delta \vdash \text{split } e$ into $\langle x_1, x_2 \rangle$ in e_1 and $\Delta \vdash A$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi \sqcup \phi'$ and $\Gamma \vdash \text{split } e$ into $\langle x_1, x_2 \rangle$ in e_1 .
 - (c) We have as premises:
 - (i) $\Delta; \Gamma \vdash e : A_1 \otimes A_2 \mid \phi$
 - (ii) $\Delta; \Gamma, x_1 : A_1, x_2 : A_2 \vdash e_1 : A \mid \phi'$
 - (d) Apply the induction hypothesis to the first to obtain $\Delta \vdash e$ and $\Delta \vdash A_1 \otimes A_2$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi$ and $\Gamma \vdash e$.
 - (e) By inversion on $\Delta \vdash A_1 \otimes A_2$ we have $\Delta \vdash A_1$ and $\Delta \vdash A_2$.
 - (f) Apply the induction hypothesis to the second premise and $\Delta \vdash A_1, \Delta \vdash A_2$ to obtain $\Delta \vdash e_1$ and $\Delta \vdash A$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi'$ and $\Gamma, x_1, x_2 \vdash e_1$.
 - (g) Apply F-18 to $\Delta \vdash e$ and $\Delta \vdash e_1$ to obtain $\Delta \vdash \text{split } e$ into $\langle x_1, x_2 \rangle$ in e_1 .
 - (h) Apply Lemma C.14 to $\Delta \vdash \phi$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi'$ to get $\Delta \vdash \phi \sqcup \phi'$.
 - (i) Apply F-31 to $\Gamma \vdash e$ and $\Gamma, x_1, x_2 \vdash e_1$ to obtain $\Gamma \vdash \text{split } e$ into $\langle x_1, x_2 \rangle$ in e_1 .
- (11) Case: T-LAM
- (a) We have $\Delta; \Gamma \vdash \lambda(x.e) : A_1 \rightarrow A_2 \mid \circ$.
 - (b) Show $\Delta \vdash \lambda(x.e)$ and $\Delta \vdash A_1 \rightarrow A_2$ and $\Gamma \vdash \lambda(x.e)$.
 - (c) We have as premises $\Delta; \Gamma, x : A_1 \vdash e : A_2 \mid \circ$ and $\Delta \vdash A_1$.
 - (d) Apply the induction hypothesis to the typing premise and $\Delta \vdash A_1$ to obtain $\Delta \vdash e$ and $\Delta \vdash A_2$ and $\Gamma, x \vdash e$.
 - (e) Apply F-19 to $\Delta \vdash e$ to obtain $\Delta \vdash \lambda(x.e)$.
 - (f) Apply F-6 to $\Delta \vdash A_1$ and $\Delta \vdash A_2$ to obtain $\Delta \vdash A_1 \rightarrow A_2$.
 - (g) Apply F-32 to $\Gamma, x \vdash e$ to obtain $\Gamma \vdash \lambda(x.e)$.
- (12) Case: T-AP
- (a) We have $\Delta; \Gamma \vdash \text{ap}(e; e_1) : A_2 \mid \phi \sqcup \phi_1$.
 - (b) Show $\Delta \vdash \text{ap}(e; e_1)$ and $\Delta \vdash A_2$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi \sqcup \phi_1$ and $\Gamma \vdash \text{ap}(e; e_1)$.
 - (c) We have as premises that $\Delta; \Gamma \vdash e : A_1 \rightarrow A_2 \mid \phi$ and $\Delta; \Gamma \vdash e_1 : A_1 \mid \phi_1$.
 - (d) Apply the induction hypothesis to both to obtain $\Delta \vdash e, e_1$ and $\Delta \vdash A_1 \rightarrow A_2$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi, \phi_1$ and $\Gamma \vdash e, e_1$.
 - (e) Apply F-20 to $\Delta \vdash e, e_1$ to obtain $\Delta \vdash \text{ap}(e; e_1)$.
 - (f) By inversion on $\Delta \vdash A_1 \rightarrow A_2$ we have $\Delta \vdash A_2$.
 - (g) Apply Lemma C.14 to $\Delta \vdash \phi, \phi_1$ to get $\Delta \vdash \phi \sqcup \phi_1$.
 - (h) Apply F-33 to $\Gamma \vdash e, e_1$ to obtain $\Gamma \vdash \text{ap}(e; e_1)$.
- (13) Case: T-DEPLAM
- (a) We have $\Delta; \Gamma \vdash \Lambda(\alpha.e) : \forall(\alpha.A) \mid \circ$.
 - (b) Show $\Delta \vdash \Lambda(\alpha.e)$ and $\Delta \vdash \forall(\alpha.A)$ and $\Gamma \vdash \Lambda(\alpha.e)$.
 - (c) We have as a premise that $\Delta, \alpha; \Gamma \vdash e : A \mid \circ$.
 - (d) Apply the induction hypothesis to this to obtain $\Delta, \alpha \vdash e$ and $\Delta, \alpha \vdash A$ and $\Gamma \vdash e$.
 - (e) Apply F-21 to $\Delta, \alpha \vdash e$ to obtain $\Delta \vdash \Lambda(\alpha.e)$.
 - (f) Apply F-5 to $\Delta, \alpha \vdash A$ to obtain $\Delta \vdash \forall(\alpha.A)$.
 - (g) Apply F-34 to $\Gamma \vdash e$ to obtain $\Gamma \vdash \Lambda(\alpha.e)$.
- (14) Case: T-DEPAP
- (a) We have $\Delta; \Gamma \vdash e[\phi] : [\phi/\alpha]A \mid \phi'$.
 - (b) Show $\Delta \vdash e[\phi]$ and $\Delta \vdash [\phi/\alpha]A$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi'$ and $\Gamma \vdash e[\phi]$.
 - (c) We have as a premise that $\Delta; \Gamma \vdash e : \forall(\alpha.A) \mid \phi'$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi$.

- (d) Apply the induction hypothesis to the typing premise to obtain $\Delta \vdash e$ and $\Delta \vdash \forall(\alpha.A)$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi'$ and $\Gamma \vdash e$.
- (e) Apply F-22 to $\Delta \vdash e$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi$ to obtain $\Delta \vdash e[\phi]$.
- (f) By inversion on $\Delta \vdash \forall(\alpha.A)$ we have $\Delta, \alpha \vdash A$.
- (g) Apply Lemma C.16 to $\Delta, \alpha \vdash A$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi$ to obtain $\Delta \vdash [\phi/\alpha]A$.
- (h) Apply F-35 to $\Gamma \vdash e$ to obtain $\Gamma \vdash e[\phi]$.

□

Lemma C.23 (Deterministic Evaluation). *If $e \mapsto e'$, there is at most one such e' .*

PROOF. Proceed by cases on e .

- (1) Case: $\langle \rangle$
This is a value, so this case is vacuous.
- (2) Case: x
This cannot appear on the left hand side of an evaluation, so this case is vacuous.
- (3) Case: $\#e$
This is a value, so this case is vacuous.
- (4) Case: $!e$
Then if e is a value, the only option is E-PRODUCE- β . If it is not, the only option is E-PRODUCE-CONG.
- (5) Case: $l \cdot e$
If e is a value, then this case is vacuous. If it is not, the only option is E-INJL-CONG.
- (6) Case: $r \cdot e$
If e is a value, then this case is vacuous. If it is not, the only option is E-INJR-CONG.
- (7) Case: $\text{case } e \{ l \cdot x_1 \hookrightarrow e_1 \mid r \cdot x_2 \hookrightarrow e_2 \}$
Case on whether e val.
 - (a) Case: Value
Case on e .
 - (i) $l \cdot e_l$
Then E-CASE- $\beta 1$ is the only applicable rule.
 - (ii) $r \cdot e_r$
Then E-CASE- $\beta 2$ is the only applicable rule.
 - (iii) Other
Then there are no applicable rules.
 - (b) Case: Non-value
Then E-CASE-CONG is the only applicable rule.
- (8) Case: $\langle e_1, e_2 \rangle$
If e_1 is not a value, the only option is E-PAIR-CONG1. If it is, the only option is E-PAIR-CONG2.
- (9) Case: $\text{split } e$ into $\langle x_1, x_2 \rangle$ in e'
Case on whether e val.
 - (a) Case: Value
Case on e .
 - (i) $\langle e_1, e_2 \rangle$
Then the only option is E-SPLIT-CONG.
 - (ii) Other
Then there are no applicable rules.
 - (b) Case: Non-value
Then the only option is E-SPLIT- β .

- (10) Case: $\lambda(x.e_1)$
This is a value, so this case is vacuous.
- (11) Case: $\text{ap}(e_1; e_2)$
Case on whether e_1 val.
 - (a) Case: Value
Then if e_2 val the only option is E-AP- β . If e_2 is not a value, the only option is E-AP-CONG2
 - (b) Case: Non-value
Then the only option is E-AP-CONG1.
- (12) Case: $\Lambda(\alpha.e_1)$
This is a value, so this case is vacuous.
- (13) Case: $e_1[\phi_1]$
Case on whether e_1 val.
 - (a) Case: Value
Then the only option is E-DEPAP- β .
 - (b) Case: Non-value
Then the only option is E-DEPAP-CONG.

□

Note that while the logical relation requires well-scopedness for its type, security level, and observer level, we do not generally mention this explicitly. Proofs involving the logical relation note the preservation of this invariant only if it is not apparent.

Lemma C.24 (Head Expansion). *If $e \sim^* e' \in A \mid \phi_1[\phi_2][\Delta]$ and $e_1 \mapsto^* e$ then $e_1 \sim^* e' \in A \mid \phi_1[\phi_2][\Delta]$.*

PROOF. Proceed directly.

- (1) If $\phi_1 \not\sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$ then we have the result immediately.
- (2) Otherwise, we have e_2 val, e'_2 val, $e \mapsto^* e_2$, $e' \mapsto^* e'_2$.
- (3) We know transitively that $e_1 \mapsto^* e \mapsto^* e_2$.
- (4) So we have the result by replacing the first evaluation in 2 with 3.

□

Lemma C.25 (Head Reduction). *If $e \sim^* e' \in A \mid \phi_1[\phi_2][\Delta]$ and $e \mapsto^* e_1$ then $e_1 \sim^* e' \in A \mid \phi_1[\phi_2][\Delta]$.*

PROOF. Proceed directly.

- (1) If $\phi_1 \not\sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$ then we have the result immediately.
- (2) Otherwise, we have e_2 val, e'_2 val, $e \mapsto^* e_2$, $e' \mapsto^* e'_2$.
- (3) We know that $e \mapsto^* e_1 \mapsto^* e_2$ by Lemma C.23.
- (4) So we have $e_1 \mapsto^* e_2$.
- (5) So we have the result by replacing the first evaluation in 2 with 4.

□

Lemma C.26 (Monotonicity). *If $e \sim^* e' \in A \mid \phi_1[\phi_2][\Delta]$ and $\phi_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'_1$ then $e \sim^* e' \in A \mid \phi'_1[\phi_2][\Delta]$.*

PROOF. Proceed by induction on the height of A .

- (1) Case: Non-interference
 - (a) Consider the first case.
 - (b) We have $\phi_1 \not\sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$.
 - (c) Show $\phi'_1 \not\sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$.
 - (d) Apply Lemma C.8 to 1b and $\phi_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'_1$ to obtain $\phi'_1 \not\sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$.

- (e) For the second case, we have $e \mapsto^* e_1$, $e_1 \text{ val}$ and $e' \mapsto^* e'_1$, $e'_1 \text{ val}$ and $e_1 \sim e'_1 \in A \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$.
Case on A .
- (2) Subcase: `unit`
We have $\langle \rangle \sim \langle \rangle \in \text{unit} \mid \phi'_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$ immediately.
- (3) Subcase: $A_1 + A_2$
(a) We have $e \sim e' \in A_1 + A_2 \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$ and $\phi_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'_1$.
(b) Show $e \sim e' \in A_1 + A_2 \mid \phi'_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$.
(c) By the equality in 3a we have either:
(i) $e = 1 \cdot e_1$, $e' = 1 \cdot e'_1$, $e_1 \sim^* e'_1 \in A_1 \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$
(ii) $e = r \cdot e_1$, $e' = r \cdot e'_1$, $e_1 \sim^* e'_1 \in A_2 \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$
(d) Consider the first case without loss of generality.
(e) Apply the induction hypothesis to $e_1 \sim^* e'_1 \in A_1 \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$ and $\phi_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'_1$ to obtain $e_1 \sim^* e'_1 \in A_1 \mid \phi'_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$.
(f) Apply the definition of equality at $A_1 + A_2$ to 3c, replacing the equality in 3(c)i with 3e, to obtain $e \sim e' \in A_1 + A_2 \mid \phi'_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$.
- (4) Subcase: $A_1 \otimes A_2$
(a) We have $e \sim e' \in A_1 \otimes A_2 \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$ and $\phi_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'_1$.
(b) Show $e \sim e' \in A_1 \otimes A_2 \mid \phi'_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$.
(c) By the equality in 4a we have:
(i) $e = \langle e_1, e_2 \rangle$, $e' = \langle e'_1, e'_2 \rangle$
(ii) $e_1 \sim^* e'_1 \in A_1 \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$
(iii) $e_2 \sim^* e'_2 \in A_2 \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$
(d) Apply the induction hypothesis to 4(c)ii and $\phi_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'_1$ to obtain $e_1 \sim^* e'_1 \in A_1 \mid \phi'_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$.
(e) Apply the induction hypothesis to 4(c)iii and $\phi_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'_1$ to obtain $e_2 \sim^* e'_2 \in A_2 \mid \phi'_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$.
(f) Apply the definition of equality at $A_1 \otimes A_2$ to 4c, replacing 4(c)ii and 4(c)iii with 4d and 4e, to obtain $e \sim e' \in A_1 \otimes A_2 \mid \phi'_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$.
- (5) Subcase: $[A \cdot \phi]$
(a) We have $e \sim e' \in [A \cdot \phi] \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$ and $\phi_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'_1$.
(b) Show that $e \sim e' \in [A \cdot \phi] \mid \phi'_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$.
(c) Suffices to show $!e \sim^* !e' \in A \mid \phi \sqcup \phi'_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$.
(d) From the equality assumption we have $!e \sim^* !e' \in A \mid \phi \sqcup \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$
(e) By Lemma C.6 on $\phi_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'_1$ we have that $\phi \sqcup \phi_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi \sqcup \phi'_1$.
(f) Apply the induction hypothesis to the equality in 5d and 5e to obtain $!e \sim^* !e' \in A \mid \phi \sqcup \phi'_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$.
- (6) Subcase: $A_1 \rightarrow A_2$
(a) We have that $e \sim e' \in A_1 \rightarrow A_2 \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$ and $\phi_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'_1$.
(b) Show that $e \sim e' \in A_1 \rightarrow A_2 \mid \phi'_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$.
(c) Assume some $\phi'_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi'_1$ and $e_1 \text{ val}$, $e'_1 \text{ val}$ and $e_1 \sim^* e'_1 \in A_1 \mid \phi'_1 [\phi'_2] [\Delta]$.
(d) Suffices to show $\text{ap}(e; e_1) \sim^* \text{ap}(e'; e'_1) \in A_2 \mid \phi''_1 \sqcup \phi'_1 [\phi'_2] [\Delta]$.
(e) We have by applying our initial equality assumption to 6c that $\text{ap}(e; e_1) \sim^* \text{ap}(e'; e'_1) \in A_2 \mid \phi'_1 \sqcup \phi_1 [\phi'_2] [\Delta]$.
(f) By Lemma C.6 on $\phi_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'_1$ we have $\phi'_1 \sqcup \phi_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'_1 \sqcup \phi'_1$.
(g) Apply the induction hypothesis to 6e and 6f to obtain $\text{ap}(e; e_1) \sim^* \text{ap}(e'; e'_1) \in A_2 \mid \phi''_1 \sqcup \phi'_1 [\phi'_2] [\Delta]$.
- (7) Subcase: $\forall(\alpha.A)$
(a) We have that $e \sim e' \in \forall(\alpha.A) \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$ and $\phi_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'_1$.
(b) Show that $e \sim e' \in \forall(\alpha.A) \mid \phi'_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$.

- (c) Assume some $\Delta \vdash \phi$.
- (d) Suffices to show $e[\phi] \sim e'[\phi] \in [\phi/\alpha]A \mid \phi'_1[\phi_2][\Delta]$.
- (e) We have by applying 7c to our equality assumption that $e[\phi] \sim e'[\phi] \in [\phi/\alpha]A \mid \phi_1[\phi_2][\Delta]$.
- (f) Apply the induction hypothesis to 7e and $\phi_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'_1$ to obtain $e[\phi] \sim e'[\phi] \in [\phi/\alpha]A \mid \phi'_1[\phi_2][\Delta]$. \square

Corollary C.27 (Security Level Increase). *If $e_1 \sim e_2 \in A \mid \phi[\phi'][\Delta]$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi_1$ then $e_1 \sim e_2 \in A \mid \phi \sqcup \phi_1[\phi'][\Delta]$.*

PROOF. Proceed directly.

- (1) We have $\phi \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi \sqcup \phi_1$ by repeatedly weakening elements of ϕ_1 onto ϕ .
- (2) Apply Lemma C.26 to $e_1 \sim e_2 \in A \mid \phi[\phi'][\Delta]$ and 1 to obtain $e_1 \sim e_2 \in A \mid \phi \sqcup \phi_1[\phi'][\Delta]$. \square

Lemma C.28 (Type Monotonicity). *If $e \sim e' \in A \mid \phi_1[\phi_2][\Delta]$ and $A \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A'$ then $e \sim e' \in A' \mid \phi_1[\phi_2][\Delta]$.*

PROOF. Proceed by induction on the height of A .

- (1) Case: Non-interference
 - (a) Consider the first case.
 - (b) We have $\phi_1 \not\sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$ from the assumption.
 - (c) For the second case, we have $e \mapsto^* e_1$, $e_1 \text{ val}$ and $e' \mapsto^* e'_1$, $e'_1 \text{ val}$ and $e_1 \sim e'_1 \in A \mid \phi_1[\phi_2][\Delta]$.
Case on A .
- (2) Subcase: unit
 - We have $\langle \rangle \sim \langle \rangle \in \text{unit} \mid \phi_1[\phi_2][\Delta]$ immediately.
- (3) Subcase: $A_1 + A_2$
 - (a) We have $e \sim e' \in A_1 + A_2 \mid \phi_1[\phi_2][\Delta]$ and $A_1 + A_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A'$.
 - (b) Show $e \sim e' \in A' \mid \phi_1[\phi_2][\Delta]$.
 - (c) By inversion on $A_1 + A_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A'$ we have $A' = A'_1 + A'_2$ and $A_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A'_1$ and $A_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A'_2$.
 - (d) Suffices to show $e \sim e' \in A'_1 + A'_2 \mid \phi_1[\phi_2][\Delta]$.
 - (e) By the equality in 3a we have either:
 - (i) $e = 1 \cdot e_1$, $e' = 1 \cdot e'_1$, $e_1 \sim e'_1 \in A_1 \mid \phi_1[\phi_2][\Delta]$
 - (ii) $e = r \cdot e_1$, $e' = r \cdot e'_1$, $e_1 \sim e'_1 \in A_2 \mid \phi_1[\phi_2][\Delta]$
 - (f) Consider the first case without loss of generality.
 - (g) Apply the induction hypothesis to the equality from 3(e)i and $A_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A'_1$ to obtain $e_1 \sim e_2 \in A'_1 \mid \phi_1[\phi_2][\Delta]$.
 - (h) Apply the definition of equality at $A_1 + A_2$ to 3e, replacing the equality in 3(e)i with 3g, to obtain $e \sim e' \in A'_1 + A'_2 \mid \phi_1[\phi_2][\Delta]$.
- (4) Subcase: $A_1 \otimes A_2$
 - (a) We have $e \sim e' \in A_1 \otimes A_2 \mid \phi_1[\phi_2][\Delta]$ and $A_1 \otimes A_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A'$.
 - (b) Show $e \sim e' \in A' \mid \phi_1[\phi_2][\Delta]$.
 - (c) By inversion on $A_1 \otimes A_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A'$ we have $A' = A'_1 \otimes A'_2$ and $A_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A'_1$ and $A_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A'_2$.
 - (d) Suffices to show $e \sim e' \in A'_1 \otimes A'_2 \mid \phi_1[\phi_2][\Delta]$.
 - (e) By the equality in 4a we have:
 - (i) $e = \langle e_1, e_2 \rangle$
 - (ii) $e' = \langle e'_1, e'_2 \rangle$
 - (iii) $e_1 \sim e'_1 \in A_1 \mid \phi_1[\phi_2][\Delta]$
 - (iv) $e_2 \sim e'_2 \in A_2 \mid \phi_1[\phi_2][\Delta]$

- (f) Apply the induction hypothesis to 4(e)iii and $A_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A'_1$ to obtain $e_1 \overset{*}{\sim} e'_1 \in A'_1 \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$.
- (g) Apply the induction hypothesis to 4(e)iv and $A_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A'_2$ to obtain $e_2 \overset{*}{\sim} e'_2 \in A'_2 \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$.
- (h) Apply the definition of equality at $A'_1 \otimes A'_2$ to 4e, replacing 4(e)iii and 4(e)iv with 4f and 4g, to obtain $e \sim e' \in A'_1 \otimes A'_2 \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$.
- (5) Subcase: $[A_1 \cdot \phi]$
- (a) We have $e \sim e' \in [A_1 \cdot \phi] \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$ and $[A_1 \cdot \phi] \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A'$.
- (b) We want to show $e \sim e' \in A' \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$.
- (c) By inversion on $[A_1 \cdot \phi] \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A'$ we have that $A' = [A'_1 \cdot \phi']$ and $A_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A'_1$ and $\phi \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'$.
- (d) Suffices to show $!e \overset{*}{\sim} !e' \in A'_1 \mid \phi' \sqcup \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$.
- (e) From the equality assumption we have $!e \overset{*}{\sim} !e' \in A_1 \mid \phi \sqcup \phi_1 [\phi'_2] [\Delta]$.
- (f) Apply the induction hypothesis to the equality from 5e and $A_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A'_1$ from 5c to get $!e \overset{*}{\sim} !e' \in A'_1 \mid \phi \sqcup \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$.
- (g) By Lemma C.6 on $\phi \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'$ we have $\phi \sqcup \phi_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi' \sqcup \phi_1$.
- (h) Apply Lemma C.26 to 5f and 5g to get $!e \overset{*}{\sim} !e' \in A'_1 \mid \phi' \sqcup \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$.
- (6) Subcase: $A_1 \rightarrow A_2$
- (a) We have $e \sim e' \in A_1 \rightarrow A_2 \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$ and $A_1 \rightarrow A_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A'$.
- (b) We want to show $e \sim e' \in A' \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$.
- (c) By inversion on $A_1 \rightarrow A_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A'$ we have that $A' = A'_1 \rightarrow A'_2$ and $A'_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A_1$ and $A_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A'_2$.
- (d) Assume $\phi'_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi'_1$ and $e_1 \text{ val}, e'_1 \text{ val}$ and $e_1 \overset{*}{\sim} e'_1 \in A'_1 \mid \phi'_1 [\phi'_2] [\Delta]$.
- (e) Suffices to show $\text{ap}(e; e_1) \overset{*}{\sim} \text{ap}(e'; e'_1) \in A'_2 \mid \phi'_1 \sqcup \phi_1 [\phi'_2] [\Delta]$.
- (f) Apply the induction hypothesis to the equality from 6d and $A'_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A_1$ from 6c to obtain $e_1 \overset{*}{\sim} e'_1 \in A_1 \mid \phi'_1 [\phi'_2] [\Delta]$.
- (g) Apply the initial equality assumption to ϕ'_2 and ϕ'_1 and $e_1 \text{ val}, e'_1 \text{ val}$ and 6f to obtain $\text{ap}(e; e_1) \overset{*}{\sim} \text{ap}(e'; e'_1) \in A_2 \mid \phi'_1 \sqcup \phi_1 [\phi'_2] [\Delta]$.
- (h) Apply the induction hypothesis to 6g and $A_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A'_2$ from 6c to obtain $\text{ap}(e; e_1) \overset{*}{\sim} \text{ap}(e'; e'_1) \in A'_2 \mid \phi'_1 \sqcup \phi_1 [\phi'_2] [\Delta]$.
- (7) Subcase: $\forall(\alpha.A_1)$
- (a) We have $e \sim e' \in \forall(\alpha.A_1) \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$ and $\forall(\alpha.A_1) \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A'$.
- (b) We want to show $e \sim e' \in A' \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$.
- (c) By inversion on $\forall(\alpha.A_1) \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} A'$ we have that $A' = \forall(\alpha.A'_1)$ and $A_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta, \alpha} A'_1$.
- (d) Assume $\Delta \vdash \phi$.
- (e) Apply Lemma C.18 to 7c and $\Delta \vdash \phi$ from 7d to obtain $[\phi/\alpha]A_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} [\phi/\alpha]A'_1$.
- (f) Suffices to show $e[\phi] \overset{*}{\sim} e'[\phi] \in [\phi/\alpha]A'_1 \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$.
- (g) We have by applying the initial equality assumption to 7d that $e[\phi] \overset{*}{\sim} e'[\phi] \in [\phi/\alpha]A_1 \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$.
- (h) By applying the induction hypothesis to 7g and 7e we have $e[\phi] \overset{*}{\sim} e'[\phi] \in [\phi/\alpha]A'_1 \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$. \square

Lemma C.29 (Anti-monotonicity). *If $e \overset{*}{\sim} e' \in A \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$ and $\phi'_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$ then $e \overset{*}{\sim} e' \in A \mid \phi_1 [\phi'_2] [\Delta]$.*

PROOF. Proceed by induction on the height of A .

(1) Case: Non-interference

- (a) Consider the first case.
- (b) We have $\phi_1 \not\sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$.
- (c) Show $\phi_1 \not\sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'_2$.

- (d) Apply Lemma C.9 to 1b and $\phi'_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$ to obtain the goal.
- (e) Now consider the second case. Proceed by cases on A .
- (2) Subcase: unit
 - We have $\langle \rangle \sim \langle \rangle \in \text{unit} \mid \phi_1 [\phi'_2] [\Delta]$ immediately.
- (3) Subcase: $A_1 + A_2$
 - (a) We have $e \sim e' \in A_1 + A_2 \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$ and $\phi'_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$.
 - (b) Show that $e \sim e' \in A_1 + A_2 \mid \phi_1 [\phi'_2] [\Delta]$.
 - (c) By the equality in 3a we have either:
 - (i) $e = 1 \cdot e_1, e' = 1 \cdot e'_1, e_1 \overset{*}{\sim} e'_1 \in A_1 \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$
 - (ii) $e = r \cdot e_1, e' = r \cdot e'_1, e_1 \overset{*}{\sim} e'_1 \in A_2 \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$
 - (d) Consider the first case without loss of generality.
 - (e) Apply the induction hypothesis to the equality from 3(c)i and $\phi'_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$ to obtain $e_1 \overset{*}{\sim} e'_1 \in A_1 \mid \phi_1 [\phi'_2] [\Delta]$.
 - (f) Apply the definition of equality at $A_1 + A_2$ to 3(c)i, replacing the equality with 3e, to obtain $e \sim e' \in A_1 + A_2 \mid \phi_1 [\phi'_2] [\Delta]$.
- (4) Subcase: $A_1 \otimes A_2$
 - (a) We have $e \sim e' \in A_1 \otimes A_2 \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$ and $\phi'_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$.
 - (b) Show that $e \sim e' \in A_1 \otimes A_2 \mid \phi_1 [\phi'_2] [\Delta]$.
 - (c) By the equality in 4a we have:
 - (i) $e = \langle e_1, e_2 \rangle$
 - (ii) $e' = \langle e'_1, e'_2 \rangle$
 - (iii) $e_1 \overset{*}{\sim} e'_1 \in A_1 \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$
 - (iv) $e_2 \overset{*}{\sim} e'_2 \in A_2 \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$
 - (d) Apply the induction hypothesis to 4(c)iii to obtain $e_1 \overset{*}{\sim} e'_1 \in A_1 \mid \phi_1 [\phi'_2] [\Delta]$.
 - (e) Apply the induction hypothesis to 4(c)iv to obtain $e_2 \overset{*}{\sim} e'_2 \in A_2 \mid \phi_1 [\phi'_2] [\Delta]$.
 - (f) Apply the definition of equality at $A_1 \otimes A_2$ to 4c, replacing 4(c)iii and 4(c)iv with 4d and 4e, to obtain $e \sim e' \in A_1 \otimes A_2 \mid \phi_1 [\phi'_2] [\Delta]$.
- (5) Subcase: $[A \cdot \phi]$
 - (a) We have $e \sim e' \in [A \cdot \phi] \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$ and $\phi'_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$.
 - (b) Show that $e \sim e' \in [A \cdot \phi] \mid \phi_1 [\phi'_2] [\Delta]$.
 - (c) Suffices to show $!e \overset{*}{\sim} !e' \in A \mid \phi \sqcup \phi_1 [\phi'_2] [\Delta]$.
 - (d) By the equality in 5a we have $!e \overset{*}{\sim} !e' \in A \mid \phi \sqcup \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$.
 - (e) Apply the induction hypothesis to 5d to obtain $!e \overset{*}{\sim} !e' \in A \mid \phi \sqcup \phi_1 [\phi'_2] [\Delta]$.
- (6) Subcase: $A_1 \rightarrow A_2$
 - (a) We have $e \sim e' \in A_1 \rightarrow A_2 \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$ and $\phi'_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$.
 - (b) Show that $e \sim e' \in A_1 \rightarrow A_2 \mid \phi_1 [\phi'_2] [\Delta]$.
 - (c) Assume some $\phi''_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'_2$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi'_1$ and $e_1 \text{ val}, e'_1 \text{ val}$ and $e_1 \overset{*}{\sim} e'_1 \in A_1 \mid \phi'_1 [\phi''_2] [\Delta]$.
 - (d) Suffices to show $\text{ap}(e; e_1) \overset{*}{\sim} \text{ap}(e'; e'_1) \in A_2 \mid \phi'_1 \sqcup \phi_1 [\phi''_2] [\Delta]$.
 - (e) Apply Lemma C.3 to $\phi''_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'_2$ and $\phi'_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$ to obtain $\phi''_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$.
 - (f) Apply the initially assumed equality to 6c, replacing the inequality with 6e, to obtain $\text{ap}(e; e_1) \overset{*}{\sim} \text{ap}(e'; e'_1) \in A_2 \mid \phi'_1 \sqcup \phi_1 [\phi''_2] [\Delta]$.
- (7) Subcase: $\forall(\alpha.A)$
 - (a) We have $e \sim e' \in \forall(\alpha.A) \mid \phi_1 [\phi_2] [\Delta]$ and $\phi'_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$.
 - (b) Show that $e \sim e' \in \forall(\alpha.A) \mid \phi_1 [\phi'_2] [\Delta]$.
 - (c) Assume some $\Delta \vdash \phi$.
 - (d) Suffices to show $e[\phi] \overset{*}{\sim} e'[\phi] \in [\phi/\alpha]A \mid \phi_1 [\phi'_2] [\Delta]$.

- (e) Apply the initially assumed equality to 7c to obtain $e[\phi] \stackrel{*}{\sim} e'[\phi] \in [\phi/\alpha]A \mid \phi_1[\phi_2][\Delta]$.
- (f) Apply the induction hypothesis to 7e to obtain $e[\phi] \stackrel{*}{\sim} e'[\phi] \in [\phi/\alpha]A \mid \phi_1[\phi'_2][\Delta]$.

□

Lemma C.30 (Symmetry). *If $e_1 \stackrel{*}{\sim} e_2 \in A \mid \phi[\phi'][\Delta]$ then $e_2 \stackrel{*}{\sim} e_1 \in A \mid \phi[\phi'][\Delta]$.*

PROOF. Proceed by induction on A .

(1) Case: Non-interference

- (a) We have either $\phi \not\sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'$ or $e_1 \sim e_2 \in A \mid \phi[\phi'][\Delta]$.
- (b) Consider the first case. We have the result immediately.
- (c) Consider the second case:
 - (i) We have $e_1 \mapsto^* e'_1, e'_1 \text{ val}$ and $e_2 \mapsto^* e'_2, e'_2 \text{ val}$ and $e'_1 \sim e'_2 \in A \mid \phi[\phi'][\Delta]$.
 - (ii) Show $e'_2 \sim e'_1 \in A \mid \phi[\phi'][\Delta]$.
 - (iii) Proceed by cases on A .

(2) Subcase: unit

We have $\langle \rangle \sim \langle \rangle \in A \mid \phi[\phi'][\Delta]$ immediately.

(3) Subcase: $A_1 + A_2$

- (a) Consider the left case without loss of generality.
- (b) We have $1 \cdot e_1 \sim 1 \cdot e_2 \in A_1 + A_2 \mid \phi[\phi'][\Delta]$.
- (c) Show $1 \cdot e_2 \sim 1 \cdot e_1 \in A_1 + A_2 \mid \phi[\phi'][\Delta]$.
- (d) From the equality assumption we have $e_1 \stackrel{*}{\sim} e_2 \in A_1 \mid \phi[\phi'][\Delta]$.
- (e) Apply the induction hypothesis to this to obtain $e_2 \stackrel{*}{\sim} e_1 \in A_1 \mid \phi[\phi'][\Delta]$.
- (f) So we have $1 \cdot e_2 \sim 1 \cdot e_1 \in A_1 + A_2 \mid \phi[\phi'][\Delta]$.

(4) Subcase: $A_1 \otimes A_2$

- (a) We have $\langle e_1, e_2 \rangle \sim \langle e'_1, e'_2 \rangle \in A_1 \otimes A_2 \mid \phi[\phi'][\Delta]$.
- (b) Show $\langle e'_1, e'_2 \rangle \sim \langle e_1, e_2 \rangle \in A_1 \otimes A_2 \mid \phi[\phi'][\Delta]$.
- (c) So we have:
 - (i) $e_1 \stackrel{*}{\sim} e'_1 \in A_1 \mid \phi[\phi'][\Delta]$
 - (ii) $e_2 \stackrel{*}{\sim} e'_2 \in A_2 \mid \phi[\phi'][\Delta]$
- (d) Apply the induction hypothesis to both equalities to obtain:
 - (i) $e'_1 \stackrel{*}{\sim} e_1 \in A_1 \mid \phi[\phi'][\Delta]$
 - (ii) $e'_2 \stackrel{*}{\sim} e_2 \in A_2 \mid \phi[\phi'][\Delta]$
- (e) So we have $\langle e_1, e_2 \rangle \sim \langle e'_1, e'_2 \rangle \in A_1 \otimes A_2 \mid \phi[\phi'][\Delta]$.

(5) Subcase: $[A \cdot \phi]$

- (a) We have $e_1 \sim e_2 \in [A \cdot \phi_1] \mid \phi[\phi'][\Delta]$.
- (b) Show $e_2 \sim e_1 \in [A \cdot \phi_1] \mid \phi[\phi'][\Delta]$.
- (c) Suffices to show $!e_2 \stackrel{*}{\sim} !e_1 \in A \mid \phi_1 \sqcup \phi[\phi'][\Delta]$.
- (d) From the equality assumption we have $!e_1 \stackrel{*}{\sim} !e_2 \in A \mid \phi_1 \sqcup \phi[\phi'][\Delta]$.
- (e) Apply the induction hypothesis to this equality to obtain $!e_2 \stackrel{*}{\sim} !e_1 \in A \mid \phi_1 \sqcup \phi[\phi'][\Delta]$.

(6) Subcase: $A_1 \rightarrow A_2$

- (a) We have $e_1 \sim e_2 \in A_1 \rightarrow A_2 \mid \phi[\phi'][\Delta]$.
- (b) Show $e_2 \sim e_1 \in A_1 \rightarrow A_2 \mid \phi[\phi'][\Delta]$.
- (c) Assume some $\phi'' \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi'_1$ and $e \text{ val}, e' \text{ val}$ and $e \stackrel{*}{\sim} e' \in A_1 \mid \phi'_1[\phi''][\Delta]$.
- (d) Suffices to show $\text{ap}(e_2; e) \stackrel{*}{\sim} \text{ap}(e_1; e') \in A_2 \mid \phi'_1 \sqcup \phi[\phi''][\Delta]$.
- (e) Apply the induction hypothesis to $e \stackrel{*}{\sim} e' \in A_1 \mid \phi'_1[\phi''][\Delta]$ to obtain $e' \stackrel{*}{\sim} e \in A_1 \mid \phi'_1[\phi''][\Delta]$.
- (f) Apply the initial equality assumption to this result to obtain $\text{ap}(e_1; e') \stackrel{*}{\sim} \text{ap}(e_2; e) \in A_2 \mid \phi'_1 \sqcup \phi[\phi''][\Delta]$.

- (g) Apply the induction hypothesis to this result to obtain
 $\text{ap}(e_2; e) \stackrel{*}{\sim} \text{ap}(e_1; e') \in A_2 \mid \phi'_1 \sqcup \phi [\phi''] [\Delta]$.
- (7) Subcase: $\forall(\alpha.A)$
- (a) We have $e_1 \sim e_2 \in \forall(\alpha.A) \mid \phi [\phi'] [\Delta]$.
 - (b) Show $e_2 \sim e_1 \in \forall(\alpha.A) \mid \phi [\phi'] [\Delta]$.
 - (c) Assume some $\Delta \vdash \phi_1$.
 - (d) Suffices to show $e_2[\phi_1] \stackrel{*}{\sim} e_1[\phi_1] \in [\phi_1/\alpha]A \mid \phi [\phi'] [\Delta]$.
 - (e) Apply the equality assumption to $\Delta \vdash \phi_1$ to obtain $e_1[\phi_1] \stackrel{*}{\sim} e_2[\phi_1] \in [\phi_1/\alpha]A \mid \phi [\phi'] [\Delta]$.
 - (f) Apply the induction hypothesis to this to obtain $e_2[\phi_1] \stackrel{*}{\sim} e_1[\phi_1] \in [\phi_1/\alpha]A \mid \phi [\phi'] [\Delta]$.

□

Lemma C.31 (Transitivity). *If $e_1 \stackrel{*}{\sim} e_2 \in A \mid \phi [\phi'] [\Delta]$ and $e_2 \stackrel{*}{\sim} e_3 \in A \mid \phi [\phi'] [\Delta]$ then $e_1 \stackrel{*}{\sim} e_3 \in A \mid \phi [\phi'] [\Delta]$*

PROOF. Proceed by induction on A .

(1) Case: Non-interference

- (a) Consider the first case.
- (b) If $\phi \not\sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'$ then we have the result immediately.
- (c) Consider the second case.
- (d) Then we have $e_1 \sim e_2 \in A \mid \phi [\phi'] [\Delta]$ and $e_2 \sim e_3 \in A \mid \phi [\phi'] [\Delta]$.
- (e) Want to show that $e_1 \sim e_3 \in A \mid \phi [\phi'] [\Delta]$.
- (f) Proceed by cases on A .

(2) Case: unit

We have $\langle \rangle \sim \langle \rangle \in \text{unit} \mid \phi [\phi'] [\Delta]$.

(3) Case: $A_1 + A_2$

- (a) So we have $e_1 \sim e_2 \in A_1 + A_2 \mid \phi [\phi'] [\Delta]$ and $e_2 \sim e_3 \in A_1 + A_2 \mid \phi [\phi'] [\Delta]$.
- (b) Show $e_1 \sim e_3 \in A_1 + A_2 \mid \phi [\phi'] [\Delta]$.
- (c) So we have, without loss of generality for the first equality assumption:
 - (i) $e_1 = 1 \cdot e'_1, e_2 = 1 \cdot e'_2$
 - (ii) $e'_1 \stackrel{*}{\sim} e'_2 \in A_1 \mid \phi [\phi'] [\Delta]$
- (d) So we know that we must have for the second equality assumption:
 - (i) $e_2 = 1 \cdot e'_2, e_3 = 1 \cdot e'_3$
 - (ii) $e'_2 \stackrel{*}{\sim} e'_3 \in A_1 \mid \phi [\phi'] [\Delta]$
- (e) Apply the induction hypothesis to 3(c)ii and 3(d)ii to obtain $e'_1 \stackrel{*}{\sim} e'_3 \in A_1 \mid \phi [\phi'] [\Delta]$.
- (f) Apply the definition of exact equality at type $A_1 + A_2$ to $e_1 = 1 \cdot e'_1, e_3 = 1 \cdot e'_3$ and 3e to obtain $e_1 \sim e_3 \in A_1 + A_2 \mid \phi [\phi'] [\Delta]$.

(4) Case: $A_1 \otimes A_2$

- (a) So we have $e_1 \sim e_2 \in A_1 \otimes A_2 \mid \phi [\phi'] [\Delta]$ and $e_2 \sim e_3 \in A_1 \otimes A_2 \mid \phi [\phi'] [\Delta]$.
- (b) Show $e_1 \sim e_3 \in A_1 \otimes A_2 \mid \phi [\phi'] [\Delta]$.
- (c) From the assumptions we have:
 - (i) $e_1 = \langle e'_1, e''_1 \rangle$
 - (ii) $e_2 = \langle e'_2, e''_2 \rangle$
 - (iii) $e_3 = \langle e'_3, e''_3 \rangle$
 - (iv) $e'_1 \stackrel{*}{\sim} e'_2 \in A_1 \mid \phi [\phi'] [\Delta]$
 - (v) $e''_1 \stackrel{*}{\sim} e''_2 \in A_2 \mid \phi [\phi'] [\Delta]$
 - (vi) $e'_2 \stackrel{*}{\sim} e'_3 \in A_1 \mid \phi [\phi'] [\Delta]$
 - (vii) $e''_2 \stackrel{*}{\sim} e''_3 \in A_2 \mid \phi [\phi'] [\Delta]$

- (d) Apply the induction hypothesis to 4(c)iv and 4(c)vi to obtain $e'_1 \sim^* e'_3 \in A_1 \mid \phi[\phi'] [\Delta]$.
- (e) Apply the induction hypothesis to 4(c)v and 4(c)vii to obtain $e''_1 \sim^* e''_3 \in A_2 \mid \phi[\phi'] [\Delta]$.
- (f) Apply the definition of exact equality at $A_1 \otimes A_2$ to 4d and 4e to obtain $\langle e'_1, e''_1 \rangle \sim \langle e'_3, e''_3 \rangle \in A_1 \otimes A_2 \mid \phi[\phi'] [\Delta]$.
- (g) This is equivalent to $e_1 \sim e_3 \in A_1 \otimes A_2 \mid \phi[\phi'] [\Delta]$.
- (5) Case: $[A \cdot \phi_1]$
- (a) So we have $e_1 \sim e_2 \in [A_1 \cdot \phi_1] \mid \phi[\phi'] [\Delta]$ and $e_2 \sim e_3 \in [A_1 \cdot \phi_1] \mid \phi[\phi'] [\Delta]$.
- (b) Show $e_1 \sim e_3 \in [A_1 \cdot \phi_1] \mid \phi[\phi'] [\Delta]$.
- (c) Suffices to show $!e_1 \sim^* !e_3 \in A_1 \mid \phi_1 \sqcup \phi[\phi'] [\Delta]$.
- (d) From both equality assumptions we have:
- (i) $!e_1 \sim^* !e_2 \in A_1 \mid \phi_1 \sqcup \phi[\phi'] [\Delta]$
- (ii) $!e_2 \sim^* !e_3 \in A_1 \mid \phi_1 \sqcup \phi[\phi'] [\Delta]$.
- (e) Apply the induction hypothesis to both of these equalities to obtain $!e_1 \sim^* !e_3 \in A_1 \mid \phi_1 \sqcup \phi[\phi'] [\Delta]$.
- (6) Case: $A_1 \rightarrow A_2$
- (a) So we have $e_1 \sim e_2 \in A_1 \rightarrow A_2 \mid \phi[\phi'] [\Delta]$ and $e_2 \sim e_3 \in A_1 \rightarrow A_2 \mid \phi[\phi'] [\Delta]$.
- (b) Show $e_1 \sim e_3 \in A_1 \rightarrow A_2 \mid \phi[\phi'] [\Delta]$.
- (c) Assume some $\phi'' \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi_1$ and $e \text{ val}, e' \text{ val}$ and $e \sim^* e' \in A_1 \mid \phi_1[\phi''] [\Delta]$.
- (d) Suffices to show $\text{ap}(e_1; e) \sim^* \text{ap}(e_3; e') \in A_2 \mid \phi_1 \sqcup \phi[\phi''] [\Delta]$.
- (e) Apply Lemma C.30 to the equality assumption in 6c to obtain $e' \sim^* e \in A_1 \mid \phi_1[\phi''] [\Delta]$.
- (f) Apply the induction hypothesis to the equality assumption in 6c and 6e to obtain $e \sim^* e \in A_1 \mid \phi_1[\phi''] [\Delta]$.
- (g) Instantiate the first equality assumption in 6a with ϕ'' and ϕ_1 and $e \text{ val}, e' \text{ val}$ and 6f to obtain $\text{ap}(e_1; e) \sim^* \text{ap}(e_2; e) \in A_2 \mid \phi_1 \sqcup \phi[\phi''] [\Delta]$.
- (h) Instantiate the second equality assumption in 6a with 6c to obtain $\text{ap}(e_2; e) \sim^* \text{ap}(e_3; e') \in A_2 \mid \phi_1 \sqcup \phi[\phi''] [\Delta]$.
- (i) Apply the induction hypothesis to 6g and 6h to obtain $\text{ap}(e_1; e) \sim^* \text{ap}(e_3; e') \in A_2 \mid \phi_1 \sqcup \phi[\phi''] [\Delta]$.
- (7) Case: $\forall(\alpha.A)$
- (a) So we have $e_1 \sim e_2 \in \forall(\alpha.A) \mid \phi[\phi'] [\Delta]$ and $e_2 \sim e_3 \in \forall(\alpha.A) \mid \phi[\phi'] [\Delta]$.
- (b) Show $e_1 \sim e_3 \in \forall(\alpha.A) \mid \phi[\phi'] [\Delta]$.
- (c) Assume some $\Delta \vdash \phi_1$.
- (d) Suffices to show $e_1[\phi_1] \sim^* e_3[\phi_1] \in [\phi_1/\alpha]A \mid \phi[\phi'] [\Delta]$.
- (e) Apply each of the equality assumptions in 7a to 7c to obtain:
- (i) $e_1[\phi_1] \sim^* e_2[\phi_1] \in [\phi_1/\alpha]A \mid \phi[\phi'] [\Delta]$
- (ii) $e_2[\phi_1] \sim^* e_3[\phi_1] \in [\phi_1/\alpha]A \mid \phi[\phi'] [\Delta]$.
- (f) Apply the induction hypothesis to both of these equalities to obtain $e_1[\phi_1] \sim^* e_3[\phi_1] \in [\phi_1/\alpha]A \mid \phi[\phi'] [\Delta]$.

□

Lemma C.32 (Self-Related). *If $e \sim^* e' \in A \mid \phi[\phi'] [\Delta]$ then $e \sim^* e \in A \mid \phi[\phi'] [\Delta]$ and $e' \sim^* e' \in A \mid \phi[\phi'] [\Delta]$.*

PROOF. Proceed directly.

- (1) We have $e \sim^* e' \in A \mid \phi[\phi'] [\Delta]$.
- (2) Apply Lemma C.30 to 1 to obtain $e' \sim^* e \in A \mid \phi[\phi'] [\Delta]$.
- (3) Apply Lemma C.31 to 1 and 2 to obtain $e \sim^* e \in A \mid \phi[\phi'] [\Delta]$.
- (4) Apply Lemma C.31 to 2 and 1 to obtain $e' \sim^* e' \in A \mid \phi[\phi'] [\Delta]$.

□

Theorem C.33 (Reflexivity). *If $\Delta_0, \Delta; \Gamma \vdash e : A \mid \phi$ then $\Delta \Gamma \gg_{\Delta_0}^{\phi'} e \sim^* e \in A \mid \phi$.*

PROOF. Assume some $\Delta_0 \vdash \phi_\gamma$ and $\Delta_0 \vdash \phi'$ and $\delta : \Delta \rightsquigarrow \Delta_0$ and $\gamma \sim^* \gamma' \in \Gamma \mid \phi_\gamma [\phi'] \mid [\Delta \rightsquigarrow \Delta_0]$. Proceed by induction on typing.

(1) Case: T-SUB

(a) We have $\Delta_0, \Delta; \Gamma \vdash e : A_2 \mid \phi$.

(b) Show $\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e)) \sim^* \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e)) \in \widehat{\delta}(A_2) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi) \sqcup \phi_\gamma [\phi'] \mid [\Delta_0]$.

(c) We have as premises $\Delta_0, \Delta; \Gamma \vdash e : A_1 \mid \phi$ and $A_1 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta_0, \Delta} A_2$.

(d) Apply the induction hypothesis to the first premise to obtain $\Delta \Gamma \gg_{\Delta_0}^{\phi'} e \sim^* e \in A_1 \mid \phi$.

(e) Instantiate **1d** with ϕ_γ and ϕ' and δ and γ, γ' to obtain

$\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e)) \sim^* \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e)) \in \widehat{\delta}(A_1) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi) \sqcup \phi_\gamma [\phi'] \mid [\Delta_0]$.

(f) We have $\widehat{\delta}(A_1) \sqsubseteq_{\Delta_0} \widehat{\delta}(A_2)$ by Lemma **C.19** on the second premise.

(g) Apply Lemma **C.28** to **1e** and **1f** to obtain $\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e)) \sim^* \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e)) \in \widehat{\delta}(A_2) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi) \sqcup \phi_\gamma [\phi'] \mid [\Delta_0]$.

(2) Case: T-UNIT

(a) We have $\Delta_0, \Delta; \Gamma \vdash \langle \rangle : \text{unit} \mid \circ$.

(b) Show $\langle \rangle \sim^* \langle \rangle \in \text{unit} \mid \phi_\gamma [\phi'] \mid [\Delta_0]$.

(c) We have this immediately.

(3) Case: T-VAR

(a) We have $\Delta_0, \Delta; \Gamma, x : A \vdash x : A \mid \circ$.

(b) Show $\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(x)) \sim^* \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(x)) \in \widehat{\delta}(A) \mid \phi_\gamma [\phi'] \mid [\Delta_0]$.

(c) By definition, $\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(x)) = \gamma(x)$ and $\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(x)) = \gamma'(x)$.

(d) So we have to show $\gamma(x) \sim^* \gamma'(x) \in \widehat{\delta}(A) \mid \phi_\gamma [\phi'] \mid [\Delta_0]$.

(e) We have this by definition of $\gamma \sim^* \gamma' \in \Gamma \mid \phi_\gamma [\phi'] \mid [\Delta \rightsquigarrow \Delta_0]$.

(4) Case: T-CONSUME

(a) We have $\Delta_0, \Delta; \Gamma \vdash \#e : [A \cdot \phi] \mid \circ$.

(b) Show $\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(\#e)) \sim^* \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(\#e)) \in \widehat{\delta}([A \cdot \phi]) \mid \phi_\gamma [\phi'] \mid [\Delta_0]$.

(c) This is equivalent to $\#\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e)) \sim^* \#\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e)) \in [\widehat{\delta}(A) \cdot \widehat{\delta}(\phi)] \mid \phi_\gamma [\phi'] \mid [\Delta_0]$.

(d) We have $\#\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e)) \text{ val}, \#\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e)) \text{ val}$ and $\#\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e)) \mapsto^* \#\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e)), \#\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e)) \mapsto^* \#\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e))$.

(e) Suffices to show $!\#\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e)) \sim^* !\#\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e)) \in \widehat{\delta}(A) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi) \sqcup \phi_\gamma [\phi'] \mid [\Delta_0]$.

(f) We have as a premise of T-CONSUME that $\Delta_0, \Delta; \Gamma \vdash e : A \mid \phi$.

(g) By applying the induction hypothesis to this premise we have $\Delta \Gamma \gg_{\Delta_0}^{\phi'} e \sim^* e \in A \mid \phi$.

(h) Instantiating with ϕ_γ and ϕ' and δ and γ, γ' we get $\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e)) \sim^* \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e)) \in \widehat{\delta}(A) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi) \sqcup \phi_\gamma [\phi'] \mid [\Delta_0]$.

(i) We have $!\#\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e)) \mapsto^* \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e)), !\#\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e)) \mapsto^* \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e))$.

(j) Apply Lemma **C.24** twice and symmetrically to **4h** and each evaluation in **4i** to obtain

$!\#\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e)) \sim^* !\#\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e)) \in \widehat{\delta}(A) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi) \sqcup \phi_\gamma [\phi'] \mid [\Delta_0]$.

(5) Case: T-PRODUCE

(a) We have $\Delta_0, \Delta; \Gamma \vdash !e : A \mid \phi_1 \sqcup \phi_2$.

(b) Show $\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(!e)) \sim^* \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(!e)) \in \widehat{\delta}(A) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi_1 \sqcup \phi_2) \sqcup \phi_\gamma [\phi'] \mid [\Delta_0]$.

(c) This is the same as $!\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e)) \sim^* !\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e)) \in \widehat{\delta}(A) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi_1) \sqcup \widehat{\delta}(\phi_2) \sqcup \phi_\gamma [\phi'] \mid [\Delta_0]$.

(d) We have as a premise of T-PRODUCE that $\Delta_0, \Delta; \Gamma \vdash e : [A \cdot \phi_1] \mid \phi_2$.

(e) By applying the induction hypothesis to this premise we have $\Delta \Gamma \gg_{\Delta_0}^{\phi'} e \sim^* e \in [A \cdot \phi_1] \mid \phi_2$.

- (f) Instantiating with ϕ_Y and ϕ' and δ and γ, γ' we have
 $\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e)) \sim \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e)) \in \widehat{\delta}([A \cdot \phi_1] \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi_2) \sqcup \phi_Y [\phi'] [\Delta_0]).$
- (g) This is the same as $\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e)) \sim \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e)) \in [\widehat{\delta}(A) \cdot \widehat{\delta}(\phi_1)] \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi_2) \sqcup \phi_Y [\phi'] [\Delta_0].$
- (h) Case on 5g:
 (i) $\widehat{\delta}(\phi_2) \sqcup \phi_Y \not\sqsubseteq_{\Delta_0} \phi'$
 (A) Apply Lemma C.7 to $\widehat{\delta}(\phi_2) \sqcup \phi_Y \not\sqsubseteq_{\Delta_0} \phi'$ and $\widehat{\delta}(\phi_1)$ to get $\widehat{\delta}(\phi_1) \sqcup \widehat{\delta}(\phi_2) \sqcup \phi_Y \not\sqsubseteq_{\Delta_0} \phi'$.
 (B) So we have $!\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e)) \sim !\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e)) \in \widehat{\delta}(A) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi_1) \sqcup \widehat{\delta}(\phi_2) \sqcup \phi_Y [\phi'] [\Delta_0].$
 (ii) $e_1 \sim e'_1 \in [\widehat{\delta}(A) \cdot \widehat{\delta}(\phi_1)] \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi_2) \sqcup \phi_Y [\phi'] [\Delta_0]$
 (A) Where $\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e)) \mapsto^* e_1, \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e)) \mapsto^* e'_1, e_1 \text{ val}, e'_1 \text{ val}.$
 (B) By definition, we have $!e_1 \sim !e'_1 \in \widehat{\delta}(A) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi_1) \sqcup \widehat{\delta}(\phi_2) \sqcup \phi_Y [\phi'] [\Delta_0].$
 (C) We have $!\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e)) \mapsto !e_1, !\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e)) \mapsto !e'_1$ from 5(h)iiiA.
 (D) Apply Lemma C.24 to 5(h)iiB and 5(h)iiC to obtain
 $!\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e)) \sim !\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e)) \in \widehat{\delta}(A) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi_1) \sqcup \widehat{\delta}(\phi_2) \sqcup \phi_Y [\phi'] [\Delta_0].$
- (6) Case: T-INJL
 (a) We have $\Delta_0, \Delta; \Gamma \vdash 1 \cdot e : A_1 + A_2 \mid \phi.$
 (b) Show $1 \cdot \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e)) \sim 1 \cdot \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e)) \in \widehat{\delta}(A_1) + \widehat{\delta}(A_2) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi) \sqcup \phi_Y [\phi'] [\Delta_0].$
 (c) We have as premises that $\Delta_0, \Delta; \Gamma \vdash e : A_1 \mid \phi$ and $\Delta_0, \Delta \vdash A_2.$
 (d) Apply the induction hypothesis to the typing premise in 6c to obtain $\Delta \Gamma \gg_{\Delta_0}^{\phi'} e \sim^* e \in A_1 \mid \phi.$
- (e) Instantiate 6d with ϕ_Y and ϕ' and δ and γ, γ' to obtain
 $\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e)) \sim \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e)) \in \widehat{\delta}(A_1) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi) \sqcup \phi_Y [\phi'] [\Delta_0].$
- (f) If $\widehat{\delta}(\phi) \sqcup \phi_Y \not\sqsubseteq_{\Delta_0} \phi'$, then we have the result immediately.
- (g) Otherwise, we have $e_1 \sim e'_1 \in \widehat{\delta}(A_1) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi) \sqcup \phi_Y [\phi'] [\Delta_0]$, where $\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e)) \mapsto^* e_1, e_1 \text{ val}$ and $\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e)) \mapsto^* e'_1, e'_1 \text{ val}.$
- (h) Apply E-LEFT-CONG to the evaluations from 6g to obtain $1 \cdot \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e)) \mapsto^* 1 \cdot e_1$ and $1 \cdot \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e)) \mapsto^* 1 \cdot e'_1.$
- (i) From 6g we have $e_1 \sim e'_1 \in \widehat{\delta}(A_1) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi) \sqcup \phi_Y [\phi'] [\Delta_0].$
- (j) Applying the definition of equality at type $\widehat{\delta}(A_1) + \widehat{\delta}(A_2)$ to the equality from 6i and $1 \cdot e_1, 1 \cdot e'_1$ we have $1 \cdot e_1 \sim 1 \cdot e'_1 \in \widehat{\delta}(A_1) + \widehat{\delta}(A_2) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi) \sqcup \phi_Y [\phi'] [\Delta_0].$
- (k) So we have $1 \cdot \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e)) \sim 1 \cdot \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e)) \in \widehat{\delta}(A_1) + \widehat{\delta}(A_2) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi) \sqcup \phi_Y [\phi'] [\Delta_0]$, combining 6j and $1 \cdot e_1 \text{ val}, 1 \cdot e'_1 \text{ val}$ and 6h.
- (7) Case: T-INJR
 Analogous to the case for T-INJL.
- (8) Case: T-CASE
 (a) We have $\Delta_0, \Delta; \Gamma \vdash \text{case } e \{ 1 \cdot x_1 \hookrightarrow e_1 \mid r \cdot x_2 \hookrightarrow e_2 \} : A \mid \phi_1 \sqcup \phi_2.$
 (b) Show case $\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e)) \{ 1 \cdot x_1 \hookrightarrow \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e_1)) \mid r \cdot x_2 \hookrightarrow \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e_2)) \} \sim \text{case } \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e)) \{ 1 \cdot x_1 \hookrightarrow \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e_1)) \mid r \cdot x_2 \hookrightarrow \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e_2)) \} \in \widehat{\delta}(A) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi_1) \sqcup \widehat{\delta}(\phi_2) \sqcup \phi_Y [\phi'] [\Delta_0].$
 (c) We have as premises:
 (i) $\Delta_0, \Delta; \Gamma \vdash e : A_1 + A_2 \mid \phi_1$
 (ii) $\Delta_0, \Delta; \Gamma, x_1 : A_1 \vdash e_1 : A \mid \phi_2$
 (iii) $\Delta_0, \Delta; \Gamma, x_2 : A_2 \vdash e_2 : A \mid \phi_2$
 (d) Apply the induction hypothesis to 8c to obtain:
 (i) $\Delta \Gamma \gg_{\Delta_0}^{\phi'} e \sim^* e \in A_1 + A_2 \mid \phi_1$

- (ii) $\Delta \Gamma, x_1 : A_1 \gg_{\Delta_0}^{\phi'} e_1 \sim^* e_1 \in A \mid \phi_2$
- (iii) $\Delta \Gamma, x_2 : A_2 \gg_{\Delta_0}^{\phi'} e_2 \sim^* e_2 \in A \mid \phi_2$
- (e) Instantiate **8(d)i** with ϕ_Y and ϕ' and δ and γ, γ' to obtain
 $\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e)) \sim^* \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e)) \in \widehat{\delta}(A_1) + \widehat{\delta}(A_2) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi_1) \sqcup \phi_Y [\phi'] [\Delta_0]$.
- (f) Case on whether **8e** is in non-interference:
 (i) $\widehat{\delta}(\phi_1) \sqcup \phi_Y \not\sqsubseteq_{\Delta_0} \phi'$
 Apply Lemma **C.7** to this case and $\widehat{\delta}(\phi_2)$ to obtain $\widehat{\delta}(\phi_1) \sqcup \widehat{\delta}(\phi_2) \sqcup \phi_Y \not\sqsubseteq_{\Delta_0} \phi'$.
- (ii) $1 \cdot e_3 \sim 1 \cdot e'_3 \in \widehat{\delta}(A_1) + \widehat{\delta}(A_2) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi_1) \sqcup \phi_Y [\phi'] [\Delta_0]$
 (A) Where $\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e)) \mapsto^* 1 \cdot e_3$, $\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e)) \mapsto^* 1 \cdot e'_3$, e_3 val, e'_3 val, without loss of generality.
 (B) So we have by definition $e_3 \sim^* e'_3 \in \widehat{\delta}(A_1) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi_1) \sqcup \phi_Y [\phi'] [\Delta_0]$.
 (C) Define $\gamma_1 = \gamma[x_1 \mapsto e_3]$, $\gamma'_1 = \gamma[x_1 \mapsto e'_3]$ where we have γ_1, γ'_1 equal at level $\widehat{\delta}(\phi_1) \sqcup \phi_Y$ by Lemma **C.27**.
 (D) Instantiate **8(d)ii** with $\widehat{\delta}(\phi_1) \sqcup \phi_Y$ and ϕ' and δ and γ_1, γ'_1 to obtain
 $\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}_1(e_1)) \sim^* \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'_1(e_1)) \in \widehat{\delta}(A) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi_2) \sqcup \widehat{\delta}(\phi_1) \sqcup \phi_Y [\phi'] [\Delta_0]$.
 (E) This is equivalent to $[e_3/x_1]\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e_1)) \sim^* [e'_3/x_1]\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e_1)) \in \widehat{\delta}(A) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi_1) \sqcup \widehat{\delta}(\phi_2) \sqcup \phi_Y [\phi'] [\Delta_0]$.
- (F) Apply E-CASE- $\beta 1$ to $\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e)) \mapsto^* 1 \cdot e_3$ and $1 \cdot e_3$ val (which we have by applying V-LEFT to e_3 val) to obtain case $\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e)) \{ 1 \cdot x_1 \hookrightarrow \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e_1)) \mid r \cdot x_2 \hookrightarrow \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e_2)) \} \mapsto^* [e_3/x_1]\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e_1))$.
- (G) Analogously we have case $\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e)) \{ 1 \cdot x_1 \hookrightarrow \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e_1)) \mid r \cdot x_2 \hookrightarrow \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e_2)) \} \mapsto^* [e'_3/x_1]\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e_1))$.
- (H) Apply Lemma **C.24** symmetrically to **8(f)iiE** and each of **8(f)iiF** and **8(f)iiG** to obtain case $\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e)) \{ 1 \cdot x_1 \hookrightarrow \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e_1)) \mid r \cdot x_2 \hookrightarrow \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e_2)) \} \sim^* \text{case } \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e)) \{ 1 \cdot x_1 \hookrightarrow \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e_1)) \mid r \cdot x_2 \hookrightarrow \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e_2)) \} \in \widehat{\delta}(A) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi_1) \sqcup \widehat{\delta}(\phi_2) \sqcup \phi_Y [\phi'] [\Delta_0]$.
- (9) Case: T-PAIR
 (a) We have $\Delta_0, \Delta; \Gamma \vdash \langle e_1, e_2 \rangle : A_1 \otimes A_2 \mid \phi_1 \sqcup \phi_2$.
 (b) Show $\langle \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e_1)), \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e_2)) \rangle \sim^* \langle \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e_1)), \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e_2)) \rangle \in \widehat{\delta}(A_1) \otimes \widehat{\delta}(A_2) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi_1) \sqcup \widehat{\delta}(\phi_2) \sqcup \phi_Y [\phi'] [\Delta_0]$.
 (c) We have as premises $\Delta_0, \Delta; \Gamma \vdash e_1 : A_1 \mid \phi_1$ and $\Delta_0, \Delta; \Gamma \vdash e_2 : A_2 \mid \phi_2$.
 (d) Apply the induction hypothesis to each of the premises to obtain:
 (i) $\Delta \Gamma \gg_{\Delta_0}^{\phi'} e_1 \sim^* e_1 \in A_1 \mid \phi_1$
 (ii) $\Delta \Gamma \gg_{\Delta_0}^{\phi'} e_2 \sim^* e_2 \in A_2 \mid \phi_2$
- (e) Instantiate **9d** with ϕ_Y and ϕ' and δ and γ, γ' to obtain:
 (i) $\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e_1)) \sim^* \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e_1)) \in \widehat{\delta}(A_1) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi_1) \sqcup \phi_Y [\phi'] [\Delta_0]$
 (ii) $\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e_2)) \sim^* \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e_2)) \in \widehat{\delta}(A_2) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi_2) \sqcup \phi_Y [\phi'] [\Delta_0]$
- (f) If either $\widehat{\delta}(\phi_1) \sqcup \phi_Y \not\sqsubseteq_{\Delta_0} \phi'$ or $\widehat{\delta}(\phi_2) \sqcup \phi_Y \not\sqsubseteq_{\Delta_0} \phi'$ then we have the result by Lemma **C.7**.
- (g) Otherwise, from each equality in **9e** we have
 (i) $\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e_1)) \mapsto^* e'_1, e'_1$ val
 (ii) $\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e_1)) \mapsto^* e''_1, e''_1$ val
 (iii) $\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e_2)) \mapsto^* e'_2, e'_2$ val
 (iv) $\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e_2)) \mapsto^* e''_2, e''_2$ val
- (h) So we have $\langle \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e_1)), \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e_2)) \rangle \mapsto^* \langle e'_1, e'_2 \rangle, \langle e'_1, e'_2 \rangle$ val and $\langle \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e_1)), \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e_2)) \rangle \mapsto^* \langle e''_1, e''_2 \rangle, \langle e''_1, e''_2 \rangle$ val.
- (i) Apply Lemma **C.25** to each equality in **9e** and each evaluation in **9g** to obtain:

- (i) $e'_1 \sim e''_1 \in \widehat{\delta}(A_1) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi_1) \sqcup \phi_\gamma [\phi'] [\Delta_0]$
(ii) $e'_2 \sim e''_2 \in \widehat{\delta}(A_2) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi_2) \sqcup \phi_\gamma [\phi'] [\Delta_0]$
(j) We have $\langle e'_1, e'_2 \rangle \sim \langle e''_1, e''_2 \rangle \in \widehat{\delta}(A_1) \otimes \widehat{\delta}(A_2) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi_1) \sqcup \widehat{\delta}(\phi_2) \sqcup \phi_\gamma [\phi'] [\Delta_0]$ by applying the definition of equality at type $\widehat{\delta}(A_1) \otimes \widehat{\delta}(A_2)$ to **9i**.
(k) And we have
 $\langle \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e_1)), \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e_2)) \rangle \sim \langle \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e_1)), \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e_2)) \rangle \in \widehat{\delta}(A_1) \otimes \widehat{\delta}(A_2) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi_1) \sqcup \widehat{\delta}(\phi_2) \sqcup \phi_\gamma [\phi'] [\Delta_0]$
by applying the definition of equality to **9j** and **9h**.
(10) Case: T-SPLIT
(a) We have $\Delta_0, \Delta; \Gamma \vdash \text{split } e \text{ into } \langle x_1, x_2 \rangle \text{ in } e' : A \mid \phi \sqcup \phi_1$.
(b) Show that
 $\text{split } \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e)) \text{ into } \langle x_1, x_2 \rangle \text{ in } \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e')) \sim \text{split } \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e)) \text{ into } \langle x_1, x_2 \rangle \text{ in } \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e')) \in$
 $\widehat{\delta}(A) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi) \sqcup \widehat{\delta}(\phi_1) \sqcup \phi_\gamma [\phi'] [\Delta_0]$.
(c) We have as premises:
(i) $\Delta_0, \Delta; \Gamma \vdash e : A_1 \otimes A_2 \mid \phi$
(ii) $\Delta_0, \Delta; \Gamma, x_1 : A_1, x_2 : A_2 \vdash e' : A \mid \phi_1$
(d) Apply the induction hypothesis to each premise to obtain:
(i) $\Delta \Gamma \gg_{\Delta_0}^{\phi'} e \sim e \in A_1 \otimes A_2 \mid \phi$
(ii) $\Delta \Gamma, x_1 : A_1, x_2 : A_2 \gg_{\Delta_0}^{\phi'} e' \sim e' \in A \mid \phi_1$
(e) Instantiate the first equality with ϕ_γ and ϕ' and δ and γ, γ' to obtain
 $\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e)) \sim \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e)) \in \widehat{\delta}(A_1) \otimes \widehat{\delta}(A_2) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi) \sqcup \phi_\gamma [\phi'] [\Delta_0]$
(f) Case on this equality:
(i) Case: $\widehat{\delta}(\phi) \sqcup \phi_\gamma \not\sqsubseteq_{\Delta_0} \phi'$
Apply Lemma **C.7** to this case and $\widehat{\delta}(\phi_1)$ to obtain $\widehat{\delta}(\phi) \sqcup \widehat{\delta}(\phi_1) \sqcup \phi_\gamma \not\sqsubseteq_{\Delta_0} \phi'$.
(ii) Case: $\langle e_1, e_2 \rangle \sim \langle e'_1, e'_2 \rangle \in \widehat{\delta}(A_1) \otimes \widehat{\delta}(A_2) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi) \sqcup \phi_\gamma [\phi'] [\Delta_0]$
(A) Where $\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e)) \mapsto^* \langle e_1, e_2 \rangle, \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e)) \mapsto^* \langle e'_1, e'_2 \rangle, \langle e_1, e_2 \rangle \text{ val}, \langle e'_1, e'_2 \rangle \text{ val}$.
(B) We have by definition $e_1 \sim e'_1 \in A_1 \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi) \sqcup \phi_\gamma [\phi'] [\Delta_0], e_2 \sim e'_2 \in A_2 \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi) \sqcup \phi_\gamma [\phi'] [\Delta_0]$.
(C) Define $\gamma_1 = \gamma[x_1 \mapsto e_1, x_2 \mapsto e_2]$ and $\gamma'_1 = \gamma[x_1 \mapsto e'_1, x_2 \mapsto e'_2]$.
(D) We have the equality of γ_1, γ'_1 at level $\widehat{\delta}(\phi) \sqcup \phi_\gamma$ by Lemma **C.27**.
(E) Instantiate the equality for the second typing premise with $\widehat{\delta}(\phi) \sqcup \phi_\gamma$ and ϕ' and δ and γ_1, γ'_1 to obtain $\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}_1(e')) \sim \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'_1(e')) \in \widehat{\delta}(A) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi_1) \sqcup \widehat{\delta}(\phi) \sqcup \phi_\gamma [\phi'] [\Delta_0]$.
(F) This is the same as
 $[e_2/x_2][e_1/x_1]\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e')) \sim [e'_2/x_2][e'_1/x_1]\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e')) \in \widehat{\delta}(A) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi) \sqcup \widehat{\delta}(\phi_1) \sqcup \phi_\gamma [\phi'] [\Delta_0]$.
(G) We have by applying Lemma **C.24** twice and symmetrically along the evaluations in **10(f)iiA** that
 $\text{split } \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e)) \text{ into } \langle x_1, x_2 \rangle \text{ in } \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e')) \sim \text{split } \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e)) \text{ into } \langle x_1, x_2 \rangle \text{ in } \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e')) \in$
 $\widehat{\delta}(A) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi) \sqcup \widehat{\delta}(\phi_1) \sqcup \phi_\gamma [\phi'] [\Delta_0]$.
(11) Case: T-LAM
(a) We have $\Delta_0, \Delta; \Gamma \vdash \lambda(x.e) : A_1 \rightarrow A_2 \mid \circ$.
(b) Show that $\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(\lambda(x.e))) \sim \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(\lambda(x.e))) \in \widehat{\delta}(A_1 \rightarrow A_2) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\circ) \sqcup \phi_\gamma [\phi'] [\Delta_0]$.
(c) This is the same as $\lambda(x.\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e))) \sim \lambda(x.\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e))) \in \widehat{\delta}(A_1) \rightarrow \widehat{\delta}(A_2) \mid \phi_\gamma [\phi'] [\Delta_0]$.
(d) We have:
(i) $\lambda(x.\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e))) \mapsto^* \lambda(x.\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e))), \lambda(x.\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e))) \text{ val}$
(ii) $\lambda(x.\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e))) \mapsto^* \lambda(x.\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e))), \lambda(x.\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e))) \text{ val}$
(e) Suffices to show $\lambda(x.\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e))) \sim \lambda(x.\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e))) \in \widehat{\delta}(A_1) \rightarrow \widehat{\delta}(A_2) \mid \phi_\gamma [\phi'] [\Delta_0]$.

- (f) We have as premises that $\Delta_0, \Delta; \Gamma, x : A_1 \vdash e : A_2 \mid \circ$ and $\Delta_0, \Delta \vdash A_1$.
- (g) Apply the induction hypothesis to the typing premise in 11f to obtain $\Delta \Gamma, x : A_1 \gg_{\Delta_0}^{\phi'} e \sim e \in A_2 \mid \circ$.
- (h) Assume some $\phi'' \sqsubseteq_{\Delta_0} \phi'$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi'_1$ and $e_1 \text{ val}, e'_1 \text{ val}$ and $e_1 \sim e'_1 \in \widehat{\delta}(A_1) \mid \phi'_1 [\phi''] [\Delta_0]$.
- (i) Apply Lemma C.20 to $\Delta_0 \vdash \phi'$ to obtain $\Delta_0 \vdash \phi''$.
- (j) Suffices to show $\text{ap}(\lambda(x.\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e))); e_1) \sim \text{ap}(\lambda(x.\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e))); e'_1) \in \widehat{\delta}(A_2) \mid \phi'_1 \sqcup \phi_Y [\phi''] [\Delta_0]$.
- (k) Define $\gamma_1 = \gamma[x \mapsto e_1], \gamma'_1 = \gamma[x \mapsto e'_1]$.
- (l) We have γ_1, γ'_1 equal at security level $\phi'_1 \sqcup \phi_Y$ by Lemma C.27 and at observer level ϕ'' by Lemma C.29.
- (m) Instantiate 11g with $\phi'_1 \sqcup \phi_Y$ and ϕ'' and δ and γ_1, γ'_1 to obtain $\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}_1(e)) \sim \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'_1(e)) \in \widehat{\delta}(A_2) \mid \phi'_1 \sqcup \phi_Y [\phi''] [\Delta_0]$.
- (n) This is the same as $[e_1/x]\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e)) \sim [e'_1/x]\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e)) \in \widehat{\delta}(A_2) \mid \phi'_1 \sqcup \phi_Y [\phi''] [\Delta_0]$.
- (o) We have $\text{ap}(\lambda(x.\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e))); e_1) \mapsto [e_1/x]\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e))$ and $\text{ap}(\lambda(x.\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e))); e'_1) \mapsto [e'_1/x]\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e))$.
- (p) Apply Lemma C.24 twice symmetrically to 11n and each of the evaluations in 11o to obtain $\text{ap}(\lambda(x.\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e))); e_1) \sim \text{ap}(\lambda(x.\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e))); e'_1) \in \widehat{\delta}(A_2) \mid \phi'_1 \sqcup \phi_Y [\phi''] [\Delta_0]$.
- (12) Case: T-AP
- (a) We have $\Delta_0, \Delta; \Gamma \vdash \text{ap}(e; e_1) : A \mid \phi \sqcup \phi_1$.
- (b) Show that $\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(\text{ap}(e; e_1))) \sim \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(\text{ap}(e; e_1))) \in \widehat{\delta}(A) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi \sqcup \phi_1) \sqcup \phi_Y [\phi'] [\Delta_0]$.
- (c) This is the same as $\text{ap}(\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e)); \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e_1))) \sim \text{ap}(\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e)); \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e_1))) \in \widehat{\delta}(A) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi_1) \sqcup \widehat{\delta}(\phi) \sqcup \phi_Y [\phi'] [\Delta_0]$.
- (d) We have as premises of T-AP that $\Delta_0, \Delta; \Gamma \vdash e : A_1 \rightarrow A \mid \phi$ and $\Delta_0, \Delta; \Gamma \vdash e_1 : A_1 \mid \phi_1$.
- (e) By the induction hypothesis on the second premise, we have $\Delta \Gamma \gg_{\Delta_0}^{\phi'} e_1 \sim e_1 \in A_1 \mid \phi_1$.
- (f) Instantiating with ϕ_Y and ϕ' and δ and γ, γ' we have $\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e_1)) \sim \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e_1)) \in \widehat{\delta}(A_1) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi_1) \sqcup \phi_Y [\phi'] [\Delta_0]$.
- (g) Case on 12f. If $\widehat{\delta}(\phi_1) \sqcup \phi_Y \not\sqsubseteq_{\Delta_0} \phi'$ then we have $\widehat{\delta}(\phi_1) \sqcup \widehat{\delta}(\phi) \sqcup \phi_Y \not\sqsubseteq_{\Delta_0} \phi'$ by Lemma C.7.
- (h) Otherwise, we have:
- (i) $\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e_1)) \mapsto^* e'_1, \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e_1)) \mapsto^* e''_1, e'_1 \text{ val}, e''_1 \text{ val}$
- (ii) $e'_1 \sim e''_1 \in \widehat{\delta}(A_1) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi_1) \sqcup \phi_Y [\phi'] [\Delta_0]$
- (i) From 12(h)ii we have $e'_1 \sim e''_1 \in \widehat{\delta}(A_1) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi_1) \sqcup \phi_Y [\phi'] [\Delta_0]$.
- (j) By the induction hypothesis on the first premise, we have $\Delta \Gamma \gg_{\Delta_0}^{\phi'} e \sim e \in A_1 \rightarrow A \mid \phi$.
- (k) Instantiate with ϕ_Y and ϕ' and δ and γ, γ' to get $\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e)) \sim \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e)) \in \widehat{\delta}(A_1) \rightarrow \widehat{\delta}(A) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi) \sqcup \phi_Y [\phi'] [\Delta_0]$.
- (l) Case on 12k:
- (i) $\widehat{\delta}(\phi) \sqcup \phi_Y \not\sqsubseteq_{\Delta_0} \phi'$
Apply Lemma C.7 to this case and $\widehat{\delta}(\phi_1)$ to obtain $\widehat{\delta}(\phi_1) \sqcup \widehat{\delta}(\phi) \sqcup \phi_Y \not\sqsubseteq_{\Delta_0} \phi'$.
- (ii) $e_2 \sim e'_2 \in \widehat{\delta}(A_1) \rightarrow \widehat{\delta}(A) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi) \sqcup \phi_Y [\phi'] [\Delta_0]$
- (A) Where $\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e)) \mapsto e_2, \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e)) \mapsto^* e'_2, e_2 \text{ val}, e'_2 \text{ val}$.
- (B) Apply the equality for this case to 12i to obtain $\text{ap}(e_2; e'_1) \sim \text{ap}(e'_2; e'_1) \in \widehat{\delta}(A) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi_1) \sqcup \phi_Y \sqcup \widehat{\delta}(\phi) \sqcup \phi_Y [\phi'] [\Delta_0]$.
- (C) This is the same as $\text{ap}(e_2; e'_1) \sim \text{ap}(e'_2; e'_1) \in \widehat{\delta}(A) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi_1) \sqcup \widehat{\delta}(\phi) \sqcup \phi_Y [\phi'] [\Delta_0]$.
- (D) We have $\text{ap}(\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e)); \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e_1))) \mapsto^* \text{ap}(e_2; e'_1), \text{ap}(\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e)); \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e_1))) \mapsto^* \text{ap}(e'_2; e'_1)$ from 12(h)i and 12(l)iiA.

(E) Apply Lemma C.24 to 12(l)iiC and 12(l)iiD to obtain

$$\text{ap}(\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e)); \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e_1))) \sim \text{ap}(\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e)); \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e_1))) \in \widehat{\delta}(A) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi_1) \sqcup \widehat{\delta}(\phi) \sqcup \phi_\gamma [\phi'] [\Delta_0].$$

(13) Case: T-DEPLAM

(a) We have $\Delta_0, \Delta; \Gamma \vdash \Lambda(\alpha.e) : \forall(\alpha.A) \mid \circ$.

(b) Show that $\Lambda(\alpha.\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e))) \sim \Lambda(\alpha.\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e))) \in \forall(\alpha.\widehat{\delta}(A)) \mid \phi_\gamma [\phi'] [\Delta_0]$.

(c) We have:

(i) $\Lambda(\alpha.\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e))) \mapsto^* \Lambda(\alpha.\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e))), \Lambda(\alpha.\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e))) \text{ val}$

(ii) $\Lambda(\alpha.\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e))) \mapsto^* \Lambda(\alpha.\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e))), \Lambda(\alpha.\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e))) \text{ val}$

(d) Suffices to show $\Lambda(\alpha.\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e))) \sim \Lambda(\alpha.\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e))) \in \forall(\alpha.\widehat{\delta}(A)) \mid \phi_\gamma [\phi'] [\Delta_0]$.

(e) We have as a premise that $\Delta_0, \Delta, \alpha; \Gamma \vdash e : A \mid \circ$.

(f) Assume $\Delta_0 \vdash \phi$.

(g) Suffices to show $\Lambda(\alpha.\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e)))[\phi] \sim \Lambda(\alpha.\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e)))[\phi] \in [\phi/\alpha]\widehat{\delta}(A) \mid \phi_\gamma [\phi'] [\Delta_0]$.

(h) Define $\delta_1 = \delta[\alpha \mapsto \phi]$.

(i) Apply the induction hypothesis to 13e to obtain $\Delta, \alpha \Gamma \gg_{\Delta_0}^{\phi'} e \sim e \in A \mid \circ$.

(j) Instantiate with ϕ_γ and ϕ' and δ_1 and γ, γ' to get $\widehat{\delta}_1(\widehat{\gamma}(e)) \sim \widehat{\delta}_1(\widehat{\gamma}'(e)) \in \widehat{\delta}_1(A) \mid \phi_\gamma [\phi'] [\Delta_0]$.

(k) This is the same as $[\phi/\alpha]\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e)) \sim [\phi/\alpha]\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e)) \in [\phi/\alpha]\widehat{\delta}(A) \mid \phi_\gamma [\phi'] [\Delta_0]$.

(l) Observe that $\Lambda(\alpha.\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e)))[\phi] \mapsto [\phi/\alpha]\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e))$ and $\Lambda(\alpha.\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e)))[\phi] \mapsto [\phi/\alpha]\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e))$.

(m) Apply Lemma C.24 twice symmetrically to 13k and each of the evaluations in 13l to obtain

$$\Lambda(\alpha.\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e)))[\phi] \sim \Lambda(\alpha.\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e)))[\phi] \in [\phi/\alpha]\widehat{\delta}(A) \mid \phi_\gamma [\phi'] [\Delta_0].$$

(14) Case: T-DEPAP

(a) We have $\Delta_0, \Delta; \Gamma \vdash e[\phi_1] : [\phi_1/\alpha]A \mid \phi_2$.

(b) Show that $\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e))[\widehat{\delta}(\phi_1)] \sim \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e))[\widehat{\delta}(\phi_1)] \in [\widehat{\delta}(\phi_1)/\alpha]\widehat{\delta}(A) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi_2) \sqcup \phi_\gamma [\phi'] [\Delta_0]$.

(c) We have as premises $\Delta_0, \Delta; \Gamma \vdash e : \forall(\alpha.A) \mid \phi_2$ and $\Delta_0, \Delta \vdash \phi_1$.

(d) Apply the induction hypothesis to the typing premise to obtain $\Delta \Gamma \gg_{\Delta_0}^{\phi'} e \sim e \in \forall(\alpha.A) \mid \phi_2$.

(e) Instantiate with ϕ_γ and ϕ' and δ and γ, γ' to obtain

$$\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e)) \sim \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e)) \in \forall(\alpha.\widehat{\delta}(A)) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi_2) \sqcup \phi_\gamma [\phi'] [\Delta_0].$$

(f) Case on 14e:

(i) $\widehat{\delta}(\phi_2) \sqcup \phi_\gamma \not\sqsubseteq_{\Delta_0} \phi'$

Then we have the result immediately.

(ii) $e_1 \sim e'_1 \in \forall(\alpha.\widehat{\delta}(A)) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi_2) \sqcup \phi_\gamma [\phi'] [\Delta_0]$

(A) Where $\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e)) \mapsto^* e_1, \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e)) \mapsto^* e'_1, e_1 \text{ val}, e'_1 \text{ val}$.

(B) So we have $\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e))[\widehat{\delta}(\phi_1)] \mapsto^* e_1[\widehat{\delta}(\phi_1)], \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e))[\widehat{\delta}(\phi_1)] \mapsto^* e'_1[\widehat{\delta}(\phi_1)]$.

(C) Apply $\Delta_0 \vdash \widehat{\delta}(\phi_1)$ to the equality for this case to get

$$e_1[\widehat{\delta}(\phi_1)] \sim e'_1[\widehat{\delta}(\phi_1)] \in [\widehat{\delta}(\phi_1)/\alpha]\widehat{\delta}(A) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi_2) \sqcup \phi_\gamma [\phi'] [\Delta_0].$$

(D) Apply Lemma C.24 twice symmetrically to 14(f)iiC and each of the evaluations in 14(f)iiB to obtain

$$\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e))[\widehat{\delta}(\phi_1)] \sim \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e))[\widehat{\delta}(\phi_1)] \in [\widehat{\delta}(\phi_1)/\alpha]\widehat{\delta}(A) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi_2) \sqcup \phi_\gamma [\phi'] [\Delta_0].$$

□

Lemma C.34 (Symmetry of open exact equality). *If $\Delta \Gamma \gg_{\Delta_0}^{\phi'} e_1 \sim e_2 \in A \mid \phi$ then $\Delta \Gamma \gg_{\Delta_0}^{\phi'} e_2 \sim e_1 \in A \mid \phi$.*

PROOF. Proceed directly.

(1) Assume some $\Delta_0 \vdash \phi_\gamma$ and $\Delta_0 \vdash \phi'$ and $\delta : \Delta \rightsquigarrow \Delta_0$ and $\gamma \sim \gamma' \in \Gamma \mid \phi_\gamma [\phi'] [\Delta \rightsquigarrow \Delta_0]$.

(2) Apply Lemma C.30 to γ, γ' to obtain $\gamma' \sim \gamma \in \Gamma \mid \phi_\gamma [\phi'] [\Delta \rightsquigarrow \Delta_0]$.

- (3) Apply $\phi_\gamma, \phi', \delta,$ and γ', γ to our equality assumption to obtain

$$\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma'}(e_1)) \sim \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e_2)) \in \widehat{\delta}(A) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi) [\phi'] [\Delta_0]$$
- (4) Apply Lemma C.30 to this to obtain the result. □

Lemma C.35 (Transitivity of open exact equality). *If $\Delta \Gamma \gg_{\Delta_0}^{\phi'} e_1 \sim e_2 \in A \mid \phi$ and $\Delta \Gamma \gg_{\Delta_0}^{\phi'} e_2 \sim e_3 \in A \mid \phi$ then $\Delta \Gamma \gg_{\Delta_0}^{\phi'} e_1 \sim e_3 \in A \mid \phi$.*

PROOF. Proceed directly.

- (1) Assume some $\Delta_0 \vdash \phi_\gamma$ and $\Delta_0 \vdash \phi'$ and $\delta : \Delta \rightsquigarrow \Delta_0$ and $\gamma \sim \gamma' \in \Gamma \mid \phi_\gamma [\phi'] [\Delta \rightsquigarrow \Delta_0]$.
- (2) Apply Lemma C.32 to γ to obtain $\gamma \sim \gamma' \in \Gamma \mid \phi_\gamma [\phi'] [\Delta \rightsquigarrow \Delta_0]$.
- (3) Apply $\phi_\gamma, \phi', \delta,$ and γ, γ' to the first equality assumption to obtain

$$\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e_1)) \sim \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e_2)) \in \widehat{\delta}(A) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi) [\phi'] [\Delta_0]$$
- (4) Apply $\Delta_0 \vdash \phi', \phi_\gamma, \delta,$ and γ, γ' to the second equality assumption to obtain

$$\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e_2)) \sim \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma'}(e_3)) \in \widehat{\delta}(A) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi) [\phi'] [\Delta_0]$$
- (5) Apply Lemma C.31 to 3 and 4 to obtain $\widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma}(e_1)) \sim \widehat{\delta}(\widehat{\gamma'}(e_3)) \in \widehat{\delta}(A) \mid \widehat{\delta}(\phi) [\phi'] [\Delta_0]$. □

Corollary C.36 (Constant Function). *If we have $\Delta; \Gamma \vdash e : [A_1 \cdot \phi_1] \rightarrow [A_2 \cdot \phi_2] \mid \circ$ and c val and $\phi_1 \not\sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$ then $\circ \Gamma \gg_{\Delta}^{\phi_2} e \sim \lambda(x.\text{ap}(e; c)) \in [A_1 \cdot \phi_1] \rightarrow [A_2 \cdot \phi_2] \mid \circ$.*

PROOF. Proceed by stepping through the logical relation.

- (1) Assume $\Delta; \Gamma \vdash e : [A_1 \cdot \phi_1] \rightarrow [A_2 \cdot \phi_2] \mid \circ$ and c val and $\phi_1 \not\sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$.
- (2) Assume some $\Delta \vdash \phi_\gamma$ and $\Delta \vdash \phi_2$ and $\delta : \circ \rightsquigarrow \Delta$ and $\gamma \sim \gamma' \in \Gamma \mid \phi_\gamma [\phi_2] [\circ \rightsquigarrow \Delta]$.
- (3) Suffices to show $\widehat{\gamma}(e) \sim \lambda(x.\text{ap}(\widehat{\gamma'}(e); c)) \in [A_1 \cdot \phi_1] \rightarrow [A_2 \cdot \phi_2] \mid \phi_\gamma [\phi_2] [\Delta]$.
- (4) Assume some $\phi'_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$ and e_1 val, e'_1 val and $e_1 \sim e'_1 \in [A_1 \cdot \phi_1] \mid \phi'_1 [\phi'_2] [\Delta]$ where $\Delta \vdash \phi'_1$.
- (5) Suffices to show $\text{ap}(\widehat{\gamma}(e); e_1) \sim \text{ap}(\lambda(x.\text{ap}(\widehat{\gamma'}(e); c)); e'_1) \in [A_2 \cdot \phi_2] \mid \phi'_1 \sqcup \phi_\gamma [\phi'_2] [\Delta]$.
- (6) Apply Lemma C.9 to $\phi_1 \not\sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$ and $\phi'_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$ to obtain $\phi_1 \not\sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'_2$.
- (7) Observe that from $\phi_1 \not\sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi'_2$ we have $!e_1 \sim !c \in A_1 \mid \phi_1 [\phi'_2] [\Delta]$.
- (8) From this we have $e_1 \sim c \in [A_1 \cdot \phi_1] \mid \circ [\phi'_2] [\Delta]$.
- (9) So $e_1 \sim c \in [A_1 \cdot \phi_1] \mid \circ [\phi'_2] [\Delta]$ from e_1 val, c val.
- (10) Apply Theorem C.33 to the typing assumption in 1 to obtain

$$\circ \Gamma \gg_{\Delta}^{\phi_2} e \sim e \in [A_1 \cdot \phi_1] \rightarrow [A_2 \cdot \phi_2] \mid \circ.$$
- (11) Instantiate 10 with 2 to obtain $\widehat{\gamma}(e) \sim \widehat{\gamma'}(e) \in [A_1 \cdot \phi_1] \rightarrow [A_2 \cdot \phi_2] \mid \phi_\gamma [\phi_2] [\Delta]$.
- (12) Case on 11.
- (13) If $\phi_\gamma \not\sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$ then by Lemma C.9 $\phi_\gamma \not\sqsubseteq \phi'_2$ and we have the result immediately by Lemma C.7.
- (14) Otherwise, we have:
 - (a) $\widehat{\gamma}(e) \mapsto^* e_2, \widehat{\gamma'}(e) \mapsto^* e'_2, e_2$ val, e'_2 val
 - (b) $e_2 \sim e'_2 \in [A_1 \cdot \phi_1] \rightarrow [A_2 \cdot \phi_2] \mid \phi_\gamma [\phi_2] [\Delta]$
- (15) Instantiate 14b with $\phi'_2 \sqsubseteq_{\Delta} \phi_2$ and $\Delta \vdash \circ$ and e_1 val, c val and 9 to obtain

$$\text{ap}(e_2; e_1) \sim \text{ap}(e'_2; c) \in [A_2 \cdot \phi_2] \mid \phi_\gamma [\phi'_2] [\Delta].$$
- (16) We have that:
 - (a) $\text{ap}(\widehat{\gamma}(e); e_1) \mapsto^* \text{ap}(e_2; e_1)$
 - (b) $\text{ap}(\lambda(x.\text{ap}(\widehat{\gamma'}(e); c)); e'_1) \mapsto^* \text{ap}(\widehat{\gamma'}(e); c) \mapsto^* \text{ap}(e'_2; c)$, since we know $\widehat{\gamma'}(e), c$ val are closed

(17) Apply Lemma C.24 to 15 and 16 to obtain

$$\text{ap}(\widehat{\gamma}(e); e_1) \sim \text{ap}(\lambda(x.\text{ap}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e); c)); e'_1) \in [A_2 \cdot \phi_2] \mid \phi_Y [\phi'_2] [\Delta].$$

(18) Apply Lemma C.27 to this equality and $\Delta \vdash \phi'_1$ to obtain

$$\text{ap}(\widehat{\gamma}(e); e_1) \sim \text{ap}(\lambda(x.\text{ap}(\widehat{\gamma}'(e); c)); e'_1) \in [A_2 \cdot \phi_2] \mid \phi'_1 \sqcup \phi_Y [\phi'_2] [\Delta].$$

□

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